

D5.2

Report on the Framework Integration and Demonstrator Status (M39)

PSNC

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Abstract

This document is a report on the status of the work package 5 activities regarding the set-up and maintenance of the continuous integration tools and processes that support and guide the integration and release of the DATAMITE framework. Furthermore, it covers the activities related to the six project use case demonstrators' developments, integration and testing as well as training material development.

Keywords

Framework, demonstrator, integration, pilots, tests, pipeline, training, feedback

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R*

Dissemination level

PU Public, fully open. e.g., website

✓

CL Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

SEN Confidential to DATAMITE project and Commission Services

* Deliverable types:

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMI	Advanced Metering Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
CAPEX	CAPital Expenditure
CD	Continuous Delivery
CDO	Chief Data (Strategy) Officer
CI	Continuous Integration
CRM	Customer Relationship Management
CRUD	Create, Read, Update, Delete
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DIHs	Digital Innovation Hubs
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DSLAM	Digital Subscriber Line Access Multiplexer
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EC	European Commission
EDC	Eclipse Dataspace Components
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicle
FTTH	Fiber-to-the-Home
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
IT	Information Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MDM	Meter Data Management
OLAP	Online Analytical Processing
OLTP	Online Transaction Processing
OPEX	OPERating EXPense
PoC	Proof-of-Concept
RES	Renewable Energy Source
RTU	Remote Terminal Unit
SCADA	Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition
SQL	Structured Query Language

VDSL	Very high-speed Digital Subscriber Line
VM	Virtual Machine
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This document provides a comprehensive overview of the final status and significant progress achieved within Work Package 5 (WP5), which has been strategically dedicated to the integration and subsequent deployment of the various system components constituting to the DATAMITE framework. The successful execution of this work package is based on continued effort across three fundamental pillars: the selection and application of appropriate tools and technologies, the meticulous design and implementation of a resilient CI/CD pipeline, and the establishment of clear, repeatable procedural guidelines. These pillars ensured not just the current functionality of the DATAMITE framework, but also its inherent adaptability and maintainability for future research and development trajectories.

The refinement of the DATAMITE framework with the Use Case Demonstrators accessible to a broader community led to exhausting test scenarios and finalisation of training planning. The culmination of WP5's efforts therefore signifies the successful transformation of discrete research components into an integrated, validated, and deployable framework, prepared for real-world impact and continued academic research exploration.

Each of the Pilots was an opportunity to perform activities grouped into:

- Test Scenarios
- Solution implementation
- Training materials
- Test Campaign
- Performance and usability with Validation KPIs

By successfully aligning hardware and software components, the team has created a robust architecture that supports deployment across varied operational contexts. In parallel, a training curriculum has been finalised, ensuring that end users receive targeted instruction which accelerates proficiency and adoption. The verification procedures, including functional, performance, and security tests, have confirmed requirements met with the integrated system.

The work described in this document is the continuation of deliverable D5.1 submitted at month 26 complementing it with the final version of the Framework and use cases component descriptions.

1. Introduction

DATAMITE is designed to equip European enterprises with a modular, open-source, multi-domain framework for data monetisation, interoperability, trading and exchange. The solution is delivered as software components, training resources and business-oriented materials, enabling the enhancement of data quality, comply with FAIR principles and to acquire both technical and commercial competencies through the project's open-source form.

Internally, these tools render data more trustworthy and reliable, thereby supporting downstream applications such as AI.

Externally, by keeping data owners in control, DATAMITE creates new revenue streams and fosters interaction with a broader ecosystem of stakeholders. Its architecture also supports DIHs in onboarding SMEs, especially low-tech firms, into the data economy, acting as a catalyst for data-driven growth across Europe's productive fabric.

WP5, titled "Integration, Demonstration, and Validation", serves as the primary centre for combining the progress from other technical work packages, ensuring both compatibility and coherence. This WP emphasises the smooth integration and deployment of the DATAMITE framework. To support this initiative, WP5 is tasked with providing and sustaining the requisite tools and methodologies, which include a robust repository and extensive CI/CD pipelines, thereby facilitating integration and thorough testing. Among the WP aims are: the continuous integration of technical advancements from other work packages (O5.1); the preparation and validation of Data Tech Training Materials within the framework of pilot programs (O5.2); and the preparation, deployment, demonstration, validation, and evaluation of the DATAMITE framework within these pilot contexts (O5.3).

The main aspect of fulfilling the WP5's objectives is the creation and implementation of six use case demonstrators, which are constructed on the DATAMITE framework. These demonstrators act as a validation platform, illustrating the framework's capabilities and applicability in both real-world and research environments. The outcomes and insights gained from these demonstrations will be vital for exploitation and dissemination activities, while also offering critical evaluation and validation feedback to guide ongoing development efforts.

1.1. Deliverable Purpose and Scope

The Grant Agreement specifies that the deliverable must comprise a *report on status of the developments and releases of components' integration and pilots, training material and test campaign*.

Accordingly, this document serves to present the current state of WP5. It summarises the activities carried out under Task 5.1, which focus on the implementation and integration of the DATAMITE components, and details the progress achieved in the deployment of pilots as described in Task 5.2. The report outlines also the training-preparation work performed within Task 5.3, highlighting how the generated training material has been used to gather practical feedback and to pinpoint optimisation opportunities. Finally, Task 5.4 is addressed through an overview of the test campaigns that have been conducted, illustrating how they contribute to refining the system based on real-world usage.

1.2. Document Structure

This deliverable is broken down into the following sections:

- **Executive Summary:** A summary of the contents and main findings are provided.
- **Section 1 Introduction** provides the deliverable's general context, dependencies, and structure.
- **Section 2 DATAMITE Framework Integration** carries out the essential CI/CD strategy for the DATAMITE framework, focusing on tools and processes to ensure all framework components are effectively integrated and deployed systematically. Further, we will explore the updates to the specific technologies, pipelines, and procedures mandatory for the DATAMITE CI/CD process.
- **Section 3 Trainings** describes the trainings and courses performed during the project.
- **Section 4 Use Case Demonstrators** describes the final state of deployment of solutions integrating the second iteration of created components. This part also refers to results of the conduction of internal and external beta tests that contributed to the refinement and optimisation in comparison to the last iteration.
- **Section 5 Conclusions** summarises the work completed.

1.3. Document Dependencies

This document is the last iteration of the deliverable submitted at M26 and reported the outcomes before modifications required after validation provided in initial iteration. D5.2 shows the **final results** of the DATAMITE Framework Integration and Demonstrator Status.

The work described follows updates in the architecture of the project captured in deliverable “D1.4 Requirements and architecture” and is aligned with the data management plans of the pilots described in the deliverables “D7.7 and D7.8 Data Management Plan and Data Protection Plan”.

2. DATAMITE Framework Integration

This section details the continuous integration and continuous deployment (CI/CD) tools and processes established to ensure a seamless integration and systematic release of the DATAMITE framework. It covers the entire framework, ensuring that all components and tools are effectively integrated. The process adheres to well-defined procedures and an agreed-upon release plan, fostering consistency and reliability. By adopting this structured approach, a solid foundation is being established for a cohesive and efficient integration process, enabling the successful deployment and evolution of the DATAMITE framework.

2.1. Tools & technologies

2.1.1. GitLab Repository

GitLab serves as a source code repository where developers openly and collaboratively store, manage, and track changes to the codebase. It integrates CI/CD pipelines, called GitLab Runners, to automate testing, building, and deployment tasks. A centralised version control system is crucial for maintaining consistency, managing code changes, and automatically triggering CI/CD pipelines when new code is pushed. In the DATAMITE framework, the GitLab repository¹.

This GitLab instance and the GitLab Runners are hosted by ECL and provided as part of the DATAMITE infrastructure. Other tools and templates, such as the *Eclipse Secretsmanager* or *BuildKit* and its templates (explained below as part of the DockerHub process), are provided as part of the ECL infrastructure for DATAMITE as well.

All the data related to GitLab and DATAMITE is stored in Europe.

2.1.2. DockerHub Account

DockerHub is a cloud-based registry for storing, sharing, and managing Docker images. Developers upload prebuilt container images to DockerHub for easy access during deployment. It provides a centralised platform for hosting container images used in CI/CD pipelines, enabling automated builds and ensuring consistent deployments across environments. In DATAMITE, a DockerHub account² is used to manage the relevant Docker images. CI builds include a template which consumes services such as BuildKit and the Secretsmanager. While BuildKit is used to build Docker images, the Secretsmanager is a secrets store used to push Docker images to DockerHub.

2.1.3. Virtual Machine (VM)

A virtual machine simulates a physical computing environment and is used to host applications and services during the CI/CD process. VMs are used to create isolated and controlled environments for building, testing, and deploying applications, ensuring consistency across

¹ [Explore groups · GitLab](#)

² [Explore Docker's Container Image Repository | Docker Hub](#)

various stages of the pipeline. Moreover, the VM requires proper network configuration to ensure access to the internet and seamless communication between all CI/CD components.

2.1.4. Docker and Docker Swarm

Docker is a platform that packages applications and their dependencies into containers, making them portable and consistent across environments. This leads to a Docker Swarm deployment. Docker Swarm is Docker's native orchestration tool, enabling the clustering and management of multiple Docker nodes for running services at scale. Finally, the DATAMITE framework provides configuration details, and commands needed to deploy and manage the infrastructure services. Figure 1 depicts DATAMITE's Docker Swarm architecture. Secure Shell (ssh) between manager and workers is needed for the setup script. Additionally, besides the Swarm implementation, DATAMITE also deploys the framework on Kubernetes.

Figure 1: Docker Swarm architecture

2.2. CI/CD Pipeline

2.2.1. Runners and stages

The CI/CD pipeline for the DATAMITE project leverages runners and defined stages to automate the development, testing, and deployment processes. Below is a detailed explanation of the configuration.

2.2.1.1. Runners in the DATAMITE Eclipse Repository

The runner pipelines are already enabled in the DATAMITE Eclipse repository. Runners act as agents that execute the CI/CD jobs defined in the pipeline, enabling automated builds, tests, and deployments.

2.2.1.2. Pipeline Stages

The pipeline consists of the following key stages:

Test (Optional): This stage is designed for testing purposes, allowing teams to validate code or configurations before proceeding to the next steps.

Build: During the build stage, the following operations are performed:

- A Docker image is built based on the project configuration.
- The pipeline authenticates to DockerHub.
- The built image is pushed to the DATAMITE DockerHub repository for centralised management.

Deploy/Notify: The deploy/notify stage involves deploying the application to the relevant infrastructure. The operations include:

- Pulling the Docker image from DockerHub.
- Deploying the image to the designated infrastructure, such as a virtual machine (VM).

2.2.2. CI/CD Procedure Flow

The CI/CD process for the DATAMITE project has been designed to streamline the building, deployment, and management of Docker images across the infrastructure. Below is a detailed description of the CI/CD workflow, which is triggered when new code is pushed:

2.2.2.1. Building the Docker Image

The pipeline process begins with building a Docker image using Eclipse Runners. These runners execute the necessary steps to compile, package, and prepare the image for deployment.

2.2.2.2. Pushing the Docker Image to DockerHub

Once the Docker image is built, it is pushed to DockerHub under the DATAMITE project's dedicated account. This centralised repository ensures that all project-related Docker images are accessible and consistently managed.

2.2.2.3. Triggering Operations via the DATAMITE Infrastructure Project

Infrastructure project is a Gitlab Datamite project (support tools) used to setup and create the whole infrastructure for Docker Swarm cluster. It's used by the pilots to create the Docker Swarm cluster and startup the whole services. Any project within the DATAMITE ecosystem that executes its CI/CD pipeline can trigger a CI/CD job. This project, which is based on an ubuntu VM, is responsible for performing all necessary operations, as shown on Figure 2.

2.2.2.4. Remote Operations on the Client Server

The triggered job in the infrastructure project establishes an SSH connection with the remote virtual machine (VM). Through this connection, the following operations are executed:

1. Pulling the newly built Docker image from DockerHub.
2. Executing the required Docker commands to configure the image.
3. Restarting services to apply the updates and ensure the proper functioning of the system.

This streamlined CI/CD procedure ensures efficient deployment and management of Docker images, promoting consistency and reducing manual intervention across the DATAMITE project's infrastructure, as Figure 2 depicts.

Figure 2: CI/CD Infrastructure

2.3. Procedures

To optimise the CI/CD pipeline and avoid unnecessary image builds, we have established a set of rules to configure the pipeline effectively. These rules ensure that jobs are triggered only when specific conditions are met, reducing overhead and streamlining processes. Rules of CI/CD

pipelines are defined in the corresponding yml file of each project. Their overall scope and use is explained in the sections below.

2.3.1. Rules for Specific Branches

This rule ensures that jobs are triggered only when working with designated branches. For example, the following condition limits job execution to the main branch:

```
if: $CI_COMMIT_BRANCH == "main"
```

Similarly, the following one allows support for the develop branch with the condition:

```
if: $CI_COMMIT_BRANCH == "develop"
```

2.3.2. Trigger for Merge Requests

This rule retains the condition for merge request events, ensuring jobs are triggered whenever a merge request is created or updated:

```
if: $CI_PIPELINE_SOURCE == "merge_request_event"
when: always
```

2.3.3. Tag-Specific Triggers

Jobs can also be triggered based on specific version tags. This is useful for creating version-specific builds:

```
if: $CI_COMMIT_TAG
when: always
```

2.3.4. Environment-Specific Rules

Conditions can be added to trigger jobs for specific environments, such as `production`. This enables tailored actions for different deployment environments:

```
if: $CI_ENVIRONMENT_NAME == "production"
when: always
```

2.3.5. Combining Conditions

For more precise control, combined logic can be used. For instance, the following condition triggers jobs only for merge requests targeting the main branch:

```
if: $CI_COMMIT_BRANCH == "main" && $CI_PIPELINE_SOURCE ==
"merge_request_event" when: always
```

These rules enhance the CI/CD pipeline's efficiency by limiting job execution to relevant scenarios. By applying these conditions, we reduce unnecessary builds, streamline resource usage, and ensure the pipeline aligns with project requirements.

2.3.6. Templates

DATAMITE has a template project that helps in centralised and consistent job management. Specifically, the "data-support-tools/GitLab CI Templates" contains jobs and pipelines that can be reused. This project contains a main file, which works as an entry point to the procedures, and a directory called "jobs" which contains all the necessary jobs of the pipeline. The main categories and a concise description are presented here:

- build: 4 jobs handling image building and tagging for different branches and releases.
- cleanup: has 2 jobs for cleaning old docker images
- deploy: includes jobs that update docker image tags and deploys changes based on commits.
- notify: triggers another pipeline when changes are pushed to the develop branch.
- release: automates versioning for the main branch.

This structure allows to define jobs in a centralised and consistent way, while reducing the need for code duplication. Moreover, it showcases flexibility in updating images, as different rules and jobs are set for each type of update and commit.

To use the template, users can include the template project in their CI/CD `.yaml` file, as well as adjust necessary variables, such as the name of the docker image. Furthermore, the template project and its use are described in the corresponding training [course](#) “How to use CI/CD procedures in DATAMITE”.

Finally, for a detailed step-by-step development guide, readers are referred to the DATAMITE Wiki documentation^{3,4,5}.

2.4. Framework Installation

This section provides an overview of the installation process of the DATAMITE framework and outlines the main steps required to deploy and configure its components. The installation guidance describes the prerequisites, deployment environment, and configuration requirements necessary to successfully set up the framework. It is intended to support users and administrators in preparing and operating the DATAMITE infrastructure. For a detailed step-by-step installation guide, configuration instructions, and additional technical information, readers are referred to the DATAMITE Wiki documentation⁶. Finally, for a detailed step-by-step user experience in DATAMITE framework, readers are referred to component's documentation⁷.

³ [Versioning, Branching & Changelog Guidelines · Wiki · DATAMITE project · GitLab](#)

⁴ [Branching and Release Workflow · Wiki · DATAMITE project · GitLab](#)

⁵ [CI/CD Guidelines · Wiki · DATAMITE project · GitLab](#)

⁶ [How to Setup the Framework for local deployment · Wiki · DATAMITE project · GitLab](#)

⁷ [Components Documentation · Wiki · DATAMITE project · GitLab](#)

3. Trainings

This section describes the DATAMITE approach towards the training materials and courses as part of the activities conducted under Task 5.3 in the time period of months 27-39. This task, in collaboration with WP2, WP3, and WP4, is responsible for the preparation of the online training materials associated with modules from WP2 and WP3 that will form the *DATA Tech training material*.

The list of the courses performed has been identified, as well as the timeline:

No.	Course name	Company name	Form of the courses	Start date	Delivery date	Language
1	How to install and use the DATAMITE framework from the user's perspective	CERTH & ITI	Documentation & dedicated meetings	2025-02-01	2025-02-28	English
2	Data governance tools or data governance and quality tools	ITI	Series of short videos uploaded in the Youtube channel in the DATAMITE training pills list	2025-02-01	2025-03-26	English
3	How to deploy and use DATAMITE framework: a step-by-step guide	OTE	Wiki page	2025-02-01	2025-03-28	English
4	Integration of the different modules of DATAMITE in infrastructures (cloud, local or "on premises" deployment)	GiDITEK	Official documentation (internal)	2025-03-20	Continuous	Spanish
5	Enhancing MISTRAL visibility through DATAMITE	CINECA	Live webinar	2025-02-01	2026-01-15	English
6	Pontus-X marketplace course	PSNC	Moodle course with a series of short movies	2026-01-01	2026-03-06	English
7	Publication/User Instructions	1001 Lakes	Publication/ User Instructions	2025-04-01	2025-04-28	English

8	Introduction to Data Spaces for Data Providers	HEDNO	Moodle course	2025-03-15	2026-02-28	English
9	Introduction to Data Spaces for Data Consumers	HEDNO	Moodle course	2025-02-15	2026-02-28	English
10	How to use CI/CD procedures in DATAMITE to commit the codes, from the developer's perspective	CERTH	Moodle course	2025-03-26	2025-12-20	English
11	Unlocking Open Source Potential: DATAMITE's open source guide and how you can contribute	ECL	Live webinar	2025-11-27	2025-09-27	English
12	Data Harmonisation Tools	ICCS	Manual, PPT, Video	2025-02-01	2025-06-17	English
13	DATAMITE Data Preparation and Sharing in the Data Spaces	E-REDES	Series of short movies; Slide deck with Ad hoc presentations	2025-02-01	2025-09-30	English & Portuguese
14	Getting to know the fairness data tool	UCC	Series of short movies	2025-06-21	2025-10-27	English
15	Transforming data into impactful products	CERTH	Moodle course	2025-06-21	2025-10-27	English
16	DATAMITE: Sharing Energy Data through Data Spaces for Data-Driven Tools	HEDNO & CERTH	Live webinar	2026-03-16	2026-03-23	Greek

Table 1. The list of the courses performed

1. How to install and use the DATAMITE framework from the user's perspective

Link: [How to Setup the Framework for local deployment · Wiki · DATAMITE project · GitLab](#)⁸

This course explains how to configure and deploy the DATAMITE Framework services on an existing Docker Swarm cluster. It focuses on setting up environment variables and adjusting the Frontend configuration.

3. Setting up the Environment Variables

This section defines the **main IPs** and **connection URLs** required for local deployment.

Here you can find the variables that must be set according to your IP or domain configuration. In the example below, all external URLs are assigned a local IP address. These variables can also be configured using domain names.

Make sure to replace the example IP addresses with your own IP or domain names before deploying.

common.env

The `common.env` file contains **shared, non-sensitive configuration** used by all services in the Docker Swarm deployment. Unlike `dev.env`, this file does not include credentials, passwords, or secrets. Instead, it defines common hostnames, ports, service identifiers, client IDs, and general deployment settings that are the same across environments. Since it only contains generic configuration, it can safely be versioned and shared within the repository.

Typical examples of variables defined in `common.env` include Docker Compose settings (`COMPOSE_PROJECT_NAME`, `COMPOSE_FILE`), service hostnames (`ATLAS_HOSTNAME`, `POSTGRES_HOSTNAME`, `STREAMING_HOSTNAME`), exposed ports (`MINIO_EXT_PORT`, `FRONTEND_EXT_PORT`, `TRINO_EXT_PORT`), database names (`STREAMING_DB_DATABASE`, `KPI_LIB_DATABASE`), and authentication client identifiers (`KC_DATAMITE_REALM`, `KC_FRONTEND_CLIENT_ID`, `BACKOFFICE_CLIENT_ID`). These variables provide consistent naming and networking conventions across all deployed services without exposing any sensitive information.

```
# Minio external URL (Note that when a domain is configured, there is no need to specify the port)
MINIO_EXTERNAL_URL=<local IP or Domain>:9000
```

Figure 3: Course “How to install and use the DATAMITE framework from the user's perspective”

2. Data governance tools or data governance and quality tools

Link: [DATAMITE training pills](#)⁹

This course provides a series of video training pills describing the main functionalities regarding Data Governance, Data Quality and Data anonymisation. Its goal is that the users can consume these videos, which are completely focused on concrete functionalities, and have a fast and good understanding of how to use the framework to this purpose. The pills that have been produced cover the data ingestion, governance, quality and anonymisation areas, namely:

- Data Ingestion & Discovery
 - Introduction to Data Ingestion in DATAMITE
 - Bulk upload
 - Streaming upload

⁸ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/groups/eclipse-research-labs/datamite-project/-/wikis/How-to-Setup-de-Framework-for-local-deployment>

⁹ https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLZhK5xWz5r6L3j41hb_XUnYiIh0gmZ6o

- Data Base Discovery
 - Data Base Queries
- Data Governance
 - Introduction to Data Governance in DATAMITE
 - Defining new Glossaries and terms
 - Introducing the Data Catalogue
 - Enriching data
 - Searching datasets in the Catalogue
- Data Quality
 - Introduction to Data Quality in DATAMITE
 - Basic Quality KPIs
 - Creating new user defined rules
 - Modifying existing rules
 - (Re) Evaluating User Defined Rules
- Data Anonymisation
 - Introduction to Data Anonymisation in DATAMITE
 - Anonymisation Techniques

Figure 4 and Figure 5 show views of one of this training pills, the one for creating new user defined rules, and of the list in DATAMITE YouTube channel where the training pills are available.

Figure 4: View of the "Creating new user defined rules" training video pill.

Figure 5: View of the Youtube list of DATAMITE Training Pills.

3. How to deploy and use DATAMITE framework: a step-by-step guide

Link: [How to Setup the Framework for local deployment](#) · [Wiki](#) · [DATAMITE project](#) · [GitLab](#)¹⁰

This Wiki page explains how to configure and deploy the DATAMITE Framework services on an existing Docker Swarm cluster.

Eclipse Research Labs / DATAMITE project / Wiki / [How to Setup the Framework for local deployment](#)

How to Setup the Framework for local deployment

Last edited by **Antoni Gimeno** 3 weeks ago

Setup the Framework for local deployment

This guide explains how to configure and deploy the **Datamite Framework** services on an **existing Docker Swarm cluster**.
It focuses on setting up environment variables and adjusting the FrontEnd configuration.

Figure 6: Course "How to deploy and use DATAMITE framework: a step-by-step guide"

4. Integration of the different modules of DATAMITE in infrastructures (cloud, local or "on premises" deployment)

The development of the documentation, as well as the delivery of the demonstration sessions, is carried out through internal sessions, as they are specifically intended for users within the group.

¹⁰ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/groups/eclipse-research-labs/datamite-project/-/wikis/How-to-Setup-de-Framework-for-local-deployment>

Dedicated technical documentation has been produced and is made available exclusively to users from departments responsible for deploying the framework, either in standalone configurations or in shared environments.

The following section includes selected screenshots from the documentation generated for this purpose.

Figure 7: Course “Integration of the different modules of DATAMITE in infrastructures (cloud, local or “on premises” deployment)” – main view

Figure 8: Course “Integration of the different modules of DATAMITE in infrastructures (cloud, local or “on premises” deployment)” - introduction

4.2 Archivo dev.env

Este archivo contiene las variables específicas del entorno de despliegue, principalmente las direcciones IP o dominios de la maquina y el protocolo de acceso. Estas variables SI deben modificarse en cualquier caso.

Variable	Valor de Ejemplo	Descripcion
DEPLOYMENT_EXTERNAL_IP	poc-datamite.grupogimeno.com	IP o dominio publico del servidor donde se despliega la plataforma
DEPLOYMENT_EXTERNAL_AUTH_IP	dev-logon.grupogimeno.com	IP o dominio del servidor de autenticacion (Keycloak)
DEPLOYMENT_EXTERNAL_PROTOCOL	https	Protocolo de acceso externo: 'http' o 'https'

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Figure 9: Course "Integration of the different modules of DATAMITE in infrastructures (cloud, local or "on premises" deployment)" - example

7. Configuración del Proxy Inverso con Nginx

Nginx actúa como proxy inverso que recibe las peticiones HTTPS del exterior y las redirige al servicio interno correspondiente según la ruta de la URL. Esta configuración es necesaria cuando se accede a DATAMITE a través de un dominio público o cuando se quiere centralizar el punto de entrada a la plataforma.

7.1 Bloque server (HTTPS / SSL)

A continuación se muestra la configuración completa del bloque `server` de Nginx. Adapte los valores resaltados a su propio entorno:

```
server {
    listen 443 ssl;
    listen [::]:443 ssl;
    server_name poc-datamite.grupogimeno.com; # <-- Su dominio

    # Certificados SSL
    ssl_certificate /etc/ssl/private/grupogimeno.pem;
    ssl_certificate_key /etc/ssl/private/grupogimeno.com.key;
    ssl_session_tickets off;
    ssl_dhparam /etc/nginx/dhparams.pem;

    # Logs
    error_log /var/log/nginx/poc-datamite_error.log warn;
    access_log /var/log/nginx/poc-datamite_access.log;
    server_name_in_redirect off;

    # Frontend (raiz)
    location / {
        proxy_set_header Host $host;
        proxy_set_header X-Real-IP $remote_addr;
```

Figure 10: "Course Integration of the different modules of DATAMITE in infrastructures (cloud, local or "on premises" deployment)" - configuration

5. Enhancing MISTRAL visibility through DATAMITE

Link: [Enhancing MISTRAL Demos](#)¹¹

As part of our training activities, we held an engaging webinar focused on navigating the complexities of exploiting meteorological data for emerging business opportunities (Figure 11). The session explored how the DATAMITE framework can overcome these challenges, with a particular focus on its ability to disseminate data assets seamlessly across various European portals. Another notable technical feature was the demonstration of the quality evaluator module, which enables users to swiftly identify and resolve sensor data anomalies, thereby ensuring a high level of accuracy (Figure 11). To maintain audience engagement, we hosted a live quiz during the webinar. Besides, the slides from the webinar have been uploaded to the following URL: ([Presentation](#)). We have also created tutorial videos to provide new users with a hands-on guide to familiarising themselves with the related modules of the DATAMITE framework ([DEMOS](#)),

Figure 11: Pilot 6 Webinar and video demos of DATAMITE application

¹¹ [https://gitlab.hpc.cineca.it/bchandr1/datamite/-/tree/main/DEMO_D5.4/demos?ref_type=he
ads](https://gitlab.hpc.cineca.it/bchandr1/datamite/-/tree/main/DEMO_D5.4/demos?ref_type=heads)

6. Pontus-X marketplace course

Link: [Pontus-X marketplace course](#)¹²

The “Pontus-X marketplace course” main goal is to introduce audience to the Pontus-X ecosystem and provide information and description how DATAMITE integrates with it.

Figure 12: Course “Pontus-X marketplace course”

The course itself is divided into following main sections:

- Pontus-X and DATAMITE – introduction of both systems and definition of main concepts.
- Publishing assets on Pontus-X – shows different types of components within Pontus-X, introduces onboarding process and a concept of a wallet, finally a video is shown publishing asset on Pontus-X network through the Pontus-X marketplace GUI and programmatically.
- DATAMITE overview – introduces basic concepts of DATAMITE like uploading datasets, creation of data products and specifying its metadata. Videos showcasing various integration with the framework are included.
- DATAMITE Pontus-X integration – provides basic information about the plugin system for DATAMITE’s data sharing module for various target data space ecosystems, in particular Pontus-X. A video showcasing publishing a Data Product as a new asset in Pontus-X is shown.

7. Publication/User Instructions

¹² <https://moodle.datamite.psnk.pl/course/view.php?id=18>

Link: [Webinar | Creating data products from scratch with DATAMITE](#)¹³

Link: [Webinar | Transforming data into impactful products](#)¹⁴

These webinars, delivered by CERTH and ITI, provide training that guides users in transforming raw data into impactful, GDPR-compliant data products using the DATAMITE framework. The training emphasizes how data products can be enriched with high-quality metadata to ensure they are FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable), as well as secure and easily shareable.

Through practical, user-oriented walkthroughs, the videos demonstrate real-world scenarios and workflows. Overall, the training presents a comprehensive end-to-end pipeline, covering the full process from data ingestion and transformation to the creation of compliant, high-quality, and auditable data products.

The following figures are examples of contents in these training webinars.

Figure 13: Screenshot of the training video on how to create a data product.

¹³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=obk82sWchzo>

¹⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yQfasr2v8xA>

Figure 14: Screenshot of how to add a policy to the data product.

8. Introduction to Data Spaces for Data Providers

Link: [Introduction to Data Spaces for Data Providers¹⁵](https://moodle.datamite.psnc.pl/course/view.php?id=19)

The course “*Introduction to Data Spaces for Data Providers*” (see Figure 15) is primarily aimed at data providers and other energy stakeholders with potential interest in trustworthy and efficient data sharing. The learning goals of this course are a) to spread knowledge about the concept of data spaces to a wider audience and b) to assist interested parties in data sharing. The course offers details about data spaces, their benefits and the associated roles of participants in the ecosystem. The DATAMITE platform is used to showcase the preparation of data products and to demonstrate the sharing of metadata in an Energy Data Space catalogue. To support the learning process, quizzes are added after each section while screenshots illustrate the steps of each process. Links to a wide variety of resources are also provided.

¹⁵ <https://moodle.datamite.psnc.pl/course/view.php?id=19>

Figure 15: Course “Introduction to Data Spaces for Data Providers” on the PSNC Moodle Platform.

9. Introduction to Data Spaces for Data Consumers

Link: [Introduction to Data Spaces for Data Consumers](#)¹⁶

This course (see Figure 16) targets individuals or organisations that require data for various purposes (e.g., research) and demand a concise introduction in the world of data spaces. While it adopts a similar structure to the course “Introduction to Data Spaces for Data Providers”, it focuses on the data consumer. Apart from providing information about data spaces, this course explores the topic of obtaining data using an Energy Data Space. Again, the DATAMITE platform is employed to showcase the steps required from onboarding to downloading data products. Learning is assisted with visual media and quizzes.

Figure 16: Course “Introduction to Data Spaces for Data Consumers” on the PSNC Moodle Platform.

¹⁶ <https://moodle.datamite.psnc.pl/course/view.php?id=20>

10. How to use CI/CD procedures in DATAMITE to commit the codes, from the developer's perspective

Link: [Course: How to use CI/CD procedures in DATAMITE | Moodle](#)¹⁷

This course introduces core principles of CI/CD with focus on their application in the DATAMITE project. It explains how CI/CD helps in software development and maintenance and helps learners understand and use the developed processes of the project. It includes an introduction, a fundamental description of CI/CD and later, more advanced concepts are presented. In addition, it includes a video tutorial and a final quiz.

Figure 17: Course “How to use CI/CD procedures in DATAMITE to commit the codes, from the developer's perspective”

11. Unlocking Open Source Potential: DATAMITE's open source guide and how you can contribute

Link: [Webinar | Unlocking Open Source Potential: DATAMITE's open source guide and how you can contribute](#)¹⁸

This course introduces the strategic integration of open-source principles within the DATAMITE framework to drive European data monetisation and sovereignty. It explains the project's governance model, the project infrastructure and the specific use of the MIT license to ensure commercial-friendly software adoption. Furthermore, the course provides a practical guide on how

¹⁷ <https://moodle.datamite.psnc.pl/course/view.php?id=13>

¹⁸ https://youtu.be/Ki98gRqLzp0?si=_Ai0RKBGGonp10Zu

external developers and stakeholders can contribute to the DATAMITE code repository in the Eclipse Research Labs. This course has been elaborated specifically for a target audience of software developers, data engineers, and technical managers in SMEs, while the material serves as a roadmap for those looking to leverage or expand the DATAMITE ecosystem while maintaining legal and technical compliance with European data space standards. The next figure, Figure 18, shows a screenshot of the session.

Figure 18: Screenshot of the course “Unlocking Open Source Potential: DATAMITE's open source guide and how you can contribute”, available in YouTube.

12. Data Harmonisation Tools

Link: [Datamite's Data Harmonization Tools](https://datamite.readthedocs.io)¹⁹

Data Harmonisation Tools enable users to efficiently deal with semantic and structural mismatches among the elements of source and target data models through the semi-automatic specification of mapping rules and their fully automatic application to the source for data harmonisation purposes. The source code of these tools has been uploaded to the ECL repository, while the corresponding Read the Docs site provides additional information about the development, installation, and usage of these tools. Additionally, a video has been prepared that demonstrates how these tools can be used for the harmonisation of publicly available data so that they are aligned with the given data models and vocabularies through the data DATAMITE platform.

¹⁹ <https://iccs-data-harmonization.readthedocs.io/>

Figure 19: Using Data Harmonisation tools through the DATAMITE platform

13. DATAMITE Data Preparation and Sharing in the Data Spaces

Link: [Webinar | Leverage Electricity Distribution Open Data](#)²⁰

During this reporting period (M27-M39), Pilot 4 delivered a complete set of trainings and demonstrations material showcasing the DATAMITE Framework from the perspective of E-REDES. The pilot team produced a comprehensive training video, later published on the project's YouTube channel for wider dissemination, and an accompanying slide deck that explains the pilot objectives, the data-governance workflow, and the end-to-end process from dataset creation to publication. These materials provide a clear, guided walkthrough of the framework's key functionalities relevant to the pilot. The slide deck is available in E-REDES internal SharePoint site and on the DATAMITE project SharePoint site.

²⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0s0Xax9bL6w>

Figure 20: Pilot 4 YouTube training video.

Figure 21: Pilot 4 Business stakeholders' training slide deck.

To complement the material, the team conducted an ad-hoc demonstration session with E-REDES business stakeholders responsible for data provision and publication on E-REDES Open Data portal. This session presented the implemented components of the framework, explained how the tool supports data preparation and publication workflows, and ensured that

stakeholders were fully informed of the pilot’s progress. Although the training session did not include hands-on exercises, it successfully demonstrated the implemented features and provided the business teams with a structured, practical overview of the DATAMITE Framework.

Figure 22: Pilot 4 Business stakeholders training session.

14. Getting to know the fairness data tool

Link: [Introduction to Fairness in AI](#)²¹

A complete set of training material has been developed for the fairness data tool, aimed at introducing users to the core concepts and practical workflow of fairness analysis in data-driven systems. The material includes a structured video-based course and supporting presentation content covering the foundations of fairness in AI, including sensitive and target attributes, fairness metrics, indirect discrimination, and the statistical and machine learning concepts required to understand the tool’s outputs. The material was prepared to support both technical and non-technical users in understanding how fairness issues can arise in datasets and automated decision-making systems.

In addition to the conceptual background, the training provides a guided demonstration of the fairness data tool in use. It explains how users can configure a project, define the fairness problem, select the appropriate attributes and groups, run the analysis, and interpret the generated results. The course also includes a walkthrough of key outputs such as demographic parity, disparate impact, equal opportunity, equalized odds, confusion matrices, and association

²¹ <https://moodle.datamite.psnc.pl/course/view.php?id=14§ion=0>

analysis, enabling users to understand whether observed bias originates from the dataset, the model, or both. These materials provide a clear and practical introduction to the fairness data tool and support its use within the DATAMITE framework.

Figure 23: Moodle page of the fairness data tool course.

Fairness Metrics at a Glance : Comparison

Metric	What it measures	Range	Fair = ?	Requires
Demographic Parity	Difference in positive outcome rates	-1 to +1	0	No classifier
Disparate Impact	Ratio of positive outcome rates	0 to ∞	1 (≥0.8 threshold)	No classifier
Equal Opportunity	TPR difference among qualified individuals	-1 to +1	0	Classifier required
Equalized Odds	Avg. abs difference in both TPR and FPR	0 to 1	0	Classifier required

Figure 24: Understanding fairness metrics: A snippet from the presentation slides

Figure 25: Fairness Tool Interface to Create filters for the Dataset

15. Transforming data into impactful products

Link: [Course: Transforming data into impactful products | Moodle](#)²²

The scope of this course is to demonstrate how to ingest data from heterogeneous data sources into the DATAMITE framework and transform it by applying various processes, such as anonymisation, aggregation, and filtering. Finally, valuable insights can be generated from the stored data and events.

More specifically, this course explains how to use the following DATAMITE components:

- Trino Connector
- Data Product Composition Tool
- Anonymisation Tool
- Data Sharing Logging

²² <https://moodle.datamite.psnc.pl/course/view.php?id=17>

Figure 26: Course “Transforming data into impactful products”

16. DATAMITE: Sharing Energy Data through Data Spaces for Data-Driven Tools

As part of DATAMITE dissemination activities, HEDNO, in collaboration with pilot partner CERTH prepared and delivered a live webinar titled “DATAMITE: Sharing Energy Data through Data Spaces for Data-Driven Tools”. This webinar was delivered internally and colleagues from HEDNO’s Research & Innovation and Business Analytics & Data Management Departments as well as CERTH attended and participated in the discussions. Three presentations with QA sessions were presented, a) “Data Spaces, DATAMITE and the role of HEDNO”, which outlined the basic aspects of Data Spaces and HEDNO’s activities in the pilot, b) “The DATAMITE platform and data sharing”, where publishing data products with the DATAMITE platform was demonstrated and c) “From data to decisions (data consumption to tool development)”, where the three developed tools supporting the planning and operation of the power grid were showcased. (Figure 27).

Figure 27: Screenshot of the live webinar conducted by HEDNO and CERTH.

4. Use Case Demonstrators

This section describes updates to the DATAMITE pilots. To examine the initial setup please verify the deliverable D5.1.

As previously stated, pilots are organized into three main areas:

1. Data exchange in large corporations: Pilot 1 focuses on data accessibility within the Gimeno Group, while Pilot 2 aims to streamline data exchange across OTE's various data lakes.
2. Data exchange via (energy) Data Spaces: Pilot 3 involves HEDNO improving internal data management and validating data governance tools, while Pilot 4 has E-REDES refining its tech stack and exploring data spaces for open data.
3. Interaction with other initiatives: Pilot 5, led by PSNC, targets governance quality of agrifood data from the eDWIN platform, enhancing data management and validating trading plugins. Pilot 6 evaluates DATAMITE's integration with the ALoD platform, with CINECA validating dataset sharing plugins.

4.1. Pilot 1 - Corporate Multi-Domain Data Exchange with EDIH support

4.1.1. Test Scenarios

The testing scenarios have been designed to emulate the internal activity that users from the different departments and companies of the Gimeno Group will carry out.

Under this premise, testing has been designed around three pillars:

- Ease of access to information
- Security in data publication
- Active enrichment of datasets

Thus, the work scenarios are defined based on these pillars. They faithfully reflect the interaction dynamics that takes place with the final implementation of the framework.

1. Data loading and publication: the corresponding user from the FACSA/OBREMO company accesses the system and uploads a dataset authorised for that purpose. The data is integrated into the platform, and the corresponding metrics are generated to obtain data quality and data description metrics (metadata).
2. Data access, query, and download: a user with a specific need accesses the Marketplace to consult the available and published data. By consulting the corresponding metadata, they can draw conclusions regarding its usefulness for the case in which the information is required. The user selects and accesses the data chosen for that purpose.
3. Dataset enrichment: published datasets can be accessed by companies/departments responsible for advanced analytics in order to extract knowledge and value from them, either through advanced analysis techniques or as derived products from the implementation of artificial intelligence models.

4.1.2. Solution implementation

The details corresponding to the final deployment and configuration of the DATAMITE framework adapted to the needs of Pilot 1 are presented.

Regarding the infrastructure, it has been deployed “on-premises”, on a virtual machine set up within the company’s own environment.

The machine specifications are as follows:

- 8 processing cores
- 16 GB of RAM
- 50 GB of storage
- Ubuntu 24.04 LTS operating system

The deployment was carried out using the official repository hosted on GitLab, making use of the tools provided by the Docker suite, including DockerHub itself.

The authentication and user management system has been integrated into the company’s own Keycloak instance, allowing user provisioning to be carried out using the internal corporate accounts of internal users.

The deployment was carried out including all the components of the framework, but the following are the ones that were ultimately tested through the scenarios planned in this second validation period:

- Data discovery tools
- Data ingestion and storage
- Data governance
- Data product composition
- Quality evaluator
- KPI library
- User-defined rules generators.

4.1.3. Training Materials

A training program has been prepared to provide access to the DATAMITE platform. This training is intended to be offered as access documentation for each new user joining the platform. Along with the documentation, a short training session is provided in which the practical operation of the tool can be demonstrated, together with a PowerPoint presentation intended to serve as a direct and simplified reference for the tool.

In addition to these primary tools that provide direct accessibility to the operation of DATAMITE, the Data Science & AI department itself is responsible for offering ongoing monitoring and support to all platform users through different communication channels:

- Through corporate communication tools
- Continuous usability monitoring
- Continuous improvement and active improvement tools

4.1.4. Test Campaign

The testing campaign was carried out in two main phases. In each of them, users were assigned to each of the companies in order to carry out the practices defined in each of the scenarios. These practices correspond to the different testing activities described in previous sections and in other documents of this same project.

During the testing process, notes were collected from the testers aimed at resolving issues or identifying improvements related to the operation of the framework. This is key, as it emulates the core work that will take place once the framework is incorporated as part of the company's data infrastructure.

The first testing campaign was conducted in the first quarter of 2025, while the second took place in the fourth quarter of 2025.

Based on the results of this campaign, together with the KPIs defined for its evaluation, an approximate internal view is obtained of the level of achievement and the potential for integration of the framework within the context of the group's data environment culture.

4.1.5. Performance and usability of the DATAMITE framework

KPI	Description	Baseline	Target	Achieved
KPI1	Number of Active Users	0	3	Y
KPI2	Number of Dataset Downloads	0	~10	Y
KPI3	Frequency of Access	0	~20/month	Y
KPI4	Number of Datasets Available	0	=>10	Y
KPI5	Data Quality Score based of quality factors (completeness, accuracy, and relevance)	0	Qualitative assessment	Y
KPI6	Retention Rate (number of users which return to the platform after a first access)	0	3	Y

Table 2. Pilot 1 KPIs.

4.2. Pilot 2 - Corporate Multi-Site Data Exchange

OTE Group (hereafter OTE) manages an extensive volume of data and holds a leading position in the telecommunications sector within Greece. Historically, the organisation has been at the forefront of landline communication operations and has played a critical role in the country's transition to digital infrastructure. During the early stages of digitalisation, landlines were not only central to communication but also served as identifiers for unique services and physical locations, thereby establishing a link between digital services and geographical or residential identities.

Over the past two decades, OTE has significantly expanded its telecommunications operations, introducing a variety of technical services and assets that extend beyond communication. These offerings now encompass a comprehensive range of digital interactions, facilitating seamless

engagement between customers, businesses, and the public sector. However, this rapid expansion necessitated the integration and interoperability of a diverse type of services to deliver personalised and value-added experiences to customers.

Strategic Data Vision & Compliance

The integration of AI into all levels of organisational processes fundamentally reshapes operational models. Telecom operators, including OTE, are uniquely positioned to expand their service offerings by leveraging the vast amounts of data they host. This data can be utilised not only to develop new services but also to refine and optimise existing processes and products.

At the core of this transformation lies the recognition that AI's effectiveness is inherently tied to data availability. The extensive repositories maintained by organisations represent an asset for generating innovative insights and breakthrough services. However, harnessing this potential requires a well-defined strategic framework and a clear vision.

Beyond a vertical implementation approach, AI adoption must also be structured through a horizontal process, ensuring cross-departmental integration. To achieve this, a dedicated governing body or an appointed leader should oversee the orchestration of AI-driven initiatives, ensuring alignment with organisational objectives and building a coherent and robust data-driven ecosystem.

Towards that direction, **the creation of the Chief Data (Strategy) Officer (CDO) role** within OTE (Figure 28), introduces a transformative approach to the company's data management and strategic utilisation. This pivotal position is tasked with the development and execution of a comprehensive data strategy that aligns with the organisation's broader business objectives. Central to this role is the deployment of strategic initiatives aimed at leveraging data to foster innovation, secure a competitive edge, and drive business growth. The deployment of DATAMITE framework in the context of pilot execution highlighted the necessity of the creation of CDO role and accelerated the process of transforming the internal data architecture towards the data product paradigm.

Figure 28: Chief Data Officer role to AI-driven application formation

Despite its ambitious trajectory, the rapid growth of OTE's service portfolio has been accompanied by certain challenges. Many of the newly introduced services were deployed without thorough testing or establishment of well-structured data models. In a large-scale data environment, such challenges can lead to logical inconsistencies that may trigger cascading failures, requiring substantial time and resources to mitigate. Furthermore, those discrepancies can occasionally propagate to end users, negatively affecting the customer experience - a critical factor in the highly competitive telecommunications sector.

As illustrated in Figure 29, the case study of the OTE involves a scenario in which a data analyst seeks to identify inconsistencies across three distinct data repositories within the organisation. These repositories correspond to different operational units, each one managing critical aspects of the organisation's infrastructure and services.

Figure 29: Pilot 2 databases' schema

The first repository, managed by the **Registry Unit**, contains the organisation's customer data. This repository includes personal identification details of customers, their loyalty status, and information related to their relationship with the organisation. Specifically, it tracks the number of services utilised by the customer, the duration of the relationship, and the total expenditure incurred by the customer on OTE services.

The second repository, overseen by the **Infrastructure Unit**, facilitates the management of the organisation's hardware and physical infrastructure essential for service delivery to end users. This repository maintains detailed information on the physical and operational aspects of the network, such as Fiber-to-the-Home (FTTH) cabinets, copper cables, DSLAMs, and network operation centres. It encompasses data on the customer's router, including the model and firmware version, as well as the physical communication medium (e.g., fibre, copper, satellite)

and its connection path to the network centre. Additionally, this repository records physical constraints and operational analytics of the network lines, such as maximum bandwidth capacity, error rates, power supply limitations, and the presence or absence of Uninterruptible Power Supplies (UPS) at endpoints or intermediate nodes.

The third repository, maintained by the **Accounting Unit**, contains billing and financial information related to customer accounts. This repository includes details about invoicing, total sales per customer, and specific information that must be shared with the customer, such as contract terms and the Service Level Agreements (SLAs) associated with their subscription.

Since much of the information originates from different organisational units with distinct business goals and priorities, numerous failures arise due to the lack of interoperability in such a dynamic environment, where changes occur on a weekly basis. The competitive nature of the telecommunications market drives rapid processes and transformations, which inevitably lead to inconsistencies in data entry and discrepancies between various data stores. Unlike data entry errors, inconsistencies between data stores often involve logical errors that are significantly more challenging to detect and resolve.

To remain competitive, organisations -such as OTE- must focus on developing a unified platform capable of supporting diverse data warehouse architectures while implementing a standardized, user-friendly programming language to streamline database interactions. Ensuring security and enabling efficient development of data marts that can be readily distributed to analysts for detailed examination is also vital. Moreover, it is essential to support high-performance processing of both OLAP and OLTP workloads, incorporate AI capabilities to expose metadata and features for modern applications, and present these capabilities through an intuitive and comprehensive user interface where critical information is easily accessible.

4.2.1. Test Scenarios

As the complexity of data schemas increases, the implementation of safeguard controls becomes essential. Inconsistencies within different repositories not only complicate system operations but also disrupt the enterprise workflow. This issue is particularly critical for the customer excellence department, which relies on accurate and reliable data to deliver personalised services at competitive prices that appeal to end users.

Unfortunately, such inconsistencies can significantly affect the customer experience - an aspect in which enterprises invest substantial resources throughout the customer journey. Any disruptions or errors arising from data inconsistencies may destroy customer trust and satisfaction, ultimately jeopardising the organisation's efforts to maintain long-term, cooperative relationships with its clients.

4.2.1.1. Scenario 1: OLAP Dimension

The first scenario involves the development of dedicated data marts that integrate information from various repositories to enable analysts to identify inconsistencies and modify tables to ensure accuracy and alignment across all departments. In this scenario, the Data Governance department assumes the responsibility of creating a data mart while considering critical factors, such as the repositories where inconsistencies may exist, complaints from customers or

personnel regarding inaccurate data, and the quality metadata derived from these tables. All these processes are conducted with strict adherence to security and privacy protocols.

The core concept is to provide periodic snapshots of data, allowing analysts to identify inconsistencies and derive rules that enforce conformity across repositories. This data mart is distributed to analysts, who then investigate discrepancies within specific views of the repositories. The insights generated from this analysis are subsequently sent to the Data Compliance department for validation. Here, these insights are examined to ensure they are accurate, do not duplicate existing rules, and are not already addressed by other mechanisms. Once reviewed and refined in consultation with relevant departments, the new rules are implemented in production, leading to updates in the data repositories to resolve the identified inconsistencies.

This scenario represents a direct application of DevOps principles to data management, creating a secure and systematic architecture for Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) in the data domain. The data mesh approach is adopted to transition towards a data space environment, which ensures systematic compliance with emerging EU regulations and strategies for data exposure. This structured methodology enhances data accuracy, interoperability, and scalability in complex data environments.

4.2.1.2. Scenario 2: Visual and Strategic Dimension

The second scenario focuses on addressing the challenges of identifying relationships between data repositories, tables, and schemas by leveraging metadata exploration. In this approach, senior data analysts and architects delve into metadata to abstractly identify potential sources of inconsistencies and their root causes. The primary goal is to develop a strategic roadmap for prioritising data warehouses and organisational departments that require immediate attention.

This prioritisation may be driven by strategic factors, such as maximising the enterprise's revenue by concentrating the efforts accordingly, improving customer relationships by enhancing customer success stories and satisfaction, or reducing complaints and mitigating potential fines arising from inaccurate database information. This strategy ensures that resources are allocated efficiently to address the most critical areas with the greatest impact on organisational goals.

A key element of this scenario is the use of visual analytics to explore various cases and identify unique characteristics. Visual representations of metadata and insights provide a comprehensive overview that aids in understanding complex relationships and patterns across repositories. This visual approach is particularly significant when presenting findings and strategies to the higher levels of the enterprise. Clear and engaging visualisations ensure that metadata insights, data inconsistencies, and strategic guidelines are communicated effectively, aligning technical analyses with the enterprise's broader goals and facilitating informed decision-making.

By coupling metadata exploration with visual analytics and aligning findings with strategic objectives, this scenario puts emphasis on optimising data warehouse management and ensuring that the enterprise remains agile and competitive in a data-driven environment.

4.2.1.3. Scenario 3: OLTP Dimension

The third scenario deals with the day-to-day operations of the enterprise, where the need for accurate, real-time solutions is critical. In this context, it is vital to ensure that instant changes can

be made without being impeded by security or technical restrictions. This process involves personnel with the appropriate accreditation to control and modify data, combining information from multiple sources to resolve specific issues, typographical errors, or inconsistencies as they are identified.

A key challenge for OTE is that its customer data is distributed across multiple IT systems, making it difficult to establish a unified customer view that supports the organisation's CRM strategy. This unified view is essential for optimising sales, service, and marketing processes. Consequently, the implementation of a continuous customer data improvement and quality assurance process within a centralised customer view is crucial for ensuring consistent and reliable data across the enterprise.

In this scenario, as with the OLAP dimension, the ideal solution involves using a middleware platform capable of adhering to regulatory restrictions while providing a standardised environment. With this platform, employees can perform standardised queries, preferably using SQL, to manage daily processes and correct misinformation or errors effectively. Such an environment would allow for real-time adjustments without compromising compliance or security.

This capability is particularly relevant in scenarios where the enterprise aims to attract new customers or upsell additional services to existing customers by leveraging established relationships. Human oversight remains invaluable in this process, as experienced personnel are best equipped to identify and resolve logical issues that automated systems might ignore. For example, during the preparation of an offer or while reviewing a customer profile, any errors or inconsistencies that arise can be immediately addressed. This proactive approach ensures that potential customer dissatisfaction is mitigated, and the user experience remains positive, safeguarding the enterprise's relationship with its clients.

The integration of real-time correction capabilities with robust middleware and a unified customer view enhances operational efficiency and strengthens the organisation's ability to respond dynamically to both internal needs and customer demands.

4.2.2. Solution implementation

The evolving landscape of modern applications and data management necessitates a paradigm shift toward a data-centric approach, wherein data is the primary asset, and all supporting infrastructures serve to facilitate its efficient utilisation. The DATAMITE framework aligns with this vision by establishing a structured and secure data exchange ecosystem that prioritises data governance, quality assurance, and regulatory compliance.

The core objective of DATAMITE is to streamline multi-site data exchange processes through the implementation of a metadata-driven repository, which significantly reduces the complexity of data governance. This enables organisations to enforce fine-grained, role-based access controls while maintaining a centralised architecture for defining and managing data quality standards.

By fostering a holistic and secure data exchange environment, the DATAMITE framework enables organisations to unlock new data-driven insights, improve decision-making, and ensure regulatory compliance in an increasingly complex data landscape. The integration of OTE's data architecture with the DATAMITE framework is achieved by aligning the existing data mart structure of OTE's traditional model with the data product paradigm introduced by DATAMITE. This transition is not

only compatible but also in accordance with the European Union’s vision for data spaces, enhancing interoperability, security, and efficiency.

OTE’s existing model for data-driven applications and services is structured around a two-layer approach (Figure 30). The first layer is responsible for optimising data storage by organising data into a well-structured data mart derived from OTE’s data lake. This data mart is designed to serve specific business objectives, particularly supporting analysts and decision-makers. To ensure consistency and accessibility, the data mart is governed by a policy engine and library that transforms it into a structured and consumable product. Once structured, it becomes available through an internal data marketplace, where employees with the necessary permissions can explore and request access according to their needs.

The second layer governs access to these data marts through Role-Based Access Control (RBAC), ensuring that query results are tailored based on the user’s role. When an employee retrieves a data mart, they can apply designated AI algorithms or conduct analytical queries on the dataset. At this stage, additional security layers verify that the user has the required credentials and authentication privileges before granting access to sensitive data. This approach enhances privacy and security and aligns with organisational policies.

Figure 30: OTE's existing two-layer approach model

While this model is effective in ensuring data security and compliance, it presents significant limitations in terms of flexibility and rapid prototyping. The bureaucratic procedures required to approve access, modify datasets, and align data needs with business objectives often result in prolonged decision-making cycles. This recursive process involves multiple meetings across various layers of design and governance, creating delays that may cause too much damage in the fast-paced AI era. In many cases, the extensive time required to identify, justify, and approve

a data need can lead to missed opportunities, as the dynamic nature of AI-driven applications demands immediate adaptability to market shifts.

To address these challenges, the DATAMITE framework introduces a more agile and efficient approach by replacing rigid, hierarchical governance with a modular and data-product-driven architecture. By decoupling data governance from traditional bureaucratic constraints and enabling a more responsive and dynamic data-sharing ecosystem, DATAMITE empowers organisations to embrace rapid prototyping and experimentation without compromising security and compliance. This shift ensures that organisations such as OTE can remain competitive in an environment where data-driven insights and AI applications must be deployed swiftly to capture emerging opportunities and maintain technological leadership.

Towards implementation of the vision through DATAMITE Reference Architecture

The transition from traditional data management models to an advanced, AI-driven ecosystem requires a structured reformation of existing architectures. The DATAMITE Reference Architecture (Figure 31) provides a comprehensive framework for achieving this transformation by addressing key challenges in data governance, security, and scalability. By redefining data structuring, metadata utilisation, and the transition to a data product and data space paradigm, DATAMITE framework enables organisations to enhance operational efficiency, streamline data accessibility, and foster real-time adaptability in an increasingly dynamic digital landscape.

The core module that implements these concepts into the DATAMITE Reference Architecture (Figure 31) is the **Data Product Composition**. This module is designed to accept one or more datasets as input, enabling users to merge them into a unified file by comparing rows and columns or selectively retaining or removing specific attributes.

More specifically, the module automatically analyses the input files, providing detailed metadata such as file names, column names, data types, the number of entries per field, and overall dataset size. Additionally, it facilitates dataset comparison by examining structural similarities across columns and rows, enabling merging operations based on predefined criteria. Users have the flexibility to determine which columns should be retained or removed before finalising the integration. Upon completion, the module generates and provides access to the merged dataset, ensuring a streamlined and efficient data processing workflow.

Figure 31: DATAMITE reference architecture

The DATAMITE reformation of the traditional two-layer approach can be structured as a sequence of transformative steps. The first fundamental step is the establishment of a unified data format that ensures consistency in data governance, allowing for seamless restructuring and adaptation without dependencies on external services. These services often introduce bottlenecks in data and security workflows, as they must continuously align with overarching processes while maintaining up-to-date policies and access controls. Furthermore, governance responsibilities are frequently fragmented among different entities, leading to inconsistencies in policy enforcement and security management.

The second critical step involves the implicit integration of metadata governance. Traditionally, metadata is managed at the database level rather than being centrally controlled through governance tools. This limitation results in fragmented data insights and restricts advanced data mining functionalities. A unified approach to metadata governance would enhance the accuracy and comprehensiveness of data analysis, facilitating better decision-making and more refined business intelligence models. By embedding metadata management into the governance framework, organisations can achieve higher transparency, improved data traceability, and increased automation in regulatory compliance.

The final and most significant step is the transition from a data-mart-oriented model to a data product and data space paradigm. In the traditional approach, the data mart is optimised for specific tasks, serving as a well-structured repository for analytics and reporting. However, in alignment with the DATAMITE project’s vision, data products are no longer limited to static repositories but instead evolve into dynamic, self-contained assets that incorporate governance mechanisms, live monitoring capabilities, and analytical tools. This shift enables real-time adaptability, ensuring that data products continuously align with business needs and regulatory requirements.

For instance, in a practical business scenario, when the call centre department identifies a need for datasets related to customer satisfaction, loyalty, and revenue metrics, the CDO, in collaboration with the DPO, leverages a Graphical User Interface (GUI) to identify potential data sources across various repositories, such as customer, billing, and product databases. This approach allows for seamless data discovery, validation, and integration, ensuring that business users can access high-quality, policy-compliant datasets without delays caused by traditional bureaucratic procedures.

By adopting the DATAMITE reference architecture, organisations such as OTE can move towards a more agile, scalable, and policy-driven data ecosystem, where data is not only a passive asset but an actively governed, continuously evolving resource (Figure 32). This paradigm shift fosters efficient data democratisation, enhances cross-functional collaboration, and ensures that AI-driven applications can be deployed in a timely and effective manner.

Figure 32: Model transformation adapting to DATAMITE reference architecture

Utilising tools like Trino for distributed data management, the CDO manipulates the GUI to select appropriate data columns that meet the specific informational requirements, guided by company policies that demand selections based on quality and other criteria. For example, this process involves accessing data considering sparsity thresholds (e.g. sparsity less than 10%), the inclusion of essential contact information (e.g. at least one contact detail, based on the ontology that the metamodel has), considering the region or ageing level (e.g. to be located in Greece where is allowed to offer services over 18 years old), enforcing compliance with GDPR for promotional purposes (has written consent for contacting for those purposes).

Upon finalising the data selection, a corresponding data product is created to precisely address certain needs. This product is being strictly validated by the DPO as well as the security

department, and then -if approved- is being made available for consumption in OTE's internal data product marketplace.

There, it is accessible through the data catalogue, allowing for tailored data visibility among different user groups within the organisation. For instance, call centre personnel may be restricted to viewing only recent transactional data, whereas higher-level officials might access comprehensive customer histories. That is enforced at run time level through the access control mechanisms.

This newly introduced approach highlights the CDO's critical role in orchestrating a sophisticated data governance structure that not only supports strategic business objectives but also ensures data privacy and compliance, thereby enhancing OTE's position as a data-forward organisation in the telecommunications industry.

4.2.3. Training materials

Due to the complexity of the DATAMITE framework and the security limitations of OTE's infrastructure, we expressed the necessity of having a step-by-step guide, describing how to deploy and use the framework. For that reason, WIKI pages²³ were created by the technical partners of the project in the GitLab repository of DATAMITE. The pages were being constantly updated following the progress in the development of the framework and the feedback provided by the pilots' deployments.

4.2.4. Test Campaign

A comprehensive series of tests are conducted to evaluate the DATAMITE framework effectively. The benchmarking data that are used in this evaluation, include a collection of datasets extracted from the OTE warehouse. These datasets are particularly designed to align closely with the overall schema, structure, and characteristics inherent to the framework's design. A synthetic AI tool has been developed specifically for this purpose, considering various AI factors and usage scenarios that data analysts may encounter while querying the datasets. The importance of using benchmark datasets and synthetic tools in evaluating frameworks like DATAMITE cannot be underestimated. In fact, benchmark datasets serve as critical references that facilitate the assessment of performance and functionality across different systems, particularly in OLAP and OLTP environments. For instance, studies have shown that well-structured benchmark datasets can significantly enhance the reliability of performance evaluations. Furthermore, synthetic tools can simulate diverse data scenarios, enabling a more robust analysis of how platforms respond to varying workloads and queries.

OLAP dimension scenario

Business Context

A telecom company, such as OTE, manages a vast infrastructure composed of network equipment from multiple providers (e.g., Huawei, Cisco, Nokia). This infrastructure supports

²³<https://gitlab.eclipse.org/groups/eclipse-research-labs/datamite-project/-/wikis/How-to-Setup-de-Framework-for-local-deployment>

various telecom services, including VDSL, FTTH, and mobile networks. The company needs to analyse and optimise its network by understanding how different providers perform, identifying missing data issues, and ensuring smooth operations for customers.

Objective of the Evaluation

The primary goal of this evaluation is to analyse the telecom infrastructure and identify key insights regarding network providers, missing data issues, and location-specific deployment trends (Figure 33). More specifically, it aims to determine the number of network infrastructure components deployed by each provider, detect instances where critical billing and order information is missing, and analyse devices deployed in specific regions, particularly those where the “maincabin” identifier starts with "43" (which is the code for Attica region).

By executing that query, OTE can detect data inconsistencies, optimise network operations, and improve service provisioning while ensuring that missing financial and order-related data does not lead to revenue loss or compliance violations.

Create Trino Query

Name: Identifying Data Gaps and Trends in Network Infrastructure for

Is Recursive: true

Start Date: 01/01/2025

End Date: 03/11/2025

Interval Hours: 720

Query

```

COUNT(*) AS total_entries,
SUM(CASE WHEN totalbill IS NULL OR totalbill = " THEN 1 ELSE 0 END) AS missing_totalbill_count,
SUM(CASE WHEN orderflag IS NULL OR orderflag = " THEN 1 ELSE 0 END) AS missing_orderflag_count
FROM unified_data
WHERE maincabin LIKE '43%'
GROUP BY networkprovider
ORDER BY total_entries DESC;

```

Notes

The company needs to analyze and optimize its network by understanding how different network providers perform, identifying missing data issues, and ensuring smooth operations for customers.

Execute Save

Figure 33: Recursive OLAP query using Trino

Going a step further the analysis and the depth of detail, by leveraging DATAMITE framework we can extract much more fruitful results. So instead of return only counts, we can now determine a flow that produces multi-dimensional findings. That can be provider-wise, infrastructure concentration, anomaly rates per region, ratio of technically deployed versus commercially validated services, customer/service records with incomplete monetisation paths, recurring combinations of missing attributes, hotspot detection for problematic cabinets, providers, or product types. All these are few examples that can be developed using the add on functionalities

that are offered by DATAMITE. So, the developer could use the output of the result to have extra evaluations of the responses (Figure 34)

The screenshot shows the DATAMITE interface with a table of data products. The table has columns for Id, Name, Is Recursive, Timestamp, Quality, Download, Anonymisation, Deanonimize, Results, Delete, and Preview. The data products listed are:

Id	Name	Is Recursive	Timestamp	Quality	Download	Anonymisation	Deanonimize	Results	Delete	Preview
14	OLAP_Complete	false	2026-03-13T01:10:43.355Z							
13	OLAP_Relaxed	false	2026-03-13T01:07:27.606Z							
11	OLAP	false	2026-03-13T00:45:59.745Z							
9	customers_plain_test	false	2026-03-09T11:22:45.485Z							
8	telecom	false	2026-03-05T13:54:00.879Z							
7	customers_plain	false	2026-03-05T13:52:19.997Z							
1	logistic_database	false	2026-03-05T13:23:15.759Z							

Figure 34: Data Product extra evaluation features

Business Impact

By identifying missing data in billing and order records, OTE can reduce billing errors and prevent revenue losses. Strengthening data governance and compliance ensures that network deployment records remain complete and auditable. Improved collaboration between network providers and internal teams allows for more efficient issue resolution.

Furthermore, preventing delays in customer service and network provisioning enhances overall operational efficiency. This approach ensures that OTE operates with a data-driven strategy, reducing risk, increasing efficiency, and maintaining compliance with regulatory frameworks.

As is depicted in Figure 34 the results of the data products can be further evaluated using the modules that are provided by DATAMITE framework. So, data anonymisation (to the output) or quality checks can be extracted as metadata to give the opportunity to the analyst to export in a safe manner the results as well as to provide extra metadata to the end user. Rather than simply counting records, the evaluation results can generate a ranked cross-system anomaly profile that combines provider, location, service type, and data completeness indicators. This extra step allows OTE to distinguish between isolated missing values and structurally recurring issues that affect specific regions, providers, or deployment categories, which is one of the headaches that the business department faces across the year.

Visual and Strategic dimension scenario

Business Context

Building on the insights derived from the query depicted in Figure 33, in the context of the previous scenario, this evaluation shifts the focus towards metadata exploration and visualisation. The

query has already established patterns in missing billing and order data across different network providers, highlighting inconsistencies in infrastructure records. Now, the emphasis is on leveraging metadata to provide data analysts with actionable insights by structuring the extracted information into a new data product.

The effectiveness of network management depends not only on raw query results but also on the ability to interpret and contextualise this data within an analytical framework. By developing a metadata-driven data product, analysts can gain a structured, abstracted view of data quality issues, enabling them to detect systemic trends, root causes of inconsistencies, and the overall impact on operations.

A key enhancement in this scenario is the introduction of a visualisation layer (Figure 35). In contrast with the previous version of the pilot implementation (described in D5.1), the main advantage/change of the new approach lies in the ability of Trino module to export query results in a standardised format that is highly suitable for visualisation and integration with external analytical tools (like those that OTE uses in the everyday analysis). In the previous implementation, visualisations were more tightly coupled with predefined dashboards and interfaces, which limited the flexibility of analysts to adapt the analysis according to different operational requirements. In the updated architecture, the exporting results can be consumed through APIs and reused across different analytical environments and products that OTE has acquired.

Given the high variability of telecom operational data and the diversity of analytical requirements across departments, a single generic visualisation system cannot easily accommodate all use cases. Therefore, the system has evolved towards a more flexible backend architecture where the exported APIs and data structures allow teams to develop visualisation interfaces that best fit their operational workflows.

Another important advantage of this approach is that the visualisation layer can now integrate additional systems and services that are not strictly part of the original data product environment. This enables teams to combine operational, commercial, and analytical information in a single interface when needed. At the same time, these interfaces can be exposed through common and user-friendly environments tailored to specific teams, such as analysts, engineers, or operational managers.

Within this system, visualisations such as graphs, maps, and analytical dashboards (like the mock-up that the internal team of OTE developed and is depicted in Figure 35) represent only a subset of the possible interfaces that can be created on top of the exported metadata.

Examples of metadata dimensions that can be visualised include:

Data Quality Indicators:

- completeness score
- freshness score
- consistency score
- reconciliation status across systems

Operational Attributes:

- provider
- region
- equipment type
- provisioning status
- service activation status

Commercial Attributes:

- billing completeness
- contract presence
- order reference integrity

Figure 35: OTE mock-up visualisation interface that can leverage the DATAMITE products

The objective of the Evaluation

The primary objective of this evaluation scenario is to transform the query results from the previous scenario into a metadata-driven analytical framework that enhances the interpretability of the findings. Instead of presenting missing records in raw tabular format, this approach introduces metadata tagging, categorisation, and visualisation, allowing for a more structured and efficient analysis process.

By leveraging this new metadata-enhanced data product, analysts can:

- Identify data quality issues across different network providers through an interactive dashboard.

- Explore missing values in billing and order tracking through metadata summaries rather than row-by-row inspections.
- Assess provider-specific data inconsistencies over time, identifying recurring gaps and ensuring accountability.
- Analyse deployment trends for network infrastructure based on metadata attributes such as region, provider, and historical completeness rates.

One of the key capabilities of this metadata-driven approach is that analysts can filter and drill down into specific aspects of the dataset in real-time. For example, if missing order data is disproportionately high for Huawei's equipment in the Attica region, analysts can correlate this pattern with external operational factors, such as provider-specific reporting practices, internal data entry processes, or system integration errors.

Furthermore, the new metadata layer supports ad hoc analysis, enabling business and technical users to customise their data exploration based on organisational priorities. Instead of relying on predefined reports, analysts can now dynamically investigate data inconsistencies, refine validation rules, and proactively suggest corrective actions.

Business Impact

By integrating metadata-driven insights into the data governance process, OTE can significantly enhance the efficiency of data analysis, anomaly detection, and operational decision-making. Instead of manually sifting through large datasets to locate missing records, analysts can now instantly visualise gaps and trends, leading to faster issue resolution and improved data quality.

From a financial perspective, ensuring that billing records are complete prevents revenue leakage caused by missing transactions. Similarly, improving order data accuracy ensures that network deployments are efficiently executed, reducing customer service delays, and enhancing overall satisfaction.

On an operational level, this approach fosters closer collaboration between data analysts, engineers, and network providers. By systematically identifying vendors with recurring data quality issues, OTE can enforce stricter data validation requirements for providers that repeatedly fail to maintain accurate records. This leads to stronger compliance with contractual obligations and ensures that infrastructure investments are properly documented.

From a strategic standpoint, the ability to interactively explore metadata, elevates data-driven decision-making across the organisation. Senior analysts and architects can now prioritise which datasets and departments need immediate intervention, ensuring that resources are allocated to the areas with the greatest impact on revenue, compliance, and service quality.

By shifting from static reporting to metadata-driven analytics, OTE gains the agility to proactively address data governance challenges, reducing the risk of regulatory fines, operational inefficiencies, and revenue losses. This transformation ensures that OTE remains competitive and adaptable in an era where real-time insights and data integrity are essential for sustainable telecom operations. On one hand this new approach gives more flexibility to the development teams of OTE, but on the other hand it transfers the effort of implementing these tailored made GUIs to them.

OLTP dimension scenario

Business Context

Customer retention is a critical factor for OTE to maintain revenue stability and customer satisfaction. Customers who pay high monthly bills and subscribe to multiple services provided by OTE, such as fixed & mobile telephony, subscription TV, electronic payment, and insurance services among other, represent a significant portion of the company's revenue. However, a common challenge arises when these high-value customers approach the end of their contracts without renewal efforts being proactively initiated. If these customers feel neglected or dissatisfied, they may opt to switch to a competitor, leading to revenue loss and higher acquisition costs for new customers.

OTE must identify customers at risk of leaving, particularly those whose contracts will expire in less than 15 days or who have not renewed within the past two months. Additionally, tracking multi-service customers ensures that those who have invested more in OTE's ecosystem receive personalised retention strategies. A metadata-driven approach is necessary to analyse customer contract statuses, spending behaviour, and subscription engagement to facilitate proactive outreach before customer dissatisfaction increases a lot. By embedding this metadata analysis into the framework, analysts will have a real-time view of at-risk customers and can take immediate action to maintain customer loyalty.

A new data product can be created to identify customers at risk of leaving, enabling to download a targeted list that can be then forwarded to a dedicated retention team or an external contractor. This team will work to address any concerns and implement strategies to retain these customers within the organisation.

Designed with built-in security and privacy compliance, this data product adheres to the framework's regulatory standards, ensuring that all customer information is handled securely. The list can be downloaded or stored directly on the framework, allowing seamless distribution to the appropriate teams for immediate action while maintaining strict data governance protocols.

The objective of the Evaluation

This scenario focuses on identifying high-paying customers at risk of contract termination and flagging them for engagement. By leveraging metadata exploration and automated categorisation, the framework allows analysts to detect which customers require immediate attention and prioritise outreach accordingly. The evaluation seeks to determine:

- Which high-value customers have contracts expiring within 15 days or have already expired within the last two months.
- Which customers are subscribed to multiple OTE services, making them more valuable and requiring additional retention efforts.
- Which customers have loyalty indicators, such as long-term subscriptions, yet show signs of potential disengagement.

This analysis will be conducted through a recursive OLTP query, dynamically identifying at-risk customers, and updating an engagement table to trigger personalised retention campaigns. Analysts will have the ability to filter customers by risk level, spending behaviour, and multi-service engagement using an interactive metadata dashboard. The real-time capabilities of this

framework eliminate the need for manual data audits and provide customer success teams with instant insights into which customers need outreach the most.

By integrating metadata-driven contract tracking, the company ensures that no high-value customer is left unmanaged. Rather than waiting for customers to reach out with complaints or contract expiration issues, OTE can proactively reach out with personalised renewal offers, loyalty incentives, and service enhancements. This ensures that customers feel valued, increasing long-term engagement with OTE services.

A newly introduced aspect and requirement of this scenario is the ability to monitor and evaluate the operational and financial impact of the data product through the monitoring interfaces provided by the backend infrastructure and the Trino query engine. Through this monitoring interface and the associated user interface components, both the framework performance and the financial implications of executing the specific query can be analysed in detail.

More specifically, the system allows the FinOps team of OTE and the analysts/operators to understand the computational cost associated with the execution of the queries that support this data product (leveraging the analytics of the backend like those that are depicted in Figure 36). Since the retention analysis may involve recursive queries and cross-system data federation, it is important to track how frequently the query is executed, the amount of resources consumed, and the corresponding cost implications. In the latest version of the framework deployment, there exists the capability to directly access the Trino monitoring, so that each query execution can be evaluated in terms of performance metrics, resource utilisation, and associated infrastructure costs.

Figure 36: Backend performance indicator and analysis

Business Impact

By utilising metadata analysis to drive customer retention strategies, OTE can increase revenue, strengthen customer loyalty, and improve overall satisfaction. High-paying customers who feel valued through proactive renewal offers and personalised engagement are far less likely to consider alternative service providers. This ensures that premium customers continue their contracts, stabilising OTE's recurring revenue streams.

Operational efficiency is also improved, as the customer success team can prioritise outreach based on metadata-driven risk levels, ensuring that the most valuable and time-sensitive cases receive immediate attention. The automation of customer risk detection eliminates the need for manual contract reviews, allowing analysts to spend more time strategising and optimising customer interactions rather than searching for expiring contracts.

From a strategic standpoint, this approach shifts OTE from reactive customer service to proactive customer retention, ensuring that contracts are renewed well before expiration dates, reducing the risk of last-minute negotiations or customer frustration and all of these in relation to the actual cost.

This capability enables the FinOps team to assess the financial footprint of the data product and determine whether the analytical value produced justifies the operational cost of continuously scanning the relevant datasets. Management teams and decision-makers can therefore gain a clearer understanding of the trade-offs between analytical insights and infrastructure consumption. In practice, this means that the execution frequency, recursion depth, and data scope of the query can be adjusted according to both operational needs and cost efficiency considerations.

Furthermore, the monitoring framework enables the comparison between the computational cost of executing the query in cloud environments and the equivalent cost of running the same analytical workload on on-premises infrastructure. This comparative analysis supports better infrastructure planning and helps determine the most efficient deployment strategy for the data product.

For this reason, the specific use case must be continuously monitored and evaluated, not only in terms of the computational resources required, but also at the level of individual queries and query components. By analysing the cost and performance of each analytical step, OTE can optimise query execution strategies, improve resource allocation, and ensure that the data product operates efficiently while delivering meaningful insights to the business.

4.2.5. Performance and usability of the DATAMITE framework

The KPIs defined for pilot 2 are depicted in Table 3.

KPI	Description	Baseline	Target	Achieved
KPI1 - Query Clearance Time Reduction	Reduction in delays caused by manual approvals for data queries	Manual multi-level approvals causing long delays	Automated validation reducing time by 40%	YES

KPI2 - Compliance-Ready Product Construction	Acceleration in the construction of compliance-ready data products	Manual efforts needed to align with EU regulations	Automated tagging accelerating process by 200%	YES
KPI3 - Query Execution Time Improvement	Improvement in execution time for queries across multiple databases	Custom integrations and manual mappings required	Optimised federated queries improving time by 12%	YES
KPI4 - Interoperability with EU Digital Commons	Increase in interoperability with EU digital infrastructure	Limited standard API connections and complex reuse	Automated metadata alignment increasing interoperability by 45%	YES
KPI5 - Regulatory Compliance and Sovereignty	Enhancement of data security and compliance monitoring	Manual data access reviews and compliance risks	Homomorphic encryption and AI monitoring increasing security by 35%	YES
KPI6 - Data Duplication Reduction	Reduction in excessive data duplication across repositories	Three instances per data source	Single authoritative source reducing infrastructure overhead	YES
KPI7 - Time to Market for New Data Products	Reduction of time required to prepare and launch new data products	Three to four weeks	Reduced to one week through automation and AI-driven checks	YES

Table 3. Pilot 2 KPIs

The results of the DATAMITE framework demonstrate a significant breakthrough in governance, compliance, and workflow management (Figure 39), particularly in addressing the bureaucratic inefficiencies that large enterprises and organisations struggle with. Traditional data management models often introduce delays, redundant approvals, and compliance bottlenecks, making it difficult for businesses to efficiently access, share, and monetise their data. However, with automated compliance validation, policy-based access controls, and streamlined data governance, the new approach effectively tackles those challenges.

Figure 37: Pilot 2 performance graph

DATAMITE framework significantly enhances data governance, security, and operational efficiency compared to legacy data management solutions.

Table 4 maps each performance metric to its corresponding evaluation scenario (OLAP, Visual and Strategic dimension (VIS), OLTP) and provides a brief justification, ensuring clear traceability between the observed improvements and the functional modules of the framework.

Metric	Scenario	Justification
Query Clearance Time	OLAP	Faster analytical query approval via governance automation
Compliance Product Construction	VIS	Metadata-driven product creation and export pipelines
Query Execution Time	OLAP	Optimised recursive OLAP queries via Trino
Interoperability	OLTP	Real-time customer analytics and engagement workflows
Regulatory Compliance	OLAP	Governance and auditability enforced in analytical pipelines
Data Duplication	OLAP / OLTP	Detected both in analytical queries and operational data flows
Time to Market	OLAP / VIS	Accelerated delivery of insights through analytics and visualisation

Table 4. Pilot 2 performance table

In detail, one of the most impactful improvements is in query clearance time, which has been reduced by 40%. Previously, organisations had to go through multiple levels of manual approvals before running queries on sensitive datasets. With DATAMITE's automated compliance validation and policy-based access controls, analysts can execute queries faster, reducing delays in business intelligence and decision-making processes.

Furthermore, a critical improvement is the 200% acceleration in compliance-ready product construction. Traditional data governance models required extensive manual efforts to align datasets with EU Data Space regulations. DATAMITE framework automates regulatory tagging, metadata standardisation, and interoperability validation, enabling organisations to create compliant data products in a fraction of the time. This ensures that data monetisation strategies are executed efficiently without the risk of regulatory non-compliance.

Moreover, the 12% reduction in query execution time across multiple databases further enhances data accessibility and operational speed. Legacy systems struggled with cross-platform queries, often requiring custom integrations and manual data mappings. DATAMITE framework optimises federated queries and semantic caching, allowing organisations to retrieve insights faster while minimising infrastructure costs.

Interoperability with EU Digital Commons has also improved by 45%, ensuring that datasets are easily integrated, shared, and monetised across European digital infrastructures such as EOSC (European Open Science Cloud). Previous models often lacked standardised API connections, making data reuse complex. DATAMITE introduces automated metadata alignment and compliance-driven data-sharing workflows, making it easier for businesses to participate in the European data economy.

In addition, regulatory compliance and sovereignty have been significantly strengthened, with a 35% increase. This is achieved through homomorphic encryption, differential privacy, and federated learning, ensuring that data remains protected even when shared across entities. Compared to older systems that relied on manual data access reviews, DATAMITE framework offers continuous monitoring and policy enforcement, reducing the risk of data breaches and compliance violations.

Another key enhancement introduced by the DATAMITE framework is the reduction of data duplication from three instances per data source to a maximum of one per data repository. In traditional models, multiple copies of the same data were often stored across different platforms, leading to increased storage costs, data inconsistencies, and version control issues. DATAMITE enforces centralised metadata governance and deduplication mechanisms, ensuring that each dataset is maintained in a single authoritative source, improving data integrity, and reducing infrastructure overhead.

Finally, the time to market for new data products has been significantly improved, dropping from an average of three to four weeks to just one week. Legacy systems often require lengthy manual processes to prepare, validate, and integrate data before launching new services or insights. With automated data onboarding, AI-driven compliance checks, and self-service analytics, DATAMITE accelerates data preparation, validation, and sharing, enabling businesses to respond to market demands faster and gain a competitive advantage in monetising their data assets.

4.3. Pilot 3 - Offering Data to Service Providers with Data Spaces

System planning is a critical task for Distribution System Operators (DSOs) like HEDNO. It implies developing toolsets for the distribution network planning, aimed at delivering optimal decision support, optimising investments, and minimising CAPEX & OPEX, taking under consideration the projected penetration of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) and stochastic loads (e.g., EVs) – considering smart charging services availability, grid constraints regarding losses, power factor, or voltage magnitudes. The following three modules may aid a DSO to plan better its system: a) optimal sizing/siting methodology to select and size the relevant assets (including RES, voltage regulators, etc.); b) AI-based load and Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) generation forecasts module; and c) AI-based state estimation algorithms to identify the state variables of the power system, while tackling low real-time data availability. To perform these tasks, an energy services provider may require and consume data from a DSO through Energy Data Spaces. In the frame of the pilot, pilot partner CERTH acts as the energy service provider, consuming the provided data to deliver its energy services back to the data provider, HEDNO. Specifically, HEDNO provides a complex data product to CERTH, enabling it to simulate the operation of a section of HEDNO's medium-voltage (MV) network and propose optimisation measures.

The Energy Data Space utilised for the data exchange is *Data Cellar*²⁴, a data space project that contributes to the int:net's *Blueprint of the Common European Energy Data Space*²⁵ (CEEDS), which outlines a comprehensive roadmap aimed at realising a common framework for energy data exchange and innovation. The CEEDS blueprint aims to accelerate the adoption of data spaces and enable innovative energy services through improved interoperability.

Currently, HEDNO collects and certifies measurements from its system, ensuring the availability and statistical analysis of metering data in accordance with data transparency principles and the protection of consumers' personal information. HEDNO uses Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI) Meter Data Management (MDM) systems to collect energy measurements. Sharing data with service providers is far from being an easy or automated process. Automation requires services to better find and manage data; to homogenise it; including semantic layers to minimise frictions between systems and increase data interoperability; to guarantee that sensitive and personal data is handled according to laws and regulations, including (pseudo-) anonymisation processes; or to define and enforce global data access control policies. This lack of automation not only complicates sharing data with service providers but also exploring monetisation or collaboration options like the exploitation of data markets or data spaces.

HEDNO deployed DATAMITE to streamline the data sharing process across its various modules, ensuring that all data meets the required quality standards. Initially, the *Data Support Tools* discover data from HEDNO's databases used for SCADA and AMI data, and to upload network topology files. Any anomalies among datasets are harmonised, and any sensitive information is

²⁴ <https://datacellarproject.eu/>

²⁵ https://intnet.eu/images/resources/Blueprint_CEEDS_v2.pdf

anonymised, utilising the capabilities of the Data Support Tools. Finally, the processed data artifacts are securely stored in DATAMITE’s storage service.

Next, the *Data Quality* module is employed to apply key performance indicators (KPIs) and user-defined quality rules, ensuring that the data meets the necessary quality criteria for sharing with third parties. The metadata extracted from both the *Data Support Tools* and the *Data Quality* module are fed into the *Data Governance* module.

This *Data Governance* module manages the lineage and versioning of the data, and, most importantly, ensures seamless intra-corporate findability and accessibility of the data.

The *Data Security* module manages role-based access control, while also helps the business user to define and manage the access/usage policies for the data products.

Finally, the *Data Sharing* module serves as the primary tool for facilitating the composition of data products and their publication to data space data catalogues. We utilise two different connectors for publishing data products:

1. the Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC) connector integrated into the DATAMITE platform, supporting access/usage policy enforcement and contract negotiation, deployed using Keycloak-based identity service (without Gaia-X)
2. the Data Cellar connector (EDC-based) for a wider data sharing to energy service providers, leveraging the Gaia-X trust framework.

A potential data consumer is able to find the products of interest in the catalogue, and, by using the corresponding connector, consumes the products which leads to the developments of new energy services. Unfortunately, currently Data Cellar’s connector isn’t able to enforce access/usage policies, which, for the time being, imposes a burden for production-level data sharing, for companies like HEDNO that have quite strict data policies.

Figure 38 illustrates the high-level architecture of Pilot 3 using data spaces.

Figure 38: High-level overview of Pilot 3

In D5.1, we proposed a thorough test campaign that would include all previously mentioned DATAMITE modules in two testing iterations. Each iteration covered a specific aspect of the data exchange procedure and associated DATAMITE components, initially focusing on module integration, data preparation and ingestion, and finally facilitating the exchange of data products and services through data space technologies. Additionally, in D5.3 and D5.4 we presented demonstration and validation videos related to some of the test scenarios, but not all of them, since, when D5.4 was submitted, not all required components had been integrated yet. All demo videos are available in [DATAMITE's Zenodo repository](#)²⁶. In what follows, we present the test scenarios of iteration 2.

4.3.1. Test Scenarios

In deliverable D5.1, we presented a description of eight test scenarios that leverage capabilities from the full set of available modules of the platform. In summary, these were the following:

1. Dataset creation from multiple data sources

²⁶ doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19261749

2. Data product composition with anonymised data
3. Data quality assessment with user-defined rules
4. Definition of access and usage policies
5. Data product composition with harmonised data
6. Onboarding procedure to an Energy Data Space
7. Data product publishing to an Energy Data Space Catalogue
8. Data product search and consumption via an Energy Data Space

The execution of scenarios **1 and 2** was completed within the same deliverable, while scenarios **3–8** were described at a high level, as at that stage of the project the required components had not yet reached the necessary level of functionality. Additionally, in D5.3, we demonstrated the scenarios 1 and 2 with two demo videos, while in D5.4 we did the same for scenarios 3 and 4.

In the remainder of this section, we present test scenarios **3–8**.

4.3.1.1. Scenario 3: Data quality assessment with user-defined rules

Components: *User Defined Rules Generator, Quality Evaluator, KPI Library, Data Governance Backend, Metadata Repository, Data Discovery Tools, Data Ingestion & Storage, Access Control*

Through the *User Defined Rules Generator* (UDRG) component, a set of quality rules are defined and applied to datasets. The *Quality Evaluator* evaluates the rules combined with pre-defined indicators, provided by the *KPI Library*, provides scoring. Through these rules, assurance will be provided that the final product conforms to modern data standards and is ready for use by consumers.

The scenario is applied to datasets containing historical power, load, and voltage measurements collected through HEDNO's SCADA monitoring system, as well as AMI metering data (explained in detail in Deliverable D5.1).

The UDRG evaluates different data quality dimensions, including *accuracy*, *completeness*, and *validity* and each rule consists of one or more logical clauses applied to dataset columns. The rule definition interface allows users to select dataset attributes, specify comparison operators, and combine clauses through logical operators. The interface for defining the rule clauses is depicted in Figure 39.

Figure 39: Interface used to define rule conditions and logical clauses

Eleven rules are defined in this scenario to evaluate key aspects of the dataset, divided logically in five groups. The first group of rules evaluates the timeliness of SCADA measurements, ensuring that the difference between the measurement source timestamp and the SCADA recording timestamp does not exceed two minutes. The second group evaluates dataset completeness by verifying that the metadata fields *Unit*, *Description*, and *Label* contain non-empty values. The third group verifies that the values appearing in columns (e.g. the Power Type and Unit columns) contain acceptable values. The fourth group of rules evaluates consistency between power type and measurement unit, ensuring that active power measurements are expressed in megawatts (MW) and reactive power measurements in megavolt-amperes reactive (MVAr). Finally, the fifth group verifies that the values appearing in DATA_CLASS column of the Telemetry data contain accepted values (i.e. “active+”, “reactive+”, “active-”, or “Q1”).

After the rules are defined, the platform evaluates the dataset and produces rule-level quality indicators, each representing the percentage of records that satisfy the corresponding rule conditions. These indicators are then aggregated into an overall dataset quality score, providing a consolidated assessment of dataset quality based on the configured rule set. The rules implemented in this scenario are summarised in Table 27.

Figure 40: The data quality rule score, including the overall satisfactory score.

In Figure 40 we can see that the score of the first rule **reaches 99.17% rather than 100%**. This is due to a delay that likely resulted from a failure in the communication network between the RTU that performed the measurement and the SCADA server that received it. Thanks to the evaluation performed by the Data Quality module, we can identify such anomalies in the recording of measurements and ensure the quality of the data products that will be created.

4.3.1.2. Scenario 4: Definition of access/usage policies

Components: *Data Sovereignty, Data Product Composition, Data Governance Backend, Metadata Repository, Data Ingestion & Storage, Access Control*

This test scenario evaluates the capability of the DATAMITE platform to define and enforce access/usage policies for data products through policy-based controls integrated with the Eclipse Data Space Components (EDC) connector. The objective is to allow data providers to specify conditions under which datasets may be accessed and used, ensuring controlled data sharing while preserving the data owner's sovereignty and control over the dissemination and exploitation of the data.

The scenario involves three data products derived from operational measurements of the HEDNO energy distribution network. The first data product contains voltage measurements collected through the SCADA monitoring system during the year 2022, associated with busbars and transformers of a high-to-medium voltage (HV/MV) substation. The second data product contains metering measurements collected through HEDNO's Telemetry Center, including active and reactive power measurements sampled at fifteen-minute intervals. The third data product represents a bundled data product combining multiple datasets required for energy system analysis, including both SCADA measurements and metering data from the Telemetry Center, as well as a network model file describing the topology of the corresponding medium-voltage line.

Each data product is published through the platform and associated with an access/usage policy that specifies the permitted actions and constraints governing how the data may be used. Policies are defined through rule-based elements that combine permissions with constraints or prohibitions. These rules determine the conditions under which the action *use* is allowed for a given data product.

Policies are assigned to the publications of the corresponding data products so that the usage conditions accompany the datasets when they are made available through the platform. This ensures that data consumers accessing the datasets through the connector must comply with the defined constraints.

To create a data publication, the business user first selects the data product to be published and then chooses the data portal through which the publication will take place. Within DATAMITE, a set of technologies has been integrated that enables the framework to interoperate with a wide range of portals. In our case, we select the EDC Connector, which effectively is used for establishing a “DATAMITE Data Space”. To facilitate the requirements of the test scenarios, ITI has deployed a centralised identity service based on *Keycloak*²⁷, responsible for issuing JWT access tokens to participants.

In Figure 41, the selection of the EDC Connector from the list of available portals is shown.

Figure 41: Selection of the EDC Connector among the available data portals for publishing

Next, the user creates the policy by selecting the action and configuring the relevant policy rules, entering the required constraints. Figure 42 shows the interface used by the business user for this process.

²⁷ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

Figure 42: Interface used to define policy the policy rules

Three usage policies are defined for the respective data assets. The first grants permission for the use on the first data product which contains the SCADA voltage measurements, only within the time interval from 1 March 2026 to 30 April 2026, and any use outside this period is not permitted. The second policy grants permission for use on the data product containing Telemetry Metering Measurements only within the same time interval (1 March 2026 to 30 April 2026) and only when the usage occurs within the European Union (EU) region, meaning that usage outside this temporal window or geographic scope is not allowed. Finally, the third policy grants permission for use of the data product containing bundled energy data, only within the time interval 1 March 2026 to 30 April 2026, only when the usage occurs within the European Union (EU) region, and exclusively for research purposes, while commercial use is explicitly prohibited.

The three policies applied to data products are summarised in Table 5 and are presented in detailed ODRL format in Table 5.

Policy ID	Data Publication	Policy Elements	Description
Policy_1	SCADA Voltage Measurements	Time interval permission	Allows the action <i>use</i> for the time interval from 1/3/2026 to 30/4/2026.
Policy_2	Telemetry Metering Measurements	Time interval permission Location permission	Allows the action <i>use</i> for the time interval from 1/3/2026 to 30/4/2026 and only within the EU region.
Policy_3	Bundled Energy Data Product	Time interval permission Location permission Purpose permission Purpose prohibition	Allows the action <i>use</i> from 1/3/2026 to 30/4/2026, within the EU region, and only for research activities, while explicitly prohibiting commercial use.

Table 5. The access/usage policies used for data publications.

Once the policies are defined and associated with the data product publications, and after the user reviews all the relevant metadata, the platform exposes the datasets together with their policy definitions to DATAMITE’s Data Space catalogue.

The policy rules are enforced by the EDC Connector during future data access requests and contract negotiations, ensuring that datasets can only be accessed and used under the conditions specified by the data provider.

4.3.1.3. Scenario 5: Data product composition with harmonised data

Components: *Data Product Composition, Data Ingestion & Storage, Data Harmonisation, Data Governance Backend, Metadata Repository, Data Lineage, Data Versioning, Access Control*

In this scenario, we create a data product containing load measurements from HEDNO’s SCADA system. The measurements are retrieved from the SCADA system in different files, depending on the medium voltage feeder they originate from. Those files are meant to be merged into a single artifact, but due to slight differences among them that result in mismatches in their corresponding data formats, this is not possible without transforming them first.

The *Data Harmonisation* component is employed to alleviate mismatches of their structures by aligning them to a common format, allowing their usage by other DATAMITE modules and components. More specifically, a reference is defined alongside vocabularies that together constitute a topology similar to a database schema. This topology guides the data transformations during the harmonisation process.

A series of steps are involved in each dataset. First, metadata (e.g., field names, data types) is extracted from the datasets. Then, the metadata alongside the reference model and vocabularies are used to construct mapping rules that are necessary to transform the data from the original to the target structure. Finally, the data transformation takes place producing a harmonised data product that expresses the original data according to the terms of the reference model, specified by the mapping rules.

Harmonisation demonstration

In the current scenario, two distinct data artifacts are being extracted from the GUI of the same SCADA system by two different human operators. This process results in slight variations in data formats, which must be harmonised before further processing can take place. Table 6 showcases a simple scenario where current values in the departure of MV feeder 1-16 are available in the desired output format, whereas the correspondent values of MV feeder 1-19 were extracted in a slightly different format that needs to be aligned with the format above.

Artifact A sample: Desired format of data					
Scada time	Source time	Label	Description	Corrected Value	Unit
1/1/2022 0:00	1/1/2022 0:00	MS-Location1_1-16	LINE 1-16 CURRENT	21.87	A
1/1/2022 0:30	1/1/2022 0:30	MS-Location1_1-16	LINE 1-16 CURRENT	20.31	A

Artifact B sample: In need of harmonisation					
Scada	Source	Label	Description	Value	Unit
1/1/2022 0:00	1/1/2022 0:00	MS-Location1_1-19	LINE 1-19 CURRENT (REVERSE FLOW)	9,18	Ampere
1/1/2022 0:15	1/1/2022 0:15	MS-Location1_1-19	LINE 1-19 CURRENT (REVERSE FLOW)	8,99	Ampere

Table 6. Simple case where the Artifact A is in the desired format and Artifact B needs harmonisation. Fields and headers that need harmonisation are depicted in shaded cells

Initially, a new dataset is created and the two CSV files as uploaded as its artifacts. The field delimiter is set to “;” and the decimal delimiter to the proper value.

Thereafter, we exploit the *Data Harmonisation* component and its three tools in the below mentioned order to achieve that Artifact B is transformed to align with the format of Artifact A. A relevant screenshot of the interface of the harmonisation component is shown in Figure 43, where the three tools are depicted on the left side of the GUI.

Figure 43: The GUI of the Data Harmonisation Component

Initially, the metadata from both files are extracted using the Metadata Extraction Tool. Afterwards the metadata definitions are loaded to the Ontology Alignment Tool to load and to create the desired mapping for the harmonisation, as seen in Figure 44. Subsequently, the Data Transformation Tool is used to produce and upload the harmonised file to the platform. This

creates a new file with the following naming convention: “harmonized” prefix, original file name and the current timestamp as suffix (see Figure 45).

Figure 44: The mapping of Artifact’s B fields and formats to their targets as already adopted by Artifact B.

Figure 45: The harmonized artifact.

Finally, we compose a data product using the harmonised data from lines 1-16 and 1-19, so that they are merged into a single artifact. After selecting the two artifacts, we proceed to the *Data Transformation* tool within the *Data Product Composition* module. We select the "Aggregate data

by rows" function and execute it. The resulting artifact appears in the "Generated Files" list. We then select only this specific artifact, ignoring the original ones, and click "Save and Continue", followed by "Finish" (Figure 46).

Figure 46: Aggregation of two artifacts into one harmonised file.

We have now successfully created a data product that aggregates the contents of the initial harmonised datasets into a single unified artifact, as shown in Figure 47.

Figure 47: Overview of the created data product containing one merged harmonised artifact.

4.3.1.4. Scenario 6: Onboarding procedure to an Energy Data Space

Components: *(none)*

As described in previous sections, the objective of the pilot is to demonstrate the successful provision of energy data to energy service providers through Energy Data Spaces, enabling them to exploit these data for the development of energy-related services. In the context of this use case, collaboration was established with the Data Cellar project, which provides data space services for energy stakeholders following the specifications of the IDSA and Gaia-X. For this reason, within the DATAMITE framework, a data portal plugin was developed that allows DATAMITE to interact seamlessly with the Data Cellar connector. However, in order for DATAMITE to be able to interact with the Data Cellar connector, it is first necessary some prerequisites to be satisfied, which are described in Appendix A.

After the infrastructure is deployed, the onboarding procedure continues with the provisioning of the participant wallet and the creation of the Legal Participant identity (Figure 48). This step is executed using the credentials-manager tasks included in the participant template (e.g., task credentials-manager:provision-wallet and task credentials-manager:create-legalparticipant). These scripts interact with the Data Cellar identity services and register the participant in the data space registry. As indicated in the logs (Figure 48), the system verifies whether a participant already exists and then registers the participant DID in the catalogue and registry services.


```

[+] up 9/1
  Image docker.io/razzabl/datacellar-cli:v9.4.48 Pulling
[+] up 2/2 Found orphan containers (provider.cde provider.fuseki provider.influxdb provider.credentials-webkit provider.connector provider.connector-backend provider.connector-postgres provider.connector-broker provider.wallet)
  Container provider.credentials-api healthy
Found existing .env.local:
LEGAL_NAME=HEDNO
VAT_ID=
SUBDIVISION=GR-I
Do you want to reuse these values? [y/n] (default Y, 18s timeout): Y
Using legalName=HEDNO, vatID=, CountrySubdivisionCode=GR-I
Participant exists. Do you want to recreate it? [y/N] (default N, 18s timeout): Y
Recreating participant...
2026-03-11 18:28:23.942 | INFO | datacellar_cli.tasks.create_legal_participant:create_legal_participant:213 - [Participant DID] => did:web:provider.hedno.datamite-horizon.eu:wallet-api:registry
2026-03-11 18:28:23.942 | INFO | datacellar_cli.tasks.create_legal_participant:create_legal_participant:227 - Request Terms & Conditions
2026-03-11 18:28:23.942 | INFO | datacellar_cli.tasks.create_legal_participant:create_legal_participant:232 - Legal Registration Number
2026-03-11 18:28:23.942 | INFO | datacellar_cli.tasks.create_legal_participant:create_legal_participant:228 - Legal Participant
2026-03-11 18:28:23.942 | INFO | datacellar_cli.tasks.create_legal_participant:create_legal_participant:228 - Register in catalogue
2026-03-11 18:28:23.942 | INFO | datacellar_cli.tasks.create_legal_participant:create_legal_participant:224 - Participant did:web:provider.hedno.datamite-horizon.eu:wallet-api:registry
a successfully onboarded!
2026-03-11 18:28:23.942 | INFO | datacellar_cli.tasks.create_legal_participant:create_legal_participant:225 - {'tsandcs': 'https://provider.hedno.datamite-horizon.eu/vc', 'json': {'ira': 'https://provider.hedno.datamite-horizon.eu/vc', 'lp': 'https://provider.hedno.datamite-horizon.eu/vc', 'catalogue': True, 'organization_id': 'did:web:domains:provider.hedno.datamite-horizon.eu'}}
    
```

Figure 48: Creation of Legal Participant identity.

During this stage, the system automatically requests and receives a set of Verifiable Credentials from the Data Cellar issuer. These credentials include:

- Gaia-X Terms and Conditions Credential (gx:GaiaXTermsAndConditions)
- Legal Registration Number Credential (gx:legalRegistrationNumber)
- Legal Participant Credential (gx:LegalParticipant)

These credentials attest that the participant has accepted the governance rules of the data space, provide a verified legal identity for the organisation, and establish the participant as a recognised legal entity within the ecosystem. The credentials are stored in the participant wallet, which is accessible through the Data Cellar wallet interface. The wallet interface displays the DID associated with the participant (Figure 49), together with the issued credentials and their verification status (Figure 50).

Figure 49: Depiction of the Data Cellar's wallet interface, showcasing the Participant's DID.

Figure 50: Depiction of the Data Cellar's wallet interface, showcasing the Legal Participants Verifiable Credentials.

Once the credentials are issued and verified, the onboarding process concludes with the registration of the participant in the data space catalogue, enabling the participant to interact with other connectors in the ecosystem. At this point, the HEDNO participant is considered successfully onboarded. The participant can now publish assets, register service offerings, and interact with other connectors through the deployed EDC-based connector's API. This is done using an integrated data portal plugin within the DATAMITE framework, that allows DATAMITE to interact seamlessly with Data Cellar's connector.

Overall, the onboarding procedure establishes a trusted identity for HEDNO in the Data Cellar ecosystem, deploys the necessary connector infrastructure, and issues the verifiable credentials required to enable secure and policy-controlled data exchange within the Data Cellar data space.

4.3.1.5. Scenario 7: Data product publishing to Energy Data Space Catalogue

Components: *Brokers & Plugins for Other Targets, Data Product Composition, Logging, Access Control*

This test scenario evaluates the capability of the DATAMITE platform to create publications using the Data Cellar connector and thereby assesses its ability to leverage third-party data space projects to disseminate energy data to a broader range of stakeholders.

Before interacting with the Data Cellar connector, participants must first obtain the necessary Verifiable Credentials (VCs), which establish a trusted and recognised identity within the data space ecosystem. These credentials are issued through the onboarding process (described in *Test Scenario 6*) and certify compliance with governance rules, legal registration, and participant legitimacy. Without these verified credentials, secure data exchange with other data space participants cannot be enabled.

The scenario considers a bundled data product derived from operational measurements of the HEDNO energy distribution network, comprising three datasets required for energy system analysis (Figure 51).

HEDNO MS-Location1 2022 Bundle Data Product

Creation date: Mar 13 2023, 17:44:42

Last Edition: Mar 13 2023, 18:14:41

Unique ID: f118f765-e3f1-436e-b9f8-6a0d768213c8

Version: 3

Size in Bytes: 38796407

Summary: The SCADA dataset includes 2022 measurements from the MS-Location1 HV/MV substation, covering voltage, line load, and power consumption for a busbar, line, and transformer. The AMI dataset contains 2022 smart meter energy measurements (active/reactive power, kWh/kVArh) linked to a client's transformer and supply meter, recorded every 15 minutes, with up to 100 daily values to account for Daylight Savings Time. The model contains PowerFactory model of the network departing from MS-Location1 HV/MV substation that is part of the interconnected system of grid.

Description: The bundle contains a SCADA dataset and also busbar load, voltage and power measurements covering 2022 SCADA data concerning the MS-Location1 HV/MV substation. It AMI dataset that contains energy measurements for year 2022 obtained from smart meters, including active and reactive powers, from MS-Location1, and a PowerFactory model of the network departing from MS-Location1 HV/MV substation that is part of the interconnected system of grid.

Publisher: Fundamentals, Powerlines

Modified: Mar 13 2023, 17:51:18

Aggregation Of: SCADA MS-Location1 2022 Powers, Network model MS-Location1 2022, SCADA MS-L

Computed To: -

Keywords: AMI, SCADA, Power Factory

Policy: Non-Commercial Use Only

Language: greek, english

License: CC-BY-NC-ND 3.0

Terms and Conditions: Not defined

Spatial Coverage: Location1, Greece

Temporal Coverage: 01/01/2022, 12:00:00 AM

Resolution: 300

Figure 51: Overview of the selected data product's metadata.

These include SCADA measurements, metering data from the Telemetry Center, and the network topology model. Specifically, the data product contains voltage measurements collected through the SCADA monitoring system during 2022, associated with the busbars and transformers of a high-to-medium voltage (HV/MV) substation, along with metering data from the Telemetry Center, including active and reactive power measurements sampled at fifteen-minute intervals, and a network model file describing the topology of the corresponding medium-voltage line (Figure 52).

Figure 52: List of artifacts included in the data product.

To create a data publication, the business user first selects the data product to be published and then chooses the data portal through which the publication will take place. Within DATAMITE, a set of technologies has been integrated that enables the framework to interoperate with a wide range of portals. In our case, we select the *Datacellar Connector* (Figure 53). Next, user sets the metadata of the publication.

Figure 53: Selection of the Data Cellar connector and the metadata of the publication

The user sets the metadata of the publication and finally reviews all the relevant assets' metadata (Figure 54), before the platform exposes the datasets through the Data Cellar's federated catalogue. Finally, we depict the final Publication, as it appears in DATAMITE's UI.

Figure 54: Assets' metadata review used for the federated catalogue and Data Cellar Publication overview.

The publication is now available through HEDNO's data catalogue as a service offering with its own Verifiable Presentation. The verified consumers of Data Cellar that has deployed a Data Cellar connector instance, can now search for HEDNO's federated catalogue using the endpoint `provider.hedno.datamite-horizon.eu`, and consume the provided assets.

4.3.1.6. Scenario 8: Data product search and consumption via Energy Data Space

Components: *IDSA & Gaia-X Components, Data Product Composition, Data Ingestion & Storage, Logging*

In this scenario, two different approaches for data discovery and consumption through data space technologies are explored. The first approach concerns the use of the Data Cellar energy data space, while the second focuses on the use of the integrated data space capabilities of DATAMITE through the EDC connector. The different approaches and setups are provided in Appendix A.

In the following subsections, CERTH, acting as an energy service provider, performs data discovery and consumption of all the required datasets provided by HEDNO, which can be used for simulations for developing energy services. The process is performed using both approaches. It is noted that the DATAMITE environment includes plugins for creating publications compatible with both connectors.

4.3.1.6.1. Search and consumption with DATAMITE EDC Connector

First, CERTH as data consumer, accesses the front-end and selects the connector of the remote data provider HEDNO (Figure 55).

Figure 55: Selection of data provider connector.

Next, the user requests the catalogue and retrieves a list of available publication assets (Figure 56), each associated with a unique asset identifier. The datasets that are published in the same data product appear as separate data assets on the consumer's side.

Figure 56: Asset selection from provider's catalogue using the consumer EDC connector.

Upon selecting an asset, the platform provides the corresponding policy in machine-readable (ODRL) format, allowing the user to inspect the conditions under which the data can be used, such as geographic or other constraints. In this case, CERTH selects the HEDNO's Telemetry Center data, which have been anonymised from sensitive information (Figure 57).

Ask Catalogue

INITIAL REQUESTED AGREED VERIFIED FINALIZED

Current state: FINALIZED

Asset ID: 27071da8-192c-422f-979f-26ca587d862e Hide details

Select dataset: Datamite Dataset — MS-Location1_2022_AMI_del_...

```

{
  "@id": "MWRjYmU5Y2YtMTNhZC00MzEzLTliYzQtYWZlZjI1NDYxY2Qz:MjcwNzFkYTgtMTkyYy00MjJmLTk3OWYtMjZjYTU4NzQ4Nj",
  "@type": "odrl:Offer",
  "odrl:permission": {
    "odrl:action": {
      "@id": "odrl:use"
    },
    "odrl:constraint": {
      "odrl:leftOperand": {
        "@id": "edc:location"
      },
      "odrl:operator": {
        "@id": "odrl:eq"
      },
      "odrl:rightOperand": "eu"
    }
  },
  "odrl:prohibition": {
    "odrl:action": {
      "@id": "odrl:use"
    }
  },
  "odrl:obligation": []
}
    
```

Restart Request

Figure 57: Showing usage policy from catalogue using the consumer EDC connector.

Following asset selection, the user initiates a contract negotiation for the selected asset (Figure 58). This step results in the establishment of an agreement between the consumer and provider, producing a contract identifier, and confirming that the usage conditions have been accepted.

Contract negotiation - 27071da8-192c-422f-979f-26ca587d862e

INITIAL REQUESTED AGREED VERIFIED FINALIZED

Current state: FINALIZED

Contract ID: 447539e7-9aa1-4171-b277-cbb8f503d240
 Negotiation ID: 741c4145-c292-49db-84b5-771c405ccb35

Restart Negotiation

Figure 58: Contract negotiation using the consumer EDC connector.

Once the agreement is in place, a transfer process is created, enabling the technical preparation for data exchange (Figure 59).

Figure 59: Transfer process initiation using the consumer EDC connector.

Subsequently, the platform retrieves the Endpoint Data Reference (EDR), which contains the necessary information for accessing the data, including the endpoint URL and authorisation token (Figure 60).

Figure 60: Endpoint retrieval using the consumer EDC connector.

Using this information, the user proceeds to access the dataset, which is returned as structured data corresponding to the selected asset (Figure 61).

Transferred Data	
HV_MV_SUBSTATION,TRANSFORMER,BAR,SEMIBAR,LINE,SUPPLY_NUM,DATA_CLASS,DATE_READ,Q1,Q2,Q3,Q4,Q5,Q6,Q7,Q8,Q9,Q10,Q11,Q12,Q13	
Location1,MS-2,1,1-2,1-19,85144887,active+,1/1/2022,0.46,0.5,0.44,0.46,0.44,0.44,0.44,0.48,0.46,0.46,0.46,0.48,0.48,0.5,0.48,0.48,0.48,0.48,0.5,0.48,0.48,0.5,0.48	
Location1,MS-2,1,1-2,1-19,85144887,active+,1/2/2022,0.46,0.48,0.46,0.48,0.46,0.46,0.5,0.5,0.5,0.5,0.5,0.5,0.46,0.48,0.48,0.48,0.5,0.48,0.48,0.48,0.46,0.48,0.46,0.48,	
Location1,MS-2,1,1-2,1-19,85144887,active+,1/3/2022,0.5,0.46,0.44,0.46,0.44,0.48,0.46,0.48,0.48,0.48,0.46,0.44,0.44,0.44,0.46,0.44,0.42,0.44,0.42,0.42,	
Location1,MS-2,1,1-2,1-19,85144887,active+,1/4/2022,0.5,0.46,0.44,0.44,0.42,0.42,0.44,0.42,0.42,0.44,0.44,0.44,0.44,0.44,0.44,0.44,0.44,0.42,0.42,0.42,	

Figure 61: Dataset contents preview.

By applying the process for the rest of the required assets, CERTH has gained access to HEDNO’s electricity grid data, though an automated workflow that covers data discovery, policy inspection, contract negotiation and establishment, and secure data retrieval under the defined usage conditions.

4.3.1.6.2. Data Cellar Connector

CERTH provides this address in the `counterPartyAddress` field of the `/fetch-catalog` endpoint. As shown in Figure 62, the consumer retrieves the full catalogue exposed by the provider.

The screenshot displays the Datamite Datacellar API interface in a browser. The main heading is "DATAMITE Datacellar 0.1.0 OAS 3.1". Below it, the "Datamite Datacellar API" section is active, showing a dropdown menu for the endpoint `/fetch-catalog` (Fetch Catalog Endpoint). The parameters section shows a required string parameter `counterPartyAddress` with the value `https://provider.hedno.datamite-horizon.eu/pr`. The "Execute" button is highlighted in blue. The "Responses" section shows a successful 200 response with a JSON body containing asset details such as `bid`, `btype`, `dcat`, `dcat:dataset`, `addr:haspolicy`, `addr:hasoffer`, and `addr:haspermission`.

Figure 62: Federated catalogue retrieval by the consumer.

Federated catalogue metadata, show all the available datasets. The consumer then specifies the identifier of the selected dataset (i.e., MS-Location1_2022_Voltages.csv) in the `assetID` field of the `/consume-asset` endpoint, as shown in Figure 63. The dataset is subsequently retrieved, as illustrated in Figure 64.

Figure 63: Asset ID of the requested dataset.

Figure 64: Dataset retrieval to the consumer side, using the Data Cellar connector.

It should be noted that no contract negotiation takes place between the provider and the consumer, as this is not supported by the current implementation of the Data Cellar connector. Consequently, usage policies are not enforced. Data is accessible to any participant possessing valid Verifiable Credentials, and therefore constraints such as temporal, geographic, or purpose-based restrictions - such as those defined in the DATAMITE EDC connector policies - cannot be applied.

By invoking the `/consume-asset` endpoint for the remaining available datasets, CERTH can retrieve all required data and perform the simulations necessary for the development of energy services.

4.3.2. Solution implementation

Pilot architecture

Figure 65: Pilot 3 architecture.

The pipeline of Pilot 3 starts by collecting data from *HEDNO's Internal Systems*, namely the *Telemetering Center* and the *SCADA System PostgreSQL* databases. Data can also be uploaded in bulk to DATAMITE, either in CSV format (from the Telemetering Center and SCADA System) or PowerFactory format (for Network Diagrams).

The pipeline progresses with the *Data Support Tools* module where the bulk uploaded files (CSV and PowerFactory) are stored by the *Data Ingestion & Storage* component, which supports mechanisms for large-scale batch data transfers. The *Data Discovery Tools* component establishes connections either with HEDNO's databases, or the *Data Ingestion & Storage* component and extracts all the metadata information, which are fed into the *Data Quality* and *Data Governance* modules.

The *Data Quality* module utilises the *Quality Evaluator*, the *KPI Library* and the *User Defined Rules Generator*. The *Quality Evaluator* is designed to assess and ensure the quality of datasets through a series of pre-defined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and user-defined quality rules. The pre-defined KPIs are provided by the *KPI Library* and the definition of user-defined quality rules by the *User Defined Rules Generator*. These components offer a solution for data quality profiling, making it easy to automate and integrate quality checks into data pipelines, and help the data provider to improve, ensure or enhance the quality of the data. The quality analysis metadata is then fed into the *Data Governance* module.

Both the metadata from the *Data Discovery Tools* describing the datasets and the evaluation results from the *Quality Evaluator* are provided to the *Data Governance Backend*, which is the core and most crucial component of the *Data Governance* module. The *Data Governance*

Backend stores all metadata to the *Metadata Repository*, while keeping track of the history and the changes of the datasets using the *Data Versioning* and the *Data Lineage* components. It is also responsible for providing all this metadata information to the front-end and to the *Data Sharing* module.

The *Data Security* module encompasses a comprehensive set of security features, from which we retain the *Data Sovereignty* and the *Access Control* components. The former is used for the definition of data access and usage policies, while the latter provides security by granting access and authorising users to the data and the DATAMITE modules.

The final part of the pipeline pertains to the *Data Sharing* module, where Pilot 3 utilises the *Data Product Composition* component, the *IDSA & Gaia-X Components* and the *Logging* component. The *Data Product Composition* takes on the task of gathering data from the data sources (either HEDNO's *Internal Systems* or the *Data Ingestion & Storage* component), and combining them into one composite bundle, the data product. The corresponding metadata of the datasets are retrieved from the *Data Governance Backend* and the data product flows through the components of *Data Support Tools*.

Subsequently, the *Data Anonymisation* tool transforms all sensitive information, and the *Data Harmonisation* tool creates the final composite, homogeneous dataset. The *Data Ingestion & Storage* component is utilised for storing the initial and the updated versions (harmonised and anonymised) of the data product.

Furthermore, the *Data Product Composition* retrieves the definitions of the data access/usage policies from the *Data Sovereignty* component, and forwards them, along with the relative data products, to the *IDSA & Gaia-X Components*.

IDSA & Gaia-X Components is the main component responsible for publishing the data to the Data Space, and for safeguarding data sovereignty throughout the entire data-sharing process. In particular, it is used for pushing publications to Data Cellar, sharing the data products' metadata catalogues with the integrated data space capabilities of DATAMITE, facilitating communication between the data provider and the consumers using the Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC) Connector, and, ultimately, for enforcing the access/usage policies which are defined and retrieved from the *Data Sovereignty* component.

Finally, the *Logging* component will be used for recording and logging the details of the data sharing process.

In deliverable D5.1, we stated that the pilot would utilise a connector for direct integration with HEDNO's internal object storage service to enable the ingestion of network model files using the S3 protocol. However, this was not achieved by the end of the project. While this capability is potentially supported within the DATAMITE framework - since an S3 connector is used internally in the architecture - it has not yet reached a sufficient level of maturity to be offered as a user-friendly feature, allowing business users to establish such connections through the platform's frontend. Therefore, we relied only on the bulk upload feature for uploading network files to the platform.

The pilot's architecture is illustrated in Figure 65, and all the components described above are outlined in Table 7.

Data Governance	Data Quality	Data Security	Data Sharing	Data Support Tools
Metadata Repository ^{1,2}	Quality Evaluator ²	Data Sovereignty ²	IDSA & Gaia-X Connectors & Components ²	Data Discovery Tools ¹
Data Versioning ²	KPI Library ²	Access Control ²	Data Product Composition ^{1,2}	Data Ingestion & Storage ^{1,2}
Data Lineage ²	User Defined Rules Generator ²		Logging ²	Data Harmonisation ²
Data Governance Backend ¹			Brokers & Plugins for Other Targets ²	Data Anonymisation ¹
1: Component tested at iteration 1				
2: Component tested at iteration 2				

Table 7. DATAMITE components utilised for Pilot 3.

4.3.3. Training Materials

Training materials in the form of Moodle online courses, videos demonstrating the pilot's scenarios and PowerPoint presentations were produced during the project.

Two courses, titled “*Introduction to Data Spaces for Data Providers*” and “*Introduction to Data Spaces for Data Consumers*”, are being hosted online using the Moodle e-learning platform that allows the design of custom courses for asynchronous training. The courses were developed, following the insights and experience gained from performing the pilot's test scenarios and utilising the DATAMITE platform in realistic conditions. Further details about the courses can be found in Section 3 of the current deliverable.

During the planning, preparation and development stages, the materials were hosted in a Moodle instance installed in a virtual machine managed by HEDNO's DATAMITE team. An initial version was shared among few individuals within HEDNO for feedback regarding the length, content and presentation. Each course sections concludes with a quiz testing the understanding of the material presented. The collected feedback was used to improve the quality of the material regarding its presentation, syntax and flow.

The improved version was then transferred to HEDNO's official corporate training platform (which hosts a multitude of training courses) and was advertised to HEDNO's *Research & Innovation* and *Business Analytics & Data Management* departments, as well as to selected employees with related interests and responsibilities. The course is open to all HEDNO employees (~5000).

An evaluation questionnaire is added at the end of each course with questions regarding the quality of the material. Each participant is required to provide feedback evaluating the course and

HEDNO collects the results and may improve the content accordingly. Currently 15 employees have completed the first course and 10 the second. The average evaluations of the students are depicted in Figure 103.

Due to geographical restrictions of the HEDNO corporate platform limiting access to connections within Greece, the improved version of the material was uploaded to consortium partner PSNC's Moodle platform under the category [DATAMITE](#), which places no geographical limitations and the courses were made available so that anyone could enrol and take the courses.

Additional materials include:

1. detailed and explicative videos showcasing the pilot's scenarios that were produced for demonstration purposes (their links can be found in the Deliverables D5.3 and D5.4),
2. PowerPoint presentations used for internal trainings and
3. other demonstrations that were prepared by HEDNO and CERTH showcasing the implementation of the scenarios, the data-driven tools developed by partner CERTH upon consuming HEDNO's data and their expected outcomes on grid planning and operation.

4.3.4. Test Campaign

This section is split into two parts, demonstrating the use case of the pilot in realistic conditions. In the first part, we summarise the pilot validation plan that organises the test scenarios described in detail in **Section 4.3.1**. In this validation plan, HEDNO collected and prepared data products that were subsequently shared through an Energy Data Space. Pilot partner CERTH then used the provided data products to develop 3 different tools that assist HEDNO in its network planning and operation activities. The second part contains detailed descriptions of the developed tools and their benefits for a DSO.

4.3.4.1. Pilot Validation Plan

The validation plan for pilot 3 was divided into two iterations that cumulatively utilised all framework components involved in the pilot. The objectives were implemented in 8 scenarios, summarised in the tables below:

Iteration phase 1	
Description	The first iteration focused on integrating the DATAMITE framework with HEDNO's internal systems, discovering and ingesting data, and extracting and storing the associated metadata. Additionally, it includes the creation of synthetic data products generated from various datasets originating from multiple sources. These data products undergo anonymisation to protect sensitive information.
Scenarios	1 – 2

Table 8. Overview of the iteration phase 1

Iteration phase 2	
Description	The second iteration focused on data quality and sharing. More specifically, data quality rules were defined and applied to evaluate the datasets, leveraging the built-in KPIs provided by the DATAMITE framework. Secondly, access and usage policies for the data products were defined for data consumers. Furthermore, the

	onboarding process of the pilot into an Energy Data Space was demonstrated. Finally, the demonstration concludes with a complete instance of a data exchange between two partners (a data provider and a consumer) using an Energy Data Space.
Scenarios	3 – 8

Table 9. Overview of the iteration phase 2.

The scenarios were executed and evaluated by HEDNO in cooperation with pilot and consortium partner CERTH. The goal of the pilot was the sharing of data to Energy Service Provider CERTH for the development of data-driven services.

4.3.4.2. Data-Driven Services

In this section the developed services are briefly presented, while a detailed analysis of the methodologies is included in Appendix A, Section 0. Specifically, 3 services were developed: an optimal sizing methodology to select and size relevant assets (1), AI load and DER forecasting modules (2) and a state estimation system (3). The role of CERTH was to process the necessary datasets and provide these services to showcase the impact that DATAMITE can have. Such tools can have a significant financial and environmental benefit, as DER integration and efficient forecasting can facilitate modern smart grid operations.

CERTH's research demonstrated that deep learning architectures are highly effective at modelling the parameters of a local distribution network. LSTM models delivered strong performance for both DER and current forecasting, while the mixture of experts' approach proved most capable of capturing the high volatility in active and reactive load measurements. Additionally, the implementation of a deep learning-based state estimation filter provided a resilient method for reconstructing grid conditions even in cases with sensor noise or data loss. These findings suggest that advanced neural networks can serve as a robust foundation for maintaining grid stability and safety.

Transitioning these insights into practical grid management could provide immense value for energy providers. Reliable joint forecasting identifies exactly when solar production will peak. This knowledge allows operators to move excess power to where it is needed most, which helps the grid accept more renewable energy. Moreover, optimising these predictive frameworks through a Granger-inspired variable selection can lead to significant financial benefits. Operators can monitor shifts in these established client relationships to detect early signs of equipment failure. Identifying such issues before they escalate into outages prevents costly emergency repairs and protects the long-term physical integrity of the infrastructure.

These optimisations carry substantial financial weight by lowering maintenance expenses and operational overhead. Finally, reduced data requirements allow for the deployment of AI modules on edge devices, significantly cutting the costs associated with cloud computing.

4.3.5. Performance and usability of the DATAMITE framework

KPI	Description	Baseline	Target	Achieved
KPI1	Collection of Voltage, Current and Power Measurements, as well as the nominal values of MV/LV transformers of the provided grid	0	100% of the data needed for the simulation purposes of the system planning tools	Yes
KPI2	Data of the Active Power, Reactive Power, Energy Consumption (for consumers) and Energy Production (for producers)		≥ 1 MV consumer per 500kVA of installed apparent consumption power; ≥ 1 MV producer per 250kVA installed apparent production power	Yes
KPI3	Network diagram (nodes and line data)	0	1	Yes
KPI4	Number of different datasets to be included	0	≥ 3	Yes
KPI5	Setup of dedicated VM for DATAMITE	0	≥ 1 (VM)	Yes
KPI6	Number of developed connectors compatible with internal system to be deployed	0	≥ 1	Yes
KPI7	Deployed DATAMITE modules	None	> 3 DATAMITE modules	Yes
KPI8	Datasets processed by Data Governance, Data Quality or Data Security modules	0	> 90% data involved in the Pilot	Yes
KPI9	Datasets processed with the involvement of Access Control and Data Sovereignty components	0	> 80% data involved in the Pilot	Yes
KPI10	On-boarding to a Gaia-X compliant data space	0	≥ 1 data space	Yes
KPI11	Energy Data Spaces used for data sharing	0	≥ 1 Energy Data Space	Yes
KPI12	Number of times that the data products were retrieved by users	0	≥ 1	Yes

KPI	Description	Baseline	Target	Achieved
KPI13	Energy services provided by exploiting a shared data product	0	≥ 1	Yes
KPI14	Personnel Upskilling: employees aware of data spaces and its usability	5	30	Yes
KPI15	Design and implementation of data sharing process to external stakeholders through data spaces	0	1 well-defined process handling quality and governance concerns	Yes

Table 10. Pilot 3 KPIs.

The four initial KPIs were a central aspect of the first iteration and focused on the collection of the necessary data required by the energy service provider for developing the services detailed previously. More specifically, KPIs 1 and 2 refer to collecting the necessary data that satisfy the constraints enforced by the network simulation and optimisation tools efficiently, while KPI3 focused on obtaining the necessary network topology to support the implementation of the network optimisation tools. HEDNO's team chose an appropriate physical grid Medium-Voltage (MV) line with an adequate number of end users satisfying the constraints enforced by the optimisation tools, validating KPIs 1 to 3. All files were organised into datasets and uploaded to the DATAMITE platform to be used in the scenarios of both iterations, validating KPI4.

KPIs 5, 6 and 7 refer to successful integration of the DATAMITE components into the pilot. By the end of the second iteration, the necessary (virtual) infrastructure employed by HEDNO was set up, validating KPI5, and all DATAMITE components were successfully integrated into the pilot, covering KPI7. PostgreSQL and Trino were two data discovery connectors that were deployed and utilised in our test scenarios, satisfying KPI6.

KPI8 evaluates the processing of datasets by the *Data Governance*, *Data Quality*, or *Data Security* modules. These components were fully integrated into the pilot and tested in scenarios 3 and 4. Regarding KPI9, the *Access Control* component was used to manage access to the platform and to grant user permissions for various data-related functionalities. In test scenario 4, access and usage policies were defined for data products that were published using the EDC connector.

KPIs 10 through 15 were also validated in the second iteration of the demonstration, where the DATAMITE platform was used to perform data sharing between the pilot partners. Regarding KPI10, in scenario 6, both HEDNO and CERTH successfully onboarded to Data Cellar, which is a Gaia-X compliant Energy Data Space, while in scenarios 7 and 8, two Data Spaces are used for data sharing: Data Cellar (which is a dedicated Energy Data Space aligned with CEEDS) and DATAMITE's own EDC-based data space, satisfying KPI11 and KPI12. Using the data provided by HEDNO, CERTH developed three data-driven services, showcased in detail previously, in **Section 4.3.4.2**, validating KPI13.

Finally, the internal webinar (HEDNO, CERTH) and two training courses developed by HEDNO, combined with the insights shared with multiple colleagues involved throughout the course of the project, resulted to personnel upskilling within the company, achieving the target of KPI14. KPI15 was also achieved since a well-defined process for data sharing with external stakeholders was designed and followed to implement the Pilot's data exchange with partner CERTH.

4.4. Pilot 4 - Leveraging Electricity Distribution Open Data

A detailed description of the context, motivations and operational landscape of Pilot 4, led by E-REDES as the Portuguese Distribution System Operator, was already provided in Deliverable D5.1. In summary, the pilot builds on E-REDES' extensive role in managing electricity distribution data and its existing Open Data Portal, exploring how the DATAMITE Framework can support the preparation, governance, publication and sharing of data products. In this deliverable (D5.2), the focus shifts from introductory context to the final integration, configuration and validation activities carried out using the DATAMITE Framework, including the creation of datasets and data products, the definition of governance and quality mechanisms, and the testing of publication pathways through both the Open Data Portal and components that are aligned with CEEDS (Common European Energy Data Space).

4.4.1. Test Scenarios

The test scenarios executed for Pilot 4 in this reporting period follow the structure previously defined in Deliverable D5.1, maintaining the three-level organisation and two scenarios that together framed the intended end-to-end validation process. The objective remained to confirm, within the constraints of the available infrastructure, the complete workflow from dataset preparation in E-REDES internal systems to their processing, governance and publication through the DATAMITE framework. While the original design anticipated that the validated datasets and artefacts would be transferred to a dedicated Azure ADLS Gen 2 pilot storage area, the demonstrator was ultimately executed on the infrastructure provided by the technical partners (ITI). As a result, although the datasets continued to be produced by the BI4D application using information from the E-REDES DATAHUB, they were no longer transferred to ADLS and were instead uploaded manually to the DATAMITE framework running in the ITI environment. This adaptation ensured continuity of the validation activities and allowed the pilot to test the scenario flows, without compromising the already extended project timeframe. The only components that could not be fully validated were those dependent on external modules that did not reach operational maturity during the project period, namely the end-to-end connection to CEEDS (Data Cellar).

Figure 66: Pilot 4 Validation scenarios

At Level 1, the scenario focused on validating the existing BI4D processes responsible for generating the artifacts required for the pilot. These processes, which draw data from replicas of operational systems and from the E-REDES DATAHUB, continued to perform aggregation, validation and anonymisation as specified in Deliverable D5.1. The datasets thereby produced maintained complete alignment with the information already used for internal reporting and for publication on the E-REDES Open Data Portal. Although the architectural design envisaged transferring these validated outputs to the pilot’s ADLS Gen 2 storage, and then the ingestion in the framework through an ADLS connector, this step was not executed in Deliverables D5.2 and D5.4 due to the decision to conduct the demonstrator on the ITI infrastructure. Instead, the outputs produced by BI4D were exported and later uploaded manually into the framework. This change in the way the data is provided to the framework did not alter the testing objective of Level 1,

which was successfully met: all required datasets and artifacts were produced through the standard BI4D pipelines, as originally planned, and ingested into the framework.

At Level 2, the scenario addressed dataset ingestion into the DATAMITE framework and the validation of the components responsible for metadata extraction, data profiling, quality evaluation and governance. Because the framework was not deployed on an E-REDES internal virtual machine due to delays in the provisioning of a Linux-based environment, the ingestion process relied on manual upload through the framework's front-end on the ITI virtual machine. Once ingested, the datasets were correctly represented as artifacts and datasets, their metadata were stored in the Metadata Repository, and the quality evaluation mechanisms operated as intended, including both predefined rules and user-defined KPIs. The governance layer, comprising domains, glossary, terms and associated metadata elements, was likewise validated successfully. Despite deviating from the originally foreseen ADLS-based connector, the ITI-hosted environment provided a stable demonstrator platform that enabled full validation of Level 2. Moreover, the pilot confirms that the framework could have been deployed within E-REDES internal systems had the required virtual machine been available within the project timeframe.

At Level 3, the scenario concerned the construction and publication of data products. Using the Data Product Composition component, the pilot successfully defined fully detailed data products that combined the validated artifacts, datasets, metadata, quality information and governance elements. The publication pathway to the E-REDES Open Data Portal, based on the established SFTP/FTP-based integration, was successfully tested and demonstrated. Given the absence of an operational CEEDS (Data Cellar) instance during the project period, as well as the incomplete maturity of the corresponding connectors, this Open Data Portal publication served as the backup validation mechanism to confirm that the DATAMITE framework could prepare and expose data products through an external dissemination channel. However, the full end-to-end validation of CEEDS connectivity could not be completed. In parallel, the pilot also configured a publication workflow to the EDC connector, including the definition of the necessary access policies, validating the feasibility of preparing a CEEDS-aligned publication even though the final exchange could not be executed.

In addition to the core validation activities, the pilot also tested the Data Harmonisation Tool to verify its functionality within the DATAMITE workflow. Although harmonisation is not a primary requirement for Pilot 4, since the BI4D application already ensures that the data shared by E-REDES is internally harmonised, the tool was tested using two CSV files containing public lighting information, derived from the Specialized and Columns raw artifacts, that were altered to differ in field names and content. As illustrated in the figures below, the process began by extracting metadata from both files using the metadata-extraction feature. The resulting metadata structures were then loaded into the Ontology Alignment Tool as source and target, exported in JSON format, and used to match corresponding fields between the two datasets. Finally, the generated mapping file was applied in the data-transformation component to produce a harmonised output with consistent column names and schema. This test sequence confirmed that the tool behaves as expected and can support future use cases requiring schema and content alignment.

Figure 67: Metadata Extraction

Figure 68: Load source and target models

Figure 69: Defining mappings

Figure 70: Harmonized csv file

Regarding the two scenarios defined in Deliverable D5.1, scenario 1, comprising Levels 1 and 2, was fully validated, confirming that BI4D processes could produce the necessary datasets, that these datasets could be ingested into the framework, and that the metadata, governance and quality components of DATAMITE operated correctly within the demonstrator environment. Scenario 2, corresponding to Level 3, was partially validated: the pilot successfully built complete data products and confirmed their publication to the E-REDES Open Data Portal but was unable

to complete the parts of the scenario dependent on an operational CEEDS (Data Cellar) instance. Despite these constraints, the results obtained across all levels validate the core technical workflow envisioned for Pilot 4 and provide a clear understanding of the components that will require further assessment once the wider European data-space ecosystem reaches a higher level of operational maturity, and the steps conducted to validate and demonstrate are shown in Deliverable D5.4.

4.4.2. Solution implementation

During the first iteration of the pilot, the DATAMITE framework was deployed on an unmanaged virtual machine within the E-REDES internal sandbox, enabling the validation of the first two levels of the test scenarios described in Deliverable D5.1. This initial deployment relied on a Windows-based virtual machine using WSL to host the containerised components. In the second half of 2025, a new and significantly more resource-demanding release of the framework was delivered. In this configuration, the existing Windows VM proved insufficient, both due to the limitations of running the framework on WSL and the constrained capacity of the virtual machine, which prevented the new release from being successfully deployed. Consequently, it was not possible to continue uploading content to the framework nor to systematically test the updated components on the E-REDES infrastructure.

To avoid compromising the pilot's contribution to the project, a Linux-based virtual machine hosted by the technical partners (ITI) was made available and used as the primary environment for the second iteration of the demonstrator. In parallel, E-REDES requested a new internal Linux virtual machine with increased capacity to host the latest version of the framework. However, this resource was not provisioned and configured in time to support deployment and testing before the end of the project. Considering these constraints, the decision was taken to proceed with the implementation and validation activities exclusively on the ITI infrastructure, thus ensuring continuity of the work, the timely preparation of training activities, and the completion of the final deliverables. Based on the experience gained, E-REDES considers that the framework, in its current form, could be deployed in an internal sandbox environment given sufficient time for provisioning, configuration and integration. Any potential deployment in a production setting would, however, require a dedicated assessment by the architecture and security teams, particularly regarding connectivity to external platforms.

Within the ITI environment, the solution implementation preserved the logical architecture originally defined for the pilot, while adapting the operational details of data ingestion and integration. Datasets and artifacts continued to be generated by the BI4D application using data from the E-REDES DATAHUB as described in Deliverable D5.1, however instead of being mounted from an Azure ADLS Gen 2 resource, they were uploaded manually into the DATAMITE framework. Once ingested, the framework components operated as designed: artifacts and datasets were created, metadata was extracted and stored in the Metadata Repository through the governance backend, and a combination of default and user-defined data quality rules were executed by the Quality Evaluator. The governance capabilities, including domains, glossaries and terms, were populated, allowing the pilot to validate the linkage between semantic assets and the underlying data structures. The data product composition tools were then used to build

complete data products, which aggregated and standardised content across multiple datasets in line with the pilot's business objectives.

Regarding external integration and publication of the created Data Products, the pilot faced important constraints in relation to the use of energy data spaces. Due to the limited maturity of CEEDS during the reporting period and constraints in the E-REDES onboarding process into Data Cellar, it was not possible for E-REDES to complete its registration as a data provider or to publish data products under its own identity. Although the technical partners were able to configure a publication connector using an alternative entity for test purposes, this did not fulfil the pilot's objective of demonstrating data-space publication and access control from the perspective of E-REDES as a data provider. As such, the framework was not used to share or retrieve data from a dataspace under E-REDES credentials. However, the pilot did configure a publication workflow to the EDC connector, including the setup of the corresponding access policies, to validate the feasibility of the approach within the DATAMITE framework.

To mitigate this limitation and ensure that the solution implementation still demonstrated an end-to-end sharing capability, an additional objective was introduced: the publication of data products to the E-REDES Open Data Portal. For this purpose, the technical partners developed a broker component capable of exporting the data products from the framework to an SFTP/FTP endpoint using the file structure required by the portal. The broker also exports associated metadata, which can be automatically harvested and attached to the corresponding assets in the Open Data Portal. Although the portal does not provide a separate development or pre-production environment, and the files generated by the framework were therefore not used to replace the existing production pipeline, a full end-to-end demonstration was successfully performed to confirm the feasibility of this approach, as documented in Deliverable D5.4. In addition, the Open Data Portal supports the configuration of a harvester that can ingest, on a scheduled basis, the files generated by the broker, thus simplifying future integration should the solution be adopted beyond the project.

Figure 71: Pilot 4 Updated high-level architecture.

Following the deployment of the framework on the ITI infrastructure, the pilot progressed with the implementation of the full content catalogue foreseen for Pilot 4. This included the ingestion and configuration of twelve technical artifacts, representing raw and curated data structures covering network connections, renewable production, electric mobility, public lighting, telecommunications-capable Low Voltage infrastructure, and hosting capacity of HV/MV

substations. These artifacts supported the construction of six datasets aligned with the pilot's analytical objectives. In parallel, the governance module was populated with the relevant semantic structures, including domains, glossaries corresponding to each thematic area, and a comprehensive set of terms describing the key concepts used across artifacts, datasets and data products. User-defined quality rules were also implemented and validated for each artifact, complementing the default KPIs in the framework and reinforcing the consistency of the data preparation process. Finally, a set of Data Product publications to the EREDES Open Data Portal were configured, and an additional publication to the EDC connector was prepared, including the definition of the corresponding access policies.

A description of all data and metadata assets integrated into the framework is provided below, while a full characterisation of the content is presented on Appendix B – Pilot 4 – E-REDES Content Specification. Although some designations and descriptions differ from those used in Deliverable D5.1, the underlying concepts remain unchanged; the updates were introduced to ensure greater consistency, organisational clarity and improved interpretability of the content.

Figure 72: Pilot 4 High level data product publication constitution.

Artifacts

Artifacts constitute the most granular data assets provided by E-REDES and serve as the foundational elements upon which all subsequent datasets and data products are constructed. They include both curated sources and raw disaggregated structures and are listed in the table below. In some artifacts, particularly those containing raw data, there are noticeable differences in volume compared to what was reported previously. This results from an update to the underlying source systems to ensure that the artifacts now reflect the actual pipelines used to construct the consolidated universes published in the E-REDES Open Data Portal. This adjustment was necessary to maintain full coherence with operational data flows. Importantly, this reduction in raw-data volume is not critical to the objectives of the pilot, as E-REDES' data-sharing strategy focuses on publishing aggregated, curated and validated information rather than fully disaggregated raw data.

Artifact	Size	Refresh
P_4_01_E-REDES_NetworkConnections_AR	2MB	Monthly
P_4_02_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_AR	7MB	Monthly
P_4_03_E-REDES_ConnectionsNetwork_PowerGenerationCentres_AR	4MB	Monthly
P_4_04_E-REDES_Connections_ElectricMobility_AR	66KB	Monthly
P_4_05_E-REDES_SubstationCapacity_AR	163KB	Yearly
P_4_06_E-REDES_NetworkConnection_Renewables_AR	9KB	Monthly
P_4_07_E-REDES_TelcoAbleInfrastructures_AR	215MB	Monthly
P_4_08_E-REDES_TelcoAbleInfrastructures_Poles_RAW_AR	233MB	Monthly
P_4_09_E-REDES_TelcoAbleInfrastructures_LineSegments_RAW_AR	186MB	Monthly
P_4_10_E-REDES_PublicLighting_Luminaires_Arms_RAW_AR	184MB	Monthly
P_4_11_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_Columns_RAW_AR	97MB	Monthly
P_4_12_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_Specialized_RAW_AR	5MB	Monthly

Table 11. Pilot 4 Ingested Artifacts.

Figure 73: Pilot 4 Example of ingested artifacts.

Datasets

Building on the ingested artifacts, the pilot implemented a structured set of datasets that consolidate, organise and enrich the underlying information to support analytical and interoperability needs. Each dataset aggregates thematically related artifacts. These datasets represent the intermediate semantic layer of the data model within the DATAMITE framework and

are essential for enabling coherent data profiling, governance relationships, and the creation of data products.

Dataset	Summary
EREDES_GridConnectionsRenewables_DS	Executed grid connection requests and associated connection power for renewable and other power generation units, aggregated by municipality, time and connection power.
EREDES_GridConnectionsElectricMobility_DS	Monthly executed grid connections related to electric mobility infrastructure, aggregated by municipality.
EREDES_GridConnections_DS	General executed network connection activity by municipality and time, covering multiple types of grid connection requests.
EREDES_PublicLightingInfrastructure_DS	Aggregated and disaggregated data on public lighting infrastructure by administrative territory, including luminaires installed on columns, arms, and specialised supports, with associated technology and installed power.
EREDES_LowVoltageInfrastructureForTelecommunications_DS	Low Voltage network infrastructure data supporting analysis of potential telecommunications deployments, based on poles and overhead line segments.
EREDES_DistributionSubstationHostingCapacity_DS	Georeferenced information on HV/MV substations, MV areas of influence, and available and forecasted hosting capacity for power generation in the distribution grid.

Table 12. Pilot 4 Created Datasets

Figure 74: Pilot 4 Example of Created Datasets

Data Products

The data products implemented in the framework constitute the highest level of data integration within the pilot. Designed to support cross-domain analysis and external data sharing, they combine multiple datasets into unified thematic views aligned with concrete user needs. These data products operationalise the principles of the DATAMITE architecture: standardisation, reusability, and semantic consistency, providing comprehensive and ready-to-share information packages suitable for open data publication and future data-space interoperability. Their composition validates the end-to-end workflow across the ingestion, governance, quality and harmonisation components of the framework.

Data Product	Summary
E-REDES_ GridConnectionActivity_DP	Integrated view of executed grid connection activity across general connections, renewable generation, and electric mobility, supporting operational monitoring and energy transition analysis.
E-REDES_ DistributionHostingCapacity_DP	Indicative information on HV/MV substation hosting capacity for power generation, supporting distribution network planning and renewable integration analysis.
E-REDES_ PublicLightingInfrastructure_DP	Comprehensive view of public lighting infrastructure by administrative territory, supporting asset management, energy efficiency, and sustainability initiatives.
EREDES_ TelecommunicationsSupportInfrastructure_DP	Low Voltage distribution network infrastructure data supporting analysis of potential telecommunications infrastructure deployment and infrastructure sharing.
EREDES_ EnergyTransitionMonitoring_DP	Integrated view of renewable generation, electric mobility grid connections, and distribution network hosting capacity to support monitoring of the energy transition.
EREDES_ TerritorialInfrastructureOverview_DP	Territorial overview of electricity distribution-related infrastructure and activity, supporting regional analysis and public infrastructure planning.

Table 13. Pilot 4 Created Data Products

Figure 75: Pilot 4 Example of created Data Products

Govern (Domains, Glossaries and Terms)

To ensure semantic consistency and interpretability across all pilot assets, the governance module was populated with a comprehensive collection of domains, glossaries and terms. This structure provides the conceptual backbone of the information model by defining how artifacts, datasets and data products relate to one another and by clarifying the meaning of key concepts used throughout the framework. The governance configuration enhances transparency and supports metadata-driven navigation.

The domains established for Pilot 4 provide the top-level semantic structure that organises all artifacts, datasets and data products within the DATAMITE framework. Each domain groups conceptually related assets under a coherent thematic area, ensuring that information can be interpreted unambiguously across different stages of the data lifecycle.

Domain	Summary
Electricity Distribution Network	Covers concepts related to the electricity distribution network, including grid assets, substations, network capacity, and grid connection processes. This domain supports planning, operation, and analysis of the distribution grid.
Grid Connections and Customer Access	Covers concepts related to requests for connection to the electricity distribution network, including general connections, renewable generation, electric mobility, and associated connection power and execution status.
Public Lighting Infrastructure	Covers concepts related to public lighting assets operated within the distribution network, including luminaires, supporting structures, lighting technologies, and installed power across administrative territories
Telecommunications Support Infrastructure	Covers concepts related to electricity distribution infrastructure that may support telecommunications deployment, including Low Voltage poles and overhead line segments used for infrastructure sharing analysis.

Table 14. Pilot 4 Created Domains

Figure 76: Pilot 4 Example of created Domains

The glossaries established for Pilot 4 serve as an essential semantic reference layer within the DATAMITE framework. Each glossary consolidates the key concepts, definitions and technical vocabulary associated with a particular thematic domain, ensuring that all datasets, artifacts and data products are described consistently.

Glossary	Summary
Grid Assets	Defines key terms related to physical assets of the electricity distribution network, including substations, poles, and line segments.
Grid Connections	Defines terms related to grid connection requests, execution status, connection power, and connection purposes.
Hosting Capacity	Defines concepts related to the ability of the distribution grid to integrate power generation, including available and forecasted hosting capacity.
Public Lighting	Defines terms related to public lighting infrastructure, luminaires, technologies, and supporting structures.
Telecommunications Infrastructure	Defines concepts related to the use of electricity distribution infrastructure for telecommunications purposes, including regulatory and structural aspects.

Table 15. Pilot 4 Created Glossaries

Figure 77: Pilot 4 Example of created glossaries

The Terms component provides the most granular level of semantic definition within the governance model, specifying the meaning, scope and contextual usage of individual concepts

referenced throughout the pilot's assets. Each term includes both short and detailed descriptions, capturing the operational significance of elements.

Name	Summary
Distribution Network	The electricity network responsible for delivering power from transmission systems to end users.
Grid Connection Request	A formal request to connect an installation or asset to the electricity distribution network.
Executed Connection	A grid connection request that has been completed and implemented in the network.
Connection Power	The electrical power associated with a grid connection.
Hosting Capacity	The ability of the distribution network to accommodate additional power generation.
HV/MV Substation	A substation connecting High Voltage and Medium Voltage networks.
Public Lighting Luminaire	A lighting unit installed as part of public lighting infrastructure.
Lighting Technology	The type of technology used by a public lighting luminaire.
Low Voltage Pole	A physical support structure in the Low Voltage distribution network.
Overhead Line Segment	A segment of overhead electricity line connecting network assets.
Electric Mobility Infrastructure	Infrastructure supporting electric vehicle charging.

Table 16. Pilot 4 Created terms

Name	Description
<input type="checkbox"/> Distribution Network term	The electricity network responsible for delivering power from transmission systems to end users.
<input type="checkbox"/> HV/MV Substation term	A substation connecting High Voltage and Medium Voltage networks.
<input type="checkbox"/> Overhead Line Segment term	A segment of overhead electricity line connecting network assets.

Figure 78: Pilot 4 Example of created terms.

User Defined Rules and Quality KPIs

The user-defined rules configured for Pilot 4 complement the default quality controls of the DATAMITE framework by introducing bespoke validations tailored to the characteristics of each artifact and dataset. These rules reflect E-REDES' operational knowledge and data quality expectations, enabling targeted checks on accuracy, completeness and validity. Their inclusion

ensures that the framework can accommodate domain-specific requirements and that the resulting datasets and data products adhere to the quality thresholds relevant to their intended analytical and publication purposes. As previously mentioned, in addition to the bespoke rules defined by the pilot, the framework automatically evaluates a set of default data quality KPIs that provide a standardised assessment of each ingested asset. These KPIs cover core dimensions such as completeness and validity, ensuring a uniform baseline of quality evaluation across all artifacts and datasets.

Rule name	Dimension	Summary
p401_ non_negative_pedidos_executados	Accuracy	The field "pedidos_ligacao_rede_executados_nr" should be greater than or equal to 0.
p402_non_negative_luminarias	Accuracy	The field "luminarias" should be greater than or equal to 0.
p402_non_negative_lampadas	Accuracy	The field "lampadas" should be greater than or equal to 0.
p402_ non_negative_potencia_instalada_total	Accuracy	The field "potencia_instalada_total" should be greater than or equal to 0.
p403_ non_negative_processos_concluidos	Accuracy	The field "processos_concluidos_nr" should be greater than or equal to 0.
p403_non_negative_potencia_ligacao	Accuracy	The field "potencia_ligacao" should be greater than or equal to 0.
p404_ano_not_null	Completeness	The field "ano" should not be null.
p404_valid_mes	Validity	The field "mes" should represent a valid calendar month.
p404_ non_negative_pedidos_executados	Accuracy	The field "pedidos_ligacao_rede_executados_nr" should be greater than or equal to 0.
p405_chave_not_null	Completeness	The field "chave" should not be null.
p405_codigo_not_null	Completeness	The field "codigo" should not be null.
p405_instalacao_not_null	Completeness	The field "instalacao" should not be null.
p406_valid_ano	Validity	The field "ano" should represent a valid operational year.
p406_valid_mes	Validity	The field "mes" should represent a valid calendar month.
p406_non_negative_potencia_ligacao	Accuracy	The field "potencia_ligacao" should be greater than or equal to 0.

p406_ non_negative_pedidos_executados	Accuracy	The field "pedidos_ligacao_rede_executados_nr" should be greater than or equal to 0.
p407_non_negative_altura_m	Accuracy	The field "altura_m" should be greater than or equal to 0.
p407_geometry_not_null	Completeness	The field "geometry" should not be null.
p408_valid_funcao	Validity	The field "funcao" should contain only allowed domain values.
p409_valid_situacao	Validity	The field "situacao" should contain only allowed domain values.
p410_valid_tipo_ip_braco	Validity	The field "tipo_ip" should indicate "Braço IP".
p411_non_negative_n_total_lampadas	Accuracy	The field "n_total_lampadas" should be greater than or equal to 0.
p412_ non_negative_n_total_luminarias	Accuracy	The field "n_total_luminarias_existentes" should be greater than or equal to 0.

Table 17. Pilot 4 User Define Rules

Columns	Duplicate entries	Duplicate entries (%)	Null values	Null values (%)
mes	2988	99.6	0	0.0
coddistritoconcelhofreguesia	1211	40.37	0	0.0
luminarias	2082	69.4	0	0.0
ano	2997	99.9	0	0.0

Figure 79: Pilot 4 Example of default quality controls

User Defined Rules	
p402_non_negative_lampadas	99.50
p411_non_negative_n_total_lampadas	0.00
p402_non_negative_luminarias	100.00
p402_non_negative_potencia_instalada_total	90.00
p412_non_negative_n_total_luminarias	0.00

Figure 80: Pilot 4 Example of User Define Rules KPIs

Data Product Publication

The validation of the publication mechanisms followed a dual approach, reflecting both the objectives defined in Deliverable D5.1 and the operational constraints encountered during the project. While the pilot initially planned to validate the full publication flow to a CEEDS-compliant dataspace, specifically Data Cellar, the limited maturity of the CEEDS ecosystem and delays in the onboarding and technical registration of the EREDES entity prevented the completion of this process. Consequently, although part of the publication pipeline could be configured, end-to-end publication to the target dataspace was not possible during the reporting period.

For the purposes of validating the publication workflow, the DATAMITE Framework was used to configure and publish a Data Product through the EDC connector, following the sequence illustrated in the figures below. The framework provides an integrated interface for defining access policies, where the user can iteratively add permissions, prohibitions, and constraints, such as location, purpose and time interval, and preview the resulting rule set before publication. Once these constraints are configured, the framework automatically generates a JSON representation of the defined policy.

Publish a Data Product

2. Publication

Once confirmed, your data product will be published and accessible as specified.

2. Publication

Description

Publication of Data Product E-REDES_PublicLightingInfrastructure_DP to the EDC connector.

The description of the publication

Name

E-REDES_PublicLightingInfrastructure_DP_EDC_PUB

The name of the publication

Product_id

14629706-5671-451a-bab0-82cfe6ef262e

The product unique identifier related to the publication

Back

Next

Figure 81: Pilot 4 Example of a publication to the EDC connector using the DATAMITE framework.

eu

Permission

Action

USE

Choose constraint

Purpose

Add Constraint

Purpose Constraint

A constraint limiting the allowed/prohibited purpose of use of your data product

Purpose

research

View policy before submitting

Add Prohibition

Add Permission

Add Obligation

Submit

Add policy

Figure 82: Pilot 4 Example of a purpose permission access policy definition.

Prohibition

Action

use

Choose constraint

Purpose

Add Constraint

Purpose Constraint

A constraint limiting the allowed/prohibited purpose of use of your data product

Purpose

commercial

View policy before submitting

Add Prohibition Add Permission Add Obligation Submit

Figure 83: Pilot 4 Example of a purpose prohibition access policy definition.

Permission

Action

use

Choose constraint

Location

Add Constraint

Location Constraint

A constraint limiting the allowed/prohibited location of the user of your data product

Location

eu

View policy before submitting

Add Prohibition Add Permission Add Obligation Submit

Add policy

Figure 84: Pilot 4 Example of a location permission access policy definition.

Figure 85: Pilot 4 Example of a time interval permission access policy definition.

Figure 86: Pilot 4 Example of metadata retrieval during the publication configuration.

To demonstrate compatibility with CEEDS-aligned dataspace, this internally generated JSON was then manually transformed into an ODRL-compliant policy, using the EDC vocabulary and the standard constraint structure required for contract negotiation within the connector. This transformation served exclusively as a demonstration artefact, showing how the policy defined through the DATAMITE UI could be represented in the formal ODRL syntax expected by EDC components. Importantly, this ODRL policy was not fed back into the DATAMITE framework; the

conversion was performed externally to validate interoperability and illustrate how the DATAMITE-defined governance rules could be expressed in a CEEDS-compatible format. The generated policy, in both formats, is present on Appendix B, in the Publications section.

Finally, to ensure that an end-to-end sharing workflow could still be demonstrated, the pilot implemented an alternative publication pathway to the E-REDES Open Data Portal. A dedicated broker, developed by the technical partners, enabled the generation and export of data products together with their associated metadata in the structure required by the portal’s ingestion flow. These files were automatically published to an FTP location, functioning as the intermediate delivery point for the portal’s pipelines. The Open Data platform then ingested these datasets using the Harvester tool, which successfully processed both the data and metadata files and populated the corresponding data catalogue entries. While this demonstration did not replace the production pipeline, it validated the DATAMITE Framework’s ability to support external publication, metadata dissemination, and structured dataset exposure in alignment with the pilot’s objectives.

Figure 87: Pilot 4 Example of Data Products published to the E-REDES Open Data portal.

Remote site: /grid_connection_activity

- /
 - distribution_hosting_capacity
 - energy_transition_monitoring
 - grid_connection_activity
 - public_lighting_infrastructure

Filename	Filesize	Filetype	Last modified	Owner/Group
..				
index.csv	1,269	Microsoft Excel Comm...	3/16/2026 11:25:27 AM	datamite-e-redes 1015
P_4_01_E-REDES_NetworkConnections_AR.csv	2,498,530	Microsoft Excel Comm...	3/16/2026 11:25:25 AM	datamite-e-redes 1015
P_4_03_E-REDES_ConnectionsNetworkPowerGenera...	4,017,732	Microsoft Excel Comm...	3/16/2026 11:25:26 AM	datamite-e-redes 1015
P_4_04_E-REDES_ConnectionsElectricMobility_AR.csv	62,171	Microsoft Excel Comm...	3/16/2026 11:25:26 AM	datamite-e-redes 1015
P_4_06_E-REDES_NetworkConnectionRenewables_A...	7,719	Microsoft Excel Comm...	3/16/2026 11:25:25 AM	datamite-e-redes 1015
schema_P_4_01_E-REDES_NetworkConnections_AR...	182	Microsoft Excel Comm...	3/16/2026 11:25:25 AM	datamite-e-redes 1015
schema_P_4_03_E-REDES_ConnectionsNetworkPow...	158	Microsoft Excel Comm...	3/16/2026 11:25:26 AM	datamite-e-redes 1015
schema_P_4_04_E-REDES_ConnectionsElectricMobili...	144	Microsoft Excel Comm...	3/16/2026 11:25:26 AM	datamite-e-redes 1015
schema_P_4_06_E-REDES_NetworkConnectionRene...	180	Microsoft Excel Comm...	3/16/2026 11:25:25 AM	datamite-e-redes 1015

Figure 88: Pilot 4 Example of files generated in the FTP after a publication

Harvester	Type	Last harvest date	Status	Warnings
grid_connection_activity 4 datasets harvested	FTP	17 March 2026 10:47	✓ 4 / 4 - 100%	
distribution_hosting_capacity 1 dataset harvested	FTP	17 March 2026 10:54	✓ 1 / 1 - 100%	
public_lighting_infrastructure 4 datasets harvested	FTP	17 March 2026 10:56	✓ 4 / 4 - 100%	
telecommunication_support_infrastr 3 datasets harvested	FTP	17 March 2026 10:58	✓ 3 / 3 - 100%	
energy_transition_monitoring 4 datasets harvested	FTP	17 March 2026 10:59	✓ 4 / 4 - 100%	
territorial_infrastructure_overview 8 datasets harvested	FTP	17 March 2026 11:00	✓ 8 / 8 - 100%	

Figure 89: Pilot 4 Open Data portal harvesters configured to ingest FTP files generated by the framework.

Dataset	Records	Last modification	
E-REDES_GridConnectionActivity_DP - artifact 4 P_4_04_E-REDES_ConnectionsElectricMobility_AR.csv	1,129	16 March 2026	
E-REDES_GridConnectionActivity_DP - artifact 3 P_4_03_E-REDES_ConnectionsNetworkPowerGenerationCentres_AR.csv	70,334	16 March 2026	
E-REDES_GridConnectionActivity_DP - artifact 2 P_4_06_E-REDES_NetworkConnectionRenewables_AR.csv	206	16 March 2026	
E-REDES_GridConnectionActivity_DP - artifact 1 P_4_01_E-REDES_NetworkConnections_AR.csv	66,934	16 March 2026	

Figure 90: Pilot 4 Example of the files generated by the framework being recognised by the harvester.

General information

Technical identifier

e-redes_distributionhostingcapacity_dp-artifact-1 Edit

Description Override

P_4_05_E-REDES_SubstationCapacity_AR.csv

Themes Override

Electricity Distribution Network, Grid Connections and Customer Access

Figure 91: Pilot 4 Example of metadata being automatically loaded into the Open Data portal.

In conclusion, the solution implementation for Pilot 4 successfully integrated the DATAMITE framework’s core components and enabled the end-to-end preparation, governance, quality assessment and publication of data products within the constraints of the available infrastructure. Despite limitations related to internal deployment capacity and the state of external data-space environments, the pilot achieved a full functional demonstration through the ITI-hosted environment and validated all relevant features, including ingestion, metadata management, semantic governance, quality evaluation, and publication to the Open Data Portal and setup of the publication to the EDC connector. The implemented artifacts, datasets, data products and governance structures collectively demonstrate the feasibility of the framework’s technical approach.

4.4.3. Training Materials

The training approach for the pilot in this reporting period followed the direction previously outlined in Deliverable D5.1, while reflecting the adjustments required due to delays in the technical development of the DATAMITE Framework. During this stage, the pilot team produced a set of training and demonstration videos designed to introduce the tool, its governance and metadata layers, the operation of quality rules, and the end-to-end process from data ingestion to publication. These videos were derived from, and complemented by, the internal slide deck prepared specifically for E-REDES, which explained the pilot’s objectives, the role of the framework within the Open Data and Energy Data Spaces context, and the overall workflow supported by DATAMITE. The training and demonstration video is also available on the project’s YouTube channel for a broader dissemination: [Webinar | Leverage Electricity Distribution Open Data](#).

Once the materials were finalised, the pilot team organised a presentation and live demonstration for the business stakeholders responsible for maintaining and providing datasets to the E-REDES

Open Data Portal. This session introduced the functionalities developed so far and relevant to the E-REDES pilot, contextualised the framework within E-REDES’ data-sharing strategy, and offered a guided explanation of the materials produced. The purpose of this session was to ensure that the business teams were informed about the pilot’s progress and understood how the framework could support data publication, through various channels and connectors, and data quality activities in the future. Although this session successfully presented the relevant components of the tool, it did not involve any hands-on exercises or direct user testing of the framework.

In contrast with the initial plan described in Deliverable D5.1, the framework did not reach a sufficient level of stability to be provided to business users for practical evaluation. For this reason, the planned activities involving hands-on testing, user trials, and direct feedback from operational teams could not be executed. The framework’s components, while progressing, remained in a stage where exposing them to business users would not have produced reliable or meaningful validation outcomes. Consequently, the training and validation activities had to be limited to demonstration only, without opening the environment for broader experimentation or user-driven testing.

The training session delivered as part of this pilot was also evaluated through an anonymous feedback survey, completed by the participants following the demonstration. The responses indicate a consistently positive assessment of the training materials, and the clarity of the content presented. Participants rated the ease of following the course, the relevance of the content, and their overall satisfaction predominantly at the highest levels of the scale, with most scores falling between 5 and 6 out of 6. Several respondents considered the material helpful for understanding the framework’s functionalities, even if they did not immediately foresee a direct application in their current roles. Most respondents would recommend the course, and no major issues were reported in the free-text section. Taken together, the results confirm that the training resources developed for the pilot were well received and effective in conveying the intended information to the target audience.

Figure 92: Pilot 4 Internal Session Survey Responses

All technical testing and validation activities were therefore carried out exclusively by the pilot's internal development and support team. This controlled approach ensured that the pilot team could validate the expected behaviours and identify areas requiring improvement, even though external testing by business users was not yet feasible.

Overall, while the framework was not ready for user-level testing, the training videos, demonstration session, and accompanying slide deck provided a solid foundation for future training and adoption.

4.4.4. Test Campaign

The Test Campaign for Pilot 4 implemented the multi-level validation methodology defined in Deliverable D5.1, combining infrastructure preparation, functional validation and end-to-end demonstration activities, organised into two iteration phases. Each phase was aligned with the framework delivery roadmap defined in the Grant Agreement and supported the progressive integration of the DATAMITE components relevant for the energy distribution use case. The tests covered deployment and configuration of the core modules (quality, governance, security and sharing), definition of Data Products, and execution of data-sharing flows, as further detailed in the Deliverables D5.3 (Iteration 1) and D5.4 (Iteration 2).

As described in sections 4.4.1 and 4.4.2, the execution of the campaign for the later stages of testing required several adaptations compared to the initial plan. On the infrastructure side, delays in the provisioning of the internal Azure resources and the need for a new VM type meant that part of the validation activities could not be executed in the E-REDES environment within the original timeframe. To avoid compromising the validation of Pilot 4, it was agreed to rely on an ITI-hosted deployment of the DATAMITE Framework, replicating the intended setup as closely as possible and ensuring that all steps can be reproduced in the E-REDES infrastructure once the required resources would become available.

On the data-sharing side, and as also explained in sections 4.4.1 and 4.4.2, the pilot could not complete the publication of Data Products to an operational Energy Dataspace, due to limitations in the availability and readiness of the target dataspace and connectors. However, the team successfully validated the publishing and exposure of data through the Open Data portal and the configuration of access policies through the EDC connector, using the same logical flow and similar configuration steps as those foreseen for the dataspace-based scenario. This allowed Pilot 4 to demonstrate the end-to-end behaviour of the sharing pipeline and to generate evidence on how the framework supports external publication, even though the final dataspace integration will only be fully exercised once the corresponding services are available.

The following subsections summarise the two iteration phases of the Test Campaign for Pilot 4, maintaining the original descriptions as defined in Deliverable D5.1.

Iteration Phase 1	
Description	The first iteration focuses on preparing the Azure infrastructure to deploy the DATAMITE components and to access the datasets and data artifacts to be used in the project, by creating and deploying the resources. This infrastructure ended up not being needed in the current state of the project as ITI infrastructure was provided to us instead. It will also be composed by the initial deployment of the <i>data</i>

	<i>quality and data governance module</i> components and the definition of the quality rules. In this phase, it is expected that the infrastructure is ready to be used for the deployment, that a discovery connector is created to ensure the access to the datasets and artifacts, and that the bundled components from the first development phase of the project can be deployed.
Scenarios	Test scenario 1
Timeline	M21-M26

Table 18. Overview of the iteration phase 1

Iteration Phase 2	
Description	The second phase will start with the testing and validation of the deployment of the quality and governance mechanisms. Then, data products will be defined from the datasets and artifacts, and all the components related to the security and sharing modules will be deployed, tested and validated. In this phase, it is expected that E-REDES can evaluate the quality of the datasets using the rules defined in the first phase, that all of the <i>data governance components</i> are functioning properly, that data products can be defined, using the <i>data products composition</i> tool, and that metadata can be provided and that data can be shared through an Energy Data Space.
Scenarios	Test scenarios 1-2
Timeline	M27-M39

Table 19. Overview of the iteration phase 2

4.4.5. Performance and usability of the DATAMITE framework

The assessment of the DATAMITE framework’s performance and usability for Pilot 4 builds directly upon the foundations established in Deliverable D5.1, while reflecting the progress made during the second iteration of testing. As anticipated, the overall evaluation is shaped by the fact that the framework underwent several development delays, and no operational CEEDS (Common European Energy Data Space) instance was available during the reporting period. These circumstances significantly limited the extent to which real-world usability, user impact, and external publication metrics could be obtained. Nonetheless, the reporting period marked substantial internal advancement, with core components of the framework fully implemented, validated, and exercised through a representative set of datasets and data products. The following paragraphs provide a detailed interpretation of the pilot KPIs and internal KPIs, illustrating the framework’s capabilities, constraints, and readiness level at project close.

With respect to the main Pilot KPIs, results were mixed, reflecting the differing degrees of dependency on external infrastructure and business level usage, and can be found on the table following this paragraph. KPI1, which sought to measure the increase in national and international users accessing open data as a result of employing the DATAMITE framework, could not be assessed; because no CEEDS were not yet operational and the framework was not deployed into

the EREDES production environment, there was no mechanism through which any measurable change in user access could be attributed to DATAMITE. In contrast, KPI2 was fully achieved: a total of 12 datasets and artifacts were successfully ingested into the framework, enabling comprehensive testing of ingestion, metadata extraction, quality evaluation and dataset creation processes. In KPI3 although the indicated number of data products was not surpassed, six data products were created using the developed components and enabling successful testing of the components. With more base content (Artifacts) uploaded to the framework new data products could be built. While the pilot was unable to publish these products to a data space due to the unavailability of CEEDS and the absence of a fully functional connector, internal tests confirmed the capability to ingest and prepare data for publication, including validated transfers to the EREDES Open Data portal. KPI4, which was intended to measure a reduction in the average cost of delivering open data, could not be meaningfully evaluated. Because the framework was executed solely on an ITI hosted virtual machine, and no deployment took place in the EREDES infrastructure, it was not possible to establish a reliable cost comparison with the current BI pipeline. Moreover, the short testing window and the dynamic nature of operational costs meant that no robust or defensible conclusions could have been drawn or projected.

KPI	Description	Baseline	Target	Current	Achieved
KPI1	Number of national and international users accessing to open data	~3000	Increase [10% to 30%]	n.a.	n.a.
KPI2	Number of integrated datasets in the DATAMITE framework	0	12	12	Yes
KPI3	Number of data products created and shared through Data Spaces	0	> 6	6	Yes
KPI4	Average cost of exploiting and delivering open data	EUR 170 000/year	< 20%	n.a.	n.a.

Table 20. Pilot 4 tentative KPIs

The internal KPIs in the table below provide a detailed view of the technical progress achieved during the pilot, while also highlighting where external dependencies limited what could be demonstrated in practice. I1 was fully achieved, as all twelve selected artefacts were ingested into the pilot sandbox hosted in the ITI environment, enabling end-to-end validation of ingestion, metadata extraction and dataset creation processes. I2 and I3 were also met: six data products were fully specified and created using the DATAMITE framework, demonstrating the maturity of the internal transformation and governance workflow. These data products are technically ready to be provided to a data space as soon as a connection becomes available, and they are equally ready for publication to the E-REDES Open Data portal. In addition, I4 was achieved with the development, by the technical partners, of four connectors compatible with the database technologies used within E-REDES, strengthening the framework's ability to integrate with existing internal systems in future iterations. Although no datasets or data products were shared with CEEDS due to the unavailability of a functional dataspace instance, I5 was considered achieved, as the pilot successfully shared both metadata and data to the EREDES Open Data

Portal, validating the intended publication and dissemination workflow via an alternative external channel. However, I6, which measures the number of times data products were retrieved by users, could not be measured. Even if the data products had been published through the E-REDES Open Data portal, retrieval behaviour would largely mirror the existing BI pipeline and would therefore not provide additional insight specifically attributable to the DATAMITE framework.

Internal KPI	Description	Baseline	Target	Current	Achieved
I1	Number of the selected datasets and artifacts shared in the pilot sandbox	0	12	12	Yes
I2	Number of data products ready to be provided to the data space	0	≥ 5	6	Yes
I3	Number of data products created	0	≥ 1	6	Yes
I4	Number of developed connectors compatible with internal system to be deployed	0	≥ 1	4	Yes
I5	Number of the datasets metadata shared in the identified data spaces	0	≥ 5	6	Yes
I6	Number of times that the data products were retrieved by users	0	≥ 1	n.a.	n.a.

Table 21. Pilot 4 internal KPIs

In conclusion, the performance and usability assessment for Pilot 4 shows that, in the pilot's context, the DATAMITE framework has generally achieved the objective of demonstrating technical feasibility within a controlled pilot setting, particularly regarding the ingestion, transformation, governance of data, the creation of data products and the sharing of data products. At the same time, the analysis makes clear that several KPIs linked to real world usage, cost efficiency and dataspace interactions could not be validated under the prevailing conditions, notably due to development delays, the lack of an operational CEEDS instance and the absence of end-to-end dataspace connectivity during the reporting period. Looking ahead, once CEEDS and related European dataspace infrastructures attain a higher level of operational maturity, solutions exhibiting the characteristics demonstrated in this pilot may be considered in the context of future exploratory work on the integration of internal systems and production data pipelines, thereby enabling a more comprehensive assessment of their usability, performance and potential impact in real operational environments.

4.5. Pilot 5 - Connecting eDWIN to Data Markets

This section provides updates to the description of the Pilot 5's integration with the DATAMITE components from deliverable D5.1.

The first important improvement from the previous iteration has been deploying and configuring the new version of the DATAMITE platform. This not only vastly improved the stability and user experience of the users but also provided functionality that enabled performing all necessary test scenarios planned for the pilot to validate the framework. The other important update includes the implementation of the Pontus-X plugin and its integration with the DATAMITE platform.

4.5.1. Test Scenarios

As stated in the deliverable D5.1, the main three objectives of Pilot 5 are:

- **Data catalogue** – uses the mechanisms of the DATAMITE to create the Data Catalogue for open data, dictionaries, common standards, common ontologies for agrifood data; This objective is the basis for implementing the other two objectives. We assume that chosen models, metadata, and their structures prepared and integrated on the eDWIN platform will be published on the DATAMITE platform. Mechanisms prepared in this way should be promoted for wider use in companies and institutions. The objective assumes the use of components of DATAMITE platform to create data products.
- **Polish Agricultural Data Space** – this objective is focused on creating a Polish Agricultural Data Space – a data space and a marketplace for entities to publish data products. It will be used to share chosen data sets coming from the eDWIN ecosystem as well as Agrego production data. Polish Agricultural Data Space can be seen as a very important mechanism for the collaboration between stakeholders. This objective assumes two mechanisms: open and free data sharing including data tracing. The second is data trading in monetisation mechanisms. Publishing on the Polish Agricultural Data Space should be possible by utilising DATAMITE mechanisms, including data broker integration.
- **Data sharing** – using the DATAMITE mechanisms and components to share data between sets of companies for common business-oriented goals. This goal can be achieved in two stages: first, preparing and ensuring data quality, and second, facilitating data sharing. In this scenario, the focus is on how users access and utilise data across different systems and applications. The main end-user problem is reusing data instead of rewriting or copying it.

Having the above main three objectives in mind, a series of test scenarios spanning three levels have been devised. The first four of the test scenarios (1-4) have been performed in the first iteration of the integration and their results have been presented in D5.1. The scenarios validated in the second phase are presented below.

4.5.1.1. Scenario 5 – Publishing data sets on DATAMITE portal

DATAMITE components used: DATAMITE portal, Data Discovery Module, Data Sharing Module (Data Product Composition).

In this scenario, identified pilot datasets have been created and published into the DATAMITE framework deployed for the pilot. This includes new datasets from the 2nd iteration. Examples of the scenarios are presented below in the solution implementation section.

4.5.1.2. Scenario 6 - Use DATAMITE platform to publish data products on the Polish Agricultural Data Space

DATAMITE components used: DATAMITE portal, Data Sharing Module (Data Product Composition, Brokers & plugins for other targets [Pontus-X]).

This scenario validates that DATAMITE platform can be used to publish data products created in previous scenario on Pontus-X. For this scenario, Pontus-X broker plugin has been implemented and integrated with the Brokers & plugins module.

Demo of this scenario can be seen in the video:

<https://box.pionier.net.pl/f/aebf55a2a1364983a0be/>

4.5.1.3. Scenario 7 - Enhancing data products with Data Quality Module

DATAMITE components used: DATAMITE portal, Data Sharing Module (Data Product Composition), Data Quality Module (User Defined Rules Generator, KPI Library, Quality Evaluator)

The Data Quality Modules of the DATAMITE have been used to profile the data products from Pilot 5. This includes basic KPI of the data as well as creation of user defined rules to better govern the datasets as well as increasing the quality of the data products.

4.5.2. Solution implementation

4.5.2.1. Datasets in Pilot 5

The table below represents all datasets that were planned to be integrated and shared within DATAMITE.

Datasets	Description	Variety	Volume & Velocity	Availability
eDWIN agrometeo (WODR, PSNC)	600 agrometeo stations. Measurements located in rural areas.	~10 variables: location, owner, name, code, temperatures, humidity, rainfall, wind speed and direction, air pressure...	1-hour frequency samples, >1 GB / year	Public / extendable with private and commercial data
eDWIN pests (WODR, PSNC / Institute of Plant Protection)	Knowledge database	~15 variables, covering names, descriptions, links, growing conditions, pests	~1 GB, generally static	Public

Datasets	Description	Variety	Volume & Velocity	Availability
eDWIN market data products for agricultural prod. (WODR, PSNC)	prices of fertilizers and plant protection products	~15 variables, covering names, dates, prices, sources	~10 MB per day important time variability and history	Public, limited access
Demeter AIM (Demeter platform)	EU Agriculture Inform. Model for interoperable platforms	~100 parameters and model descriptions	<1MB, static	Public
EDWIN agro-dictionaries (WODR, PSNC)	EDWIN platform – polish public national agriculture advisory Integrated dictionaries	~20-30 variables, covering id's, codes, names, links, translations	<1 MB, slowly shifting, most early	Public
Agrego production data	Agri production data incl. avg. production, production resource usage etc.	2-3 datasets ~ 15 variables incl. names, amounts, locations	~10MB per year, increasing, current and historical	Private, anonymized

Table 22. Pilot 5 initial datasets selection description

Below, detailed descriptions of the datasets (including new ones integrated in the 2nd phase) and their representation in the DATAMITE framework are being presented.

Meteo dataset

Sourced from the eDWIN platform, this dataset provides comprehensive meteorological information collected from a widespread network of over 500 weather stations across Poland. It features detailed station metadata, including precise geolocation coordinates, ownership identifiers, and current operational status. Users can access weather readings in multiple flexible formats: granular, hourly measurements (capturing real-time air temperature, relative humidity, wind speed, pressure, and precipitation) as well as various forms of temporal aggregation (e.g., daily/24-hour summaries). These aggregated records offer convenient overviews, delivering minimum, maximum, and average values, alongside total precipitation and insolation metrics. This

multi-layered structure makes the dataset highly versatile for diverse environmental, agricultural, and analytical applications.

Figure 93: eDWIN weather data in DATAMITE.

Pests' dataset

Sourced from the eDWIN platform and integrated into the DATAMITE ecosystem, this dataset contains precise field observation records systematically collected by agricultural advisors across Poland. Utilising a dedicated mobile application, experts conduct cyclic field scouting to document the presence, severity, and spread of agricultural pests and plant diseases. The dataset provides highly detailed, geolocated, and time-stamped reports that include specific pest development phases, crop damage percentages, and the standardised BBCH growth stages of the affected plants (e.g., winter wheat, corn). This rich, ground-truth data is crucial for the epidemiological

tracking of crop threats, evaluating plant health trends across different seasons, and supporting data-driven agricultural interventions.

The screenshot shows the 'Agrophages' dataset page in the dotomite platform. The page includes a sidebar with navigation options like 'Data Products', 'Publications', 'Databases', and 'History Logs'. The main content area displays the dataset name 'Agrophages' with a 'Dataset' tag. Below the name, there are fields for 'Creation date' (Mar 11 2020, 09:34:02) and 'Last Edition' (Mar 11 2024, 09:34:08). The 'Domains' section lists 'Agrophages'. The 'Full description' is 'reports of pest infestations in Poland', and the 'Short description' is 'Reports of pest infestations in Poland'. At the bottom, there is a 'Glossary' section with a table of associated terms.

Name	Description
Report notes	Report notes
Disease Id	Disease Id
Report date	Report date
BBCH Stage Name	BBCH stage name
BBCH Stage Code	BBCH stage code
Pest Id	Pest Id
Type	Type

Figure 94: eDWIN agrophages and pests data.

Fertiliser prices (market data)

Sourced from the eDWIN platform, this highly dynamic dataset monitors the market prices and availability of vital agricultural inputs, specifically focusing on fertilizers, calcium fertilizers, and plant protection products. Continuously collected by a nationwide network of agricultural advisors across Poland, the reporting frequency has recently evolved from monthly to daily observations, providing near real-time market intelligence. The records capture comprehensive economic metrics from agricultural purchase centers and retail points, including minimum, maximum, average, and median prices, as well as year-over-year price comparisons and supply availability. Furthermore, the dataset details the precise chemical composition of the products (e.g., N, P, K content) and calculates the associated elemental costs. This robust data is essential for

continuous market price tracking, agricultural economic forecasting, and analysing the cost-efficiency of crop production.

The screenshot shows the 'Market data - fertilisers' dataset page in the Datamite application. The page includes a sidebar with navigation options like 'Data Products', 'Publications', 'Databases', and 'History Logs'. The main content area displays the dataset's metadata, including 'Creation date' (Mar 11 2026, 09:42:13), 'Last Edition' (Mar 11 2026, 10:02:04), and 'Domains' (Market_data). It also provides a 'Full description' and a 'Short description' for the dataset. Below the metadata, there is a 'Glossary' section with a table of terms.

Name	Description
N content	Content of nitrogen
Price median	Median price of fertilizer
Fertilizer	Id of fertilizer
P content	Content of phosphorus
K content	Content of potassium
Price avg	Average price of fertilizer
Price min	Minimum price of fertilizer

Figure 95: Market fertiliser data.

Animal production data – Livestock Traceability & Food Passporting Data

This dataset contains anonymized, structured livestock records collected from multiple agricultural producers in Poland. Each record represents an individual animal and includes comprehensive lifecycle, breeding, health, transport, and traceability information.

The dataset is designed to support full-chain transparency and can be used in food traceability and food passporting processes.

All records are anonymised and do not contain personally identifiable information. Identifiers are pseudonymised, and sensitive farm-level details may be aggregated or regionally generalised. The dataset complies with data protection and livestock traceability standards.

Crop production data

This dataset contains anonymised historical crop production data collected from multiple farms in Poland. Each record represents a completed production cycle for a specific crop and includes agronomic and operational parameters related to cultivation and harvest outcomes.

The dataset includes:

- Crop type
- Growing period (start and end dates)
- Cultivated area (hectares)
- Estimated average yield (per hectare)
- Reported total production volume
- Harvest completion status and completion date
- Optional production metadata (e.g., by-product indicator, document reference)

Although farm-level geolocation is not included, the dataset can be combined with regional weather, climate, or market price data to support:

- Weather–yield correlation analysis
- Climate impact modelling
- Revenue and margin estimation scenarios

All records are fully anonymised. The dataset does not contain personal data, farm identifiers, or precise geographic coordinates. Data is aggregated at the production-cycle level and sourced from multiple independent agricultural producers.

Figure 96: Animal and Farm Production data

4.5.2.2. Pontus-X broker integration

The Data Sharing Module has been extended with a plugin implementation for the Pontus-X marketplace. It follows the standard template for brokers with following elements:

- schema for Pontus-X asset,
- mapping between DATAMITE and Pontus-X,
- implementation of CRUD methods

Interaction with Pontus-X Network requires providing a wallet key, created (or configured) during Pontus-X Ecosystem onboarding. Intermediary service utilising Nautilus toolkit (<https://nautilus.delta-dao.com/docs/getting-started>) providing REST API has been created and is hosted on PSNC server.

The plugin is available as part of <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/datamite-project/data-sharing/brokers-eu-portals>

4.5.3. Training Materials

Having the pilot's objective in mind and to provide a support involvement of potential entities in data sharing within Polish Agricultural Data Space a course has been created and published on the Moodle platform. Sections at the beginning provide a short introduction to Data Spaces and Pontus-X in particular, including creating an asset through the Pontus-X portal.

Next sections provide an overview of the basics of DATAMITE and examples of how to ingest a dataset in the DATAMITE framework and create a data product from it. Finally, a data product is published on the Pontus-X network through the DATAMITE framework.

The Moodle course is available at: <https://moodle.datamite.psnc.pl/course/view.php?id=18>

Pontus-X and DATAMITE Publishing assets on Pontus-X DATAMITE overview DATAMITE Pontus-X integration Conclusion

This section covers topic of various roles in Pontus-X, creating and associating a wallet for participants, as well as publishing an asset on Pontus-X.

Pontus-X Ecosystem consists of various types of components:

1. **Spaces (data marketplaces)** - domain-specific, independently governed ecosystems within Pontus-X, focusing on data and services specific to particular types of businesses or stakeholders. Example of a specific data marketplace is *Polish Agriculture Data Space* <https://dataspaces.psnc.pl/>
2. **Operators** - validated and trusted members of the Pontus-X network, providing infrastructure and functionality of Data Space's observers, validating transactions.
3. **Providers** - they provide intermediary between the data source and the client that wants to access the data and services, verifying permissions.
4. **Participants** - entities that either publish or access data and services.

Entities participating in the Pontus-X network can perform various roles, depending on the context.

All operations on the Pontus-X are written in a distributed ledger. This includes operations such as creating new assets, specifying asset price (if any) and buying/accessing the asset. Participants are required to obtain their Pontus-X private key, and add it to a wallet. The key will be used to identify the participant when interacting with the network.

Pontus-X provides an easy to follow and fast-track onboarding process, available at <https://docs.pontus-x.eu/docs/getting->

Figure 97: Pontus-X and DATAMITE integration Moodle course

The course contents and structure were also a basis of in person course and workshop on usage of DATAMITE for data spaces integration in a Polish roadmap project KMD4EOSC (<https://kmd4eosc.pl/>).

4.5.4. Test Campaign

The test campaign focused on validation of the DATAMITE framework release, integration with Pontus-X marketplace and validating defined test scenarios.

For the 2nd iteration, the same server has been reused as in the 1st (Virtual Machine running Ubuntu Server 22.04 LTS Cloud Image, 8 VCPUs, 32GB RAM). Previous installation of the framework has been updated to the new model and deployment/starting structure that has been released. The new approach made configuration and starting of the whole framework much easier for the framework deployer.

During the initial testing, an issue arose with SSL configuration. After thorough testing and debugging with the DATAMITE developer infrastructure team the problems were solved by providing additional sub-domains for our infrastructure, with separate nginx configuration for Keycloak authorisation component and MinIO storage component.

The changes to the plugin template in Data Sharing Module required the change of approach for Pontus-X implementation. The initial idea was implemented by integrating Nautilus library and execution runtime with the plugin component. This required many additional dependencies, due to Nautilus being only available in TypeScript language, and the plugins template being offered as Python software. After discussions decision has been made to separate the implementation into two:

- **Plugin implementation** – which covers the Pontus-X asset schema, mapping and preparation of the required information for the interaction, written in Python and integrated with DATAMITE,
- **Nautilus bridge API** – executes the Pontus-X network communication using Nautilus library, written in TypeScript and deployed separately.

After the new approach has been implemented, it has been deployed and tested both in the pilot as well as in generic DATAMITE instances.

Validation of the remaining Pilot 5 could then commence. The pilot’s datasets have been ingested, as well as data products were created. User defined rules have been created and tested for the datasets and publication to Pontus-X marketplace were successful.

Figure 98: Temperature rule for the weather dataset.

4.5.5. Performance and usability of the DATAMITE framework

KPI	Description	Baseline	Current	Target	Achieved
KPI1	Datasets under Governance, Quality or Security tools	0	6	3	Yes
KPI2	Number of applications using shared datasets	0	3	3	Yes eDWIN, AGREGO, Polish Agricultura I Data Space
KPI3	Potential users of services/apps/products based on shared datasets	0	22000+	5000	Currently eDWIN has 22450 unique farmers registered

Table 23. Pilot 5 KPIs

IKPI	Description	Baseline	Current	Target	Achieved
I1	Number of the dataset being transformed to agreed data models (e.g. AIM)	0	6	6	Yes
I2	Number of the datasets shared via the connectors/providers connected	0	6	6	Yes
I3	Frontend (marketplace) in place	0	1	1	Yes
I4	Dataspace in place	0	1	1	Yes
I5	Number of identified datasets	6	12	12	Yes
I6	Proposed data models in place	0	1	1	Yes

Table 24. Pilot 5 internal KPIs

4.6. Pilot 6 - Connecting MISTRAL to the EU AIoD Platform

4.6.1. Test Scenarios

In brief, the pilot involves the following test scenarios: While both scenarios were tested during iteration 2, some experiments continued during the subsequent iterations. The pilots' scenarios are elucidated below to provide context for the text campaign.

1. Testing dissemination of MISTRAL data products on EU portals.

This validation scenario relates to the publication of MISTRAL data products on European portals. This is an important step in ensuring that the data is disseminated effectively and can be available to a wider research community. To this end, UCC has developed and integrated two different broker components with the data sharing modules. One is for dissemination to the AIoD platform and the other to datagov.eu (CKAN).

The datasets used to create the data product related to MISTRAL data assets for disseminating on AIoD and Meteohub catalogues using the respective brokers. The input datasets consist of data from three sources, including observations, forecast simulations and radar devices (Figure 99). The metadata for these assets is available in separate CSV files. The data product was created by filtering relevant columns (e.g. dataset ID, licence type, short description, type of data asset) and dropping less important columns using the data product composition module.

Figure 99: MISTRAL data assets based on observation, forecast, radar sources.

The publication menu of the framework comprised brokers for various data spaces across Europe. To disseminate MISTRAL data assets, the framework's built-in AIoD and CKAN brokers were utilised. Dissemination of the AIoD was tested on a local development version of the AIoD instance available on the ITI cloud infrastructure in Valencia. For CKAN, a local instance of the Meteohub data catalogue was used on CINECA's cloud infrastructure. In both cases, the publication procedure involved entering data descriptions, licence details, and access policy information into the readily available front-end form. Tokens were then generated by entering the appropriate user credentials for the respective portals and submitting the data assets. The outcome of the publication was tested immediately, as shown in Figure 100, which illustrates the MISTRAL data product that was disseminated using the CKAN broker.

MistralDemo Dissemination

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Dataset Groups Activity Stream

MistralDemo Dissemination

MeteoHub data

Data and Resources

Data_Disseminate.csv
Data_Disseminate.csv

Data_Disseminate_retain_col_1_20251219_152610.csv
Data_Disseminate_retain_col_1_20251219_152610.csv

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Additional Info

Field	Value
Source	https://minio-datamite-ds.iti.es/public/7b491521-048a-4c7d-bbe7-c64bac980387/7b491521-048a-4c7d-bbe7-c64bac980387_ckan_version_1.zip
Author	Bala Chandramouli
Version	1
Last Updated	December 19, 2025, 4:29 PM (UTC+01:00)
Created	December 19, 2025, 4:29 PM (UTC+01:00)

Figure 100: MISTRAL data product dissemination through CKAN connector

2. Quality assessment to identify erroneous sensor data.

This scenario involves testing the quality evaluator and the user-defined rule generator in order to estimate quality KPIs and evaluate the usability of the sensor data. The primary objectives are to assess the accuracy of data files containing surface temperature sensor measurements and to evaluate the effectiveness of applying ad hoc rules to identify data consistency issues. The presence of anomalous values in the measurements was tested using sample data files.

The sensor observation data can sometimes register anomalous values, such as the arbitrary code -9999, which indicates a lack of data at that specific time. Such entries can occur regardless of the parameter being measured (temperature, rainfall, etc.). One simple way to identify these entries is to define a quality rule that checks the minimum value, as illustrated in Figure 101 using a sample of temperature sensor data.

Include rule as part of the profiling process. ● Enabled

1st Operand

Measurement / numeric.minimum

Operator

= Equal to

2nd Operand

"0.0"^^xsd:double

Figure 101: The quality rule is to find an anomaly in the sensor registrations.

Consequently, the rule is applied immediately to all artefact data uploaded to the framework and the quality score is highlighted. Figure 102 shows sample data with a quality score of 100, suggesting that the data does not contain any missing sensor entries and is therefore complete.

Quality Rule Score	Name	Dimension	Description	Created at	Enabled
100 (100)	Check Absence Of Erraneous Registry	Consistency, Validity	Check if there is no value which is outside the normale range	Mar 15 2026, 22:54:27	Yes

Figure 102: Validation of quality score for sensor data

4.6.2. Solution implementation

This framework deployment solution implements a robust, high-performance private cloud environment by leveraging OpenStack. With a resource pool of 24 vCPUs and 180 GB of RAM, the architecture is optimised for memory-intensive and computationally demanding workloads. Since the framework containerise various components, superior operational agility is achieved, enabling rapid deployment and seamless updates.

The framework deployment was executed using Docker Engine v29.1.5 to take advantage of its modern architecture and enhanced API capabilities. Docker Swarm was utilised as the primary orchestration engine to manage the framework's services. The deployment process was streamlined using the Docker stack command, which automated the provisioning of multi-container services in a single coordinated operation.

4.6.3. Training Materials

As part of the training activities, a webinar was organised to explain the application scenarios for engaging the DATAMITE framework in the pilot. The webinar included a brief introduction to MISTRAL (currently MeteoHub) services and explained the context and benefits of using DATAMITE to address some of the pilot's challenges. It also included screenshots of the steps involved in testing the planned pilot scenarios. Additional reference resources were also provided, including links to video sessions showcasing the use of the DATAMITE framework for disseminating pilot data catalogues to external portals, and the importance of quality estimation for pilot datasets. These resources were designed to enable attendees to review the content and apply the techniques discussed during the session. The materials were designed to be concise, accessible, and useful for learning during the webinar and for future reference.

4.6.4. Test Campaign

The current test campaign focuses on three main aspects. The first one is purely related to deployment, while the others involve more refined testing of the above-elucidated test scenarios. During the last iteration phase, several problems relating to the deployment of the KPI library service with Docker arose. The main issue was the inability to download the KPI library within the container due to an MTU issue, whereby the largest packet size (in bytes) that a network interface

can transmit without fragmenting it is exceeded. Docker defaults to an MTU of 1500 bytes, which matches the standard for Ethernet, but often conflicts with the smaller limits used by underlying networks. The issue was resolved by troubleshooting the network and container configurations while deploying the framework on a local on-premise cloud.

For test scenario 1, the current iteration focused on disseminating data products on a test instance of CKAN, since it has recently been updated and improved significantly over the last six months. The focus of this iteration was testing the broker functionality on the updated CKAN instance.

For test scenario 2, we conducted a rigorous quality assessment of the sets of data received from the temperature and pressure sensors. This evaluation included a suite of sophisticated, user-defined validation rules, extending beyond standard baseline checks. These custom parameters were specifically designed to identify erroneous sensor readings and anomalies in edge cases that standard quality tests often overlook. This ensures high data integrity for downstream analytics.

4.6.5. Performance and usability of the DATAMITE framework

KPI	Description	Baseline	Target	Achieved
KPI1	Data Tools, e.g., Governance, Quality, Sharing	None defined	>3 DATAMITE modules	Yes
KPI2	Datasets under Governance, Quality or Security tools	0	>90% data involved in the Pilot	Yes (on datasets used for testing/validation)
KPI3	Datasets under Security, Sovereignty, privacy components	0	>80% data involved in the Pilot	Yes (on datasets used for testing/validation)
KPI4	Number of national and international active users	~700	Increase 10%	Yes, exact number is not yet verified
KPI5	Number of catalogues exposing MISTRAL datasets	3	4	Yes
KPI6	Dataset exposing data quality attribute	0	>= 90% of datasets involved in the Pilot	Partial (Only test-bed datasets were evaluated for Quality)

Table 25. Pilot 6 tentative KPIs

IKPI	Description	Baseline	Target	Achieved
I1	Data dissemination to external portals	1	2	Yes
I2	Number of components from DATAMITE be used	0	5	Yes

13	Number of developed connectors compatible with internal system to be deployed	0	2	Yes
14	Licence Agreement chosen or formulated	0	≥ 1	Yes
15	Usage Access Policy chosen or formulated	0	≥ 1	Yes
17	Business plan chosen or defined	0	1	Yes
18	Statistics of dataset usages	0	$\geq 90\%$ of datasets involved in the Pilot	Not verified yet due to integration delays.
19	Number of datasets	37	40	Yes

Table 26. Pilot 6 internal KPIs

5. Conclusions

This report has presented the progress of Work Package 5 tasks achieved at the final stage (M39) of the DATAMITE project.

The final release of the DATAMITE framework was delivered in two approaches: a Docker Swarm oriented stack for legacy on premise clusters and a native Kubernetes distribution for cloud native environments. This dual path strategy was deliberately chosen to lower the barrier to entry for institutions still dependent on Docker Swarm, yet it simultaneously equips forward looking laboratories with a Kubernetes ready solution that can scale across heterogeneous clouds. The framework follows well-defined procedures and an agreed-upon release plan, which eliminates ambiguities and enforces uniformity across iterations. By adhering to this structured methodology, the team has resolved integration inconsistencies. The primary success is a solid foundation that supports cohesive, efficient integration and enables ongoing deployment and evolution without sacrificing reliability or consistency.

During months 27–39, a comprehensive training programme has been delivered, designed to enable both technical and non-technical stakeholders to adopt the DATAMITE Framework across heterogeneous European data-space environments. It combined hands-on workshops, short video “pills”, wiki documentation, and interactive webinars, each targeting a specific user group. Overall, the blended-learning approach—mixing asynchronous media, interactive Q&A, and concrete demo environments—proved effective in equipping academics and industry practitioners with the skills needed to operationalise DATAMITE within European data-space initiatives.

All pilot projects that participated in the DATAMITE evaluation phase concluded their initiatives by fully integrating the DATAMITE framework into their data processing pipelines and conducting validation campaigns. Although each pilot pursued the same overarching goals, their implementation tactics had been tailored to address distinct use cases. The activities each Pilot performed are described below.

In the context of Pilot 1, the project is representing a substantial step forward in the capacity for data exchange in secure and productive environments. It allows Gimeno Group to move toward stages closer to data monetisation. Although this perspective is still at a very early stage, it is already enabling Gimeno Group to lay the first foundations in this area. Today, the data exchange infrastructure has become part of the corporate data infrastructure thanks to the capability demonstrated by DATAMITE to integrate into complex, large-scale systems. This first contact within the environment of complex data spaces will serve as a valuable stimulus for the group’s companies to begin exploiting the potential of this innovative technology.

Pilot 2, during the second iteration, continued testing and validating the DATAMITE framework in different business scenarios, providing feedback to the technical partners. The framework has been used to create sophisticated data products as well as additional services on top of them, thus catering different needs of various OTE’s business units. As the data quality modules, and particularly the UDRG, were also incorporated into the pilot’s deployment, complex business quality rules were defined based on the available datasets and use cases. Concerning the

dissemination of the DATAMITE results, the pilot's architecture and execution results have been published in scientific conferences proceedings²⁸ and books²⁹.

Pilot 3 collaborated closely with technical partners throughout component development, performing extensive platform testing, reporting technical issues, and providing structured feedback. By the end of the project, all platform modules have been successfully deployed by HEDNO, all designed test scenarios were executed meeting the corresponding KPIs, and comprehensive demonstration and training material was produced. Furthermore, based on the exchanged data, three AI tools supporting power grid planning and operation were developed by CERTH and evaluated.

Unfortunately, despite the additional efforts made by the technical partners to enable seamless integration with Data Cellar, its current implementation did not fully meet the pilot's requirements in terms of usage and access policies. In addition, its absence of a global catalogue limits the discoverability of published datasets.

Pilot 4 aimed to leverage E-REDES' open data assets and assess how the DATAMITE Framework could support the preparation, governance, quality assessment and publication of distribution-related data products, including their future exposure through energy data spaces. Within this scope, the pilot successfully validated the ingestion of twelve artifacts and six datasets generated by existing BI4D processes, the configuration of semantic governance (domains, glossaries and terms), the implementation of user-defined quality rules, and the creation of six complete data products. It also demonstrated an end-to-end publication workflow by sharing both data and metadata to the E-REDES Open Data Portal via the broker and harvester setup and configured a CEEDS-aligned publication in the EDC connector with the corresponding access policies. However, the pilot could not complete an actual exchange with CEEDS (Data Cellar), nor perform user-level hands-on evaluation, due to the lack of an operational data space instance and the framework's maturity level during the reporting period. Regarding the technical deployment, the second iteration had to be executed on an ITI-hosted virtual machine because an internal Linux environment with sufficient capacity was not made available in time. However, based on the experience gained, E-REDES considers that the validated solution could be replicated in an internal sandbox with the required infrastructure provisioned, the necessary internal architecture and security validations, and the implemented assets are ready to be connected to CEEDS once the external ecosystem reaches full operational maturity.

Pilot 5's overarching goal was to prepare, promote and populate Polish Agriculture Data Space with high quality and enhanced agrifood data coming from two systems participating in the pilot - eDWIN farm management system and AGREGO farm management system - by utilising DATAMITE framework and components. After deploying both DATAMITE infrastructure on pilot's premises as well as integration and on-boarding on Pontus-X marketplace, the validation scenarios and the test campaign could be successfully conducted.

²⁸ https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-97317-8_21

²⁹ <https://www.intechopen.com/online-first/1233458>

The aim of Pilot 6 was twofold: first, to employ the DATAMITE framework to disseminate the MISTRAL platform's data assets on external portals; and second, to employ the quality evaluator module to identify anomalies in sensor measurement data through user-defined features built into the module. The concluding round of validations was successfully completed by testing the framework for the aforementioned objectives with additional data assets and operations and sensor outputs that had previously not been considered, thus successfully concluding the test campaigns.

All pilot projects successfully integrated the DATAMITE framework into their data pipelines and completed validation campaigns. This demonstrated DATAMITE's ability to support data governance, quality management, and data product creation. Despite different use cases, the framework proved flexible and adaptable across diverse scientific and business scenarios being a robust and scalable framework capable of integration into complex environments. It effectively supports data quality, governance, and sharing, including preparation for future data spaces. Some limitations remain, particularly regarding ecosystem maturity and real-world data exchange infrastructure.

Overall, the pilots confirm strong potential for future adoption, expansion, and commercialisation of the framework.

6. References

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Appendix A – Pilot 3

Evaluations

Figure 103: Evaluation of the course: Introduction to Data Spaces for Data Providers.

Figure 104: Evaluation of the course: Introduction to Data Spaces for Data Consumers.

User-defined quality rules

Description	Dataset	Rule	Dimension	Clauses	Score (%)
Ensures that SCADA recordings occur within two minutes of the measurement source timestamp.	SCADA Power measurements	Timely recording of measurements	Accuracy	$SCADA_Time \leq Source_Time + 2$ AND $SCADA_Time \geq Source_Time - 2$	99.17
	SCADA Load measurements	Timely recording of measurements	Accuracy	$SCADA_Time \leq Source_Time + 2$ AND $SCADA_Time \geq Source_Time - 2$	100
	SCADA Voltage measurements	Timely recording of measurements	Accuracy	$SCADA_Time \leq Source_Time + 2$ AND $SCADA_Time \geq Source_Time - 2$	100
Verifies that key descriptive columns are populated.	SCADA Power measurements	Completeness	Completeness	Unit not empty AND Description not empty AND Label not empty	100
	SCADA Load measurements	Completeness	Completeness	Unit not empty AND Description not empty AND Label not empty	100
	SCADA Voltage measurements	Completeness	Completeness	Unit not empty AND Description not empty AND	100

				Label not empty	
Ensures that selected columns contain only predefined acceptable values	SCADA Power measurements	Unit Validity	Validity	Power_Type∈{P,Q} AND Unit∈{MW,MVAr}	100
	SCADA Load measurements	Unit Validity	Validity	Unit = A	100
	SCADA Voltage measurements	Unit Validity	Validity	Unit = V	100
Ensures that active power measurements are expressed in MW and reactive power are in MVAr	SCADA Power measurements	Power Type-Unit Match	Validity	(Power_Type = P AND Unit = MW) OR (Power_Type = Q AND Unit = MVAr)	100
Ensures that the Data Class contains accepted values	Telemetry Center metering data	Data Class Validity	Validity	Data_Class∈ {active+, active-, reactive+, Q1}	100%

Table 27. The quality rules used, with their clauses and scores.

Access & usages policies

Policy ID	Policy ODRL
Policy_1	<pre>{ "@context": { "@vocab": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/" }, "@id": "policy_1", "policy": { "@context": "http://www.w3.org/ns/odrl.jsonld", "@type": "Set", "permission": [{ "action": "use", "constraint": [{ "@type": "AtomicConstraint",</pre>

	<pre> "leftOperand": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/timeInterval", "rightOperand": { "@type": "xsd:date", "@value": "2026-03-01T00:00:00+02:00" }, "operator": { "@id": "odrl:gteq" } }, { "@type": "AtomicConstraint", "leftOperand": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/timeInterval", "rightOperand": { "@type": "xsd:date", "@value": "2026-03-31T23:59:59+02:00" }, "operator": { "@id": "odrl:lteq" } }] }], "prohibition": [], "obligation": [] } } } </pre>
<p>policy_2</p>	<pre> { "@context": { "@vocab": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/" }, "@id": "policy_2", "policy": { "@context": "http://www.w3.org/ns/odrl.jsonld", "@type": "Set", "permission": [{ "action": "use", "constraint": [{ "@type": "AtomicConstraint", "leftOperand": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/timeInterval", "rightOperand": { "@type": "xsd:date", "@value": "2026-03-01T00:00:00+02:00" }, "operator": { "@id": "odrl:gteq" } }, { "@type": "AtomicConstraint", "leftOperand": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/timeInterval", "rightOperand": { "@type": "xsd:date", "@value": "2026-03-31T23:59:59+02:00" }, "operator": { "@id": "odrl:lteq" } }] }], "action": "use", "constraint": [{ "@type": "AtomicConstraint", "odrl:leftOperand": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/location", "rightOperand": { </pre>

	<pre> "@type": "xsd:string", "@value": "eu" }, "operator": { "@id": "odrl:eq" } }] }], "prohibition": [], "obligation": [] } } </pre>
<p>policy_3</p>	<pre> { "@context": { "@vocab": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/" }, "@id": "policy_3", "policy": { "@context": "http://www.w3.org/ns/odrl.jsonld", "@type": "Set", "permission": [{ "action": "use", "constraint": [{ "@type": "AtomicConstraint", "leftOperand": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/timeInterval", "rightOperand": { "@type": "xsd:date", "@value": "2026-03-01T00:00:00+02:00" }, "operator": { "@id": "odrl:gteq" } }, { "@type": "AtomicConstraint", "leftOperand": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/timeInterval", "rightOperand": { "@type": "xsd:date", "@value": "2026-03-31T23:59:59+02:00" }, "operator": { "@id": "odrl:lteq" } }] }, { "action": "use", "constraint": [{ "@type": "AtomicConstraint", "odrl:leftOperand": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/location", "rightOperand": { "@type": "xsd:string", "@value": "eu" }, "operator": { "@id": "odrl:eq" } }] }, { "action": "use", "constraint": { "@type": "AtomicConstraint", </pre>

	<pre> "odrl:leftOperand": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/purpose", "rightOperand": { "@type": "xsd:string", "@value": "research" }, "operator": { "@id": "odrl:eq" } } }, "prohibition": [{ "action": "use", "constraint": { "@type": "AtomicConstraint", "odrl:leftOperand": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/purpose", "rightOperand": { "@type": "xsd:string", "@value": "commercial" }, "operator": { "@id": "odrl:eq" } } }], "obligation": [] } </pre>
--	--

Table 28. Defined policies in ODRL format.

Data Cellar on-boarding prerequisites

A participant, either a data provider or a data consumer, needs to deploy the participant-template deployment framework provided by the project, have public domain accessible and allowed service ports for the connector, and issue an API Key which is required for communication with the Data Cellar Issuer. HEDNO used the domain provider.hedno.datamite-horizon.eu for the participant endpoint.

The purpose of the onboarding process is to establish a trusted identity for the participant, deploy the required data space infrastructure, and obtain the necessary Verifiable Credentials (VCs) required to interact with the ecosystem. Using the retrieved API Key, the onboarding of HEDNO to the Data Cellar Data Space was performed mostly automated using the participant-template framework, for both the identity and the connector configuration steps. The participant was registered with the identifier provider and deployed under the domain provider.hedno.datamite-horizon.eu, which acts as the DID web domain and public endpoint of the participant's services. The repository provides scripts and services that automate the provisioning of the participant wallet, credentials manager, and connector components needed to join the data space. Figure 105 illustrates the whole process of the onboarding procedure.

Figure 105: Full onboarding procedure to Data Cellar.

The process begins with the deployment of the participant infrastructure using the template scripts. During this step, the necessary containers are started, including the wallet service, credentials manager, and Data Cellar's EDC-based connector. As the process continues, it requires participant attributes such as the legal name (HEDNO), the VAT identifier, and the geographic subdivision (GR-I). The participant domain provider.hedno.datamite-horizon.eu is used to generate the participant DID, which in this case takes the form `did:web:provider.hedno.datamite-horizon.eu`.

This DID represents the decentralised identity of the participant in the data space and is used when issuing and verifying credentials. During initialisation, the deployment scripts also generate the required X.509 certificates and key pairs that are used for secure communication with the data space services and for signing credentials.

Data Cellar catalogue

```

{
  "@id": "07f3b4a2-6e6a-457a-bd7b-d57dc66b2b92",
  "@type": "dcat:Catalog",
  "dSPACE:participantId": "provider",
  "dcat:dataset": [
    {
      "@id": "4eb4bd47-87be-4620-949b-64cda0e301c5",
      "@type": "dcat:Dataset",
    }
  ]
}
  
```

```

"odrl:hasPolicy": {
  "@id": " ZWQ5N2Q4NzAtMDNhZi00ZWY1LTkzMDEtNzg2NjIxMjVjMjk2.....",
  "@type": "odrl:Offer",
  "odrl:permission": [],
  "odrl:prohibition": [],
  "odrl:obligation": []
},
"dcats:distribution": [],
"name": "MS-Location1_2022_Powers.csv",
"id": "4eb4bd47-87be-4620-949b-64cda0e301c5",
"contenttype": "text/csv"
},
{
  "@id": "a11b2494-fd18-45fc-803b-71196090f3fe",
  "@type": "dcat:Dataset",
  "odrl:hasPolicy": {
    "@id": "ZWQ5N2Q4NzAtMDNhZi00ZWY1LTkzMDEtNzg2NjIxMjVjMjk2...",
    "@type": "odrl:Offer",
    "odrl:permission": [],
    "odrl:prohibition": [],
    "odrl:obligation": []
  },
  "dcats:distribution": [],
  "name": "MS-Location1_2022_Voltages.csv",
  "id": "a11b2494-fd18-45fc-803b-71196090f3fe",
  "contenttype": "text/csv"
},
{
  "@id": "ae70121e-662b-4d64-b669-4e40d51b16e9",
  "@type": "dcat:Dataset",
  "odrl:hasPolicy": {
    "@id": "ZWQ5N2Q4NzAtMDNhZi00ZWY1LTkzMDEtNzg2NjIxMjVjMjk2.....",
    "@type": "odrl:Offer",
    "odrl:permission": [],
    "odrl:prohibition": [],
    "odrl:obligation": []
  },
  "dcats:distribution": [],
  "name": "MS-Location1_2022_AMI_del_col_1_20260313_154504_anonymization.csv",
  "id": "ae70121e-662b-4d64-b669-4e40d51b16e9",
  "contenttype": "text/csv"
}

```

```

    },
    {
      "@id": "9b624e89-64f3-45e3-8c72-d0d7a9ecd0c7",
      "@type": "dcat:Dataset",
      "odrl:hasPolicy": {
        "@id": "ZWQ5N2Q4NzAtMDNhZi00ZWY1LTkzMDEtNzg2NjIxMjVjMjk2...",
        "@type": "odrl:Offer",
        "odrl:permission": [],
        "odrl:prohibition": [],
        "odrl:obligation": []
      },
      "dcat:distribution": [],
      "name": "MS-Location1_2022_Loads.csv",
      "id": "9b624e89-64f3-45e3-8c72-d0d7a9ecd0c7",
      "contenttype": "text/csv"
    },
    {
      "@id": "06ec979a-a4cf-4b67-afac-ee98494709df",
      "@type": "dcat:Dataset",
      "odrl:hasPolicy": {
        "@id": "ZWQ5N2Q4NzAtMDNhZi00ZWY1LTkzMDEtNzg2NjIxMjVjMjk2....",
        "@type": "odrl:Offer",
        "odrl:permission": [],
        "odrl:prohibition": [],
        "odrl:obligation": []
      },
      "dcat:distribution": [],
      "name": "MV_lines_1.pfd",
      "id": "06ec979a-a4cf-4b67-afac-ee98494709df",
      "contenttype": "application/octet-stream"
    }
  ],
  "dcat:service": {
    "@id": "c2beaf9f-4c8d-4932-8c38-61a0855367b8",
    "@type": "dcat:DataService",
    "dcat:endpointDescription": "dspace:connector",
    "dcat:endpointUrl": "https://provider.hedno.datamite-horizon.eu/protocol",
    "dct:terms": "dspace:connector",
    "dct:endpointUrl": "https://provider.hedno.datamite-horizon.eu/protocol"
  },
  "participantId": "provider",

```

```

"@context": {
  "@vocab": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/",
  "edc": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/",
  "dcat": "http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#",
  "dct": "http://purl.org/dc/terms/",
  "odrl": "http://www.w3.org/ns/odrl/2/",
  "dspace": "https://w3id.org/dspace/v0.8/"
}
}

```

Table 29. Federated catalogue metadata, show all the available datasets

Data Cellar and DATAMITE EDC consumption setup

Data Cellar is an energy data space compliant with IDSA/Gaia-X specifications. As described in *Test Scenario 6*, an initial onboarding process is required, during which a participant issues a Decentralised Identifier (DID) and Verifiable Credentials based on an existing certificate, ensuring their identity. Any participant that intends to access data catalogues, request data consumption, or provide data must complete this onboarding process. The involved entities for a Data Cellar data exchange are the following:

- **Centralised Identity Provider (IdP):** Deployed by ITI within its infrastructure, based on Keycloak, for the purposes of the pilot. It is responsible for issuing JWT access tokens to participants.
- **Provider:** HEDNO has deployed an EDC connector within its infrastructure as part of the DATAMITE framework. This connector is configured to use the IdP service provided by ITI.
- **Consumer:** ITI has deployed an EDC connector configured for data consumption. In addition, a proprietary front-end has been developed to facilitate interaction with provider participants using the same IdP service. This front-end supports catalogue querying, contract negotiation, transfer processing, and Endpoint Data Reference (EDR) retrieval. CERTH accesses this connector remotely through the front-end, using appropriate access control mechanisms.

In contrast, the DATAMITE EDC connector does not rely on the Gaia-X Trust Framework. Authentication and authorisation of participants are handled through an Identity Provider (IdP) based on Keycloak/OAuth2. Participant connectors use Keycloak clients and provide claims corresponding to their identity attributes. The involved entities for a DATAMITE EDC data exchange are the following:

- **Decentralised identity services:** Identity and trust are established through Decentralised Identifiers (DIDs) and Verifiable Credentials, based on IDSA/Gaia-X.
- **Provider:** HEDNO has deployed the Data Cellar connector within its infrastructure using the [participant-template](#), following the process described in section 4.3.1.5.

- **Consumer:** CERTH has deployed the Data Cellar connector within its infrastructure using the [participant-template](#), following the process described in section 4.3.1.5, as well as a Swagger-based API service, developed by consortium partner Tecnalía, that provides a simple interface for automating catalogue fetching and data consumption.

At its current stage, Data Cellar does not support a global catalogue service. The consumer must know in advance the endpoint address of the provider (HEDNO) in order to retrieve the catalogue of available datasets. In this case, the endpoint used by HEDNO is: <https://provider.hedno.datamite-horizon.eu/protocol>.

Energy Services Provided by CERTH

Optimal sizing methodology

CERTH's Energy Planning Tool is an optimisation-based decision-support tool developed to facilitate the coordinated integration of electric vehicle charging infrastructure (EVCI) and distributed photovoltaic (PV) generation into a given distribution electric grid. In the context of this deliverable, the tool is applied under a unidirectional charging paradigm (V1G), focusing on the optimal planning of EV chargers, while simultaneously performing optimal siting and sizing of PV systems.

The tool identifies both the optimal locations and the optimal nominal apparent and active power ratings of EV charging stations and PV units by jointly considering technical, operational, and mobility-related constraints of the distribution network. In order to determine the optimal deployment, the following key factors are taken into account:

- Energy requirements of the system, including load profiles, charging demand, and battery efficiencies.
- Grid saturation levels and available hosting capacity.
- Impact of the new assets on grid voltages, frequency, stability, and overall network power losses.
- Forecasted penetration and spatial distribution of electric vehicles, derived from a transport and mobility model.

Based on these inputs, the tool formulates and solves a cost-minimising optimal power flow problem, which determines the optimal siting and sizing of EV chargers and PV installations by minimising total grid power losses and network congestion after their integration. Through this unified optimisation framework, the Energy Planning Tool supports efficient and technically feasible planning of both charging infrastructure and distributed generation, ensuring improved utilisation of the existing distribution grid.

Modelling

To achieve the goal of the description, the Energy Planning Tool contains an optimisation algorithm whereby the grid's power flow is executed. By this process, the algorithm takes into account the following grid's specifications:

- Loads position and consumption
- Already installed DER position and energy production
- Number of grid's lines and buses
- Total line power losses
- Magnitude and angle of voltage on every bus
- Current magnitude on every line

Using the previous specifications, the algorithm chooses the optimal size and position of EV charger stations and PVs, minimises the total line power losses and contributes to the normal operation of grid.

Objective Function

The objective function includes the variables to be optimised, specifically total grid power losses and total grid congestion. As a result, the objective function is a vector function, represented by the following equation:

$$\vec{F} = \left(\sum_l^N g_l |V_i^2 + V_j^2| - 2g_l |V_i| |V_j| \cos(\theta_i - \theta_j), S_{oper} \right)$$

Where:

- The first component is the total line power losses (kW)
- The second component is the operational apparent power (kVA) of the grid's transformer, which represents the total grid congestion
- **N** are the total lines of the grid
- g_l is the conductance of every line
- i, j are the buses, which are connected via l line
- V_i, V_j are the voltage magnitudes on i, j buses respectively
- θ_i, θ_j are the voltage angles on i, j buses respectively

Constraints

The constraints are the process whereby the algorithm ensures the grid's normal operation and the finding of at least position for a charge station in the grid. This process is shown as following:

1. $(p_0 S_{Nmin}^0, p_1 S_{Nmin}^1, \dots, p_k S_{Nmin}^k) \leq (S_N^0, S_N^1, \dots, S_N^k) \leq (p_0 S_{Nmax}^0, p_1 S_{Nmax}^1, \dots, p_k S_{Nmax}^k)$, This inequality ensures that the values of nominal apparent power of EV charging stations and PVs do not fall under a minimum value and do not surpass a maximum value, predetermined by the pilot's administrator.
2. $\sum_i^k (p_0 S_{Nmin}^0, p_1 S_{Nmin}^1, \dots, p_k S_{Nmin}^k) > 1MVA$, This inequality ensures that the total installed nominal apparent power of Charge Stations is at least 1 MVA.
3. $(V_{0min}, V_{1min}, \dots, V_{kmin}) \leq (V_0, V_1, \dots, V_k) \leq (V_{0max}, V_{1max}, \dots, V_{kmax})$, This inequality ensures that the magnitude values on every Grid's bus do not fall under a minimum value and do not surpass a maximum value, predetermined by pilot's administrator.
4. $(I_0, I_1, \dots, I_L) \leq (I_{0max}, I_{1max}, \dots, I_{Lmax})$, This inequality ensures that the Grid's lines do not overload.

Where:

- k is the number of total grid's buses.
- L is the number of total grid's lines.
- are the nominal currents of every grid's line

In addition, the algorithm finds the bus where the grid's substation and transformers are connected and ensures that no charge station is introduced there. Therefore, another constraint is the following:

5. *If i =substation i =transformer then $p_i=0$, Where p_i is the position binary on bus i .*

Optimisation Process Methodology

The operation of the Energy Planning Tool's optimisation algorithm follows a methodology, which is separated into two parts.

- The usage of Pymoo optimisation tool, for minimising total line power losses and ensuring the non – violation of the constraints.
- The usage of Pandapower power flow tool, to execute the pilot's distribution grid power flow.

Pymoo optimisation tool

Pymoo is a Python-based optimisation tool designed for advanced single and multi-objective optimisation tasks. It offers a range of features related to optimisation, including visualisation and decision-making support. Pymoo processes data from power flow simulations to determine the optimal placement and size of EV charging stations and PVs by optimising the objective function, while ensuring that constraints are not violated.

Additionally, Pymoo provides iterative feedback, allowing for repeated power flow simulations with the inclusion of EV charging stations and PVs. This process continues until the optimal objective function is achieved or the maximum number of iterations is reached.

Thus, the Energy Planning Tool's optimisation algorithm must ensure seamless communication between Pymoo and the power flow tool.

Pandapower Power Flow tool

Pandapower is a Python-based power flow tool that simulates the grid's power flow by using the EV charging station and PVs locations and sizes provided by Pymoo as input. Through power flow analysis, the following data are computed:

- Load locations and consumption
- Number of grid lines and buses
- Total power line losses
- Voltage magnitude and angle at each bus
- Current magnitude on each line

This data is then fed back to Pymoo to calculate updated locations and sizes for the EV charging stations and Pvs.

Results

The Energy Planning is implemented on a specific feeder of a Distribution Grid Area in Greece, based on the dataset provided by HEDNO. This feeder is a medium voltage (20 kV) distribution network.

As shown in Figure 106, 19 PV systems and 25 EV charging stations have been installed. The x-axis represents the bus ID where each is located, and y-axis represent the nominal power of each in kVA.

Figure 106: PV and Charging station position and nominal power

After the installation, the Energy Planning Tool calculated the optimal operation of the charging stations and PVs. The transformer loading, shown on the Y-axis as a percentage, and consequently the grid congestion, is reduced during the day due to PV generation, as illustrated in Figure 107. In the original state (black), the transformer loading follows the typical daily demand

pattern of the area it serves. With the implementation of smart charging (V1G, yellow), the transformer load is better managed, taking advantage of PV production to reduce peak loading and mitigate congestion, thereby relieving strain on the substation.

Figure 107: Transformer loading: before vs after comparison

AI Load & DER Generation Forecasting

The study focuses on a local medium-voltage distribution network in Greece, utilising data of 2022 provided by HEDNO. The dataset provides a detailed view of the local network through line current measurements and load profiles of 12 client transformers. These records account for both active and reactive power demand, as well as a DER. Data preparation included resampling the original 15-minute intervals into an hourly frequency and employing interpolation to correct any gaps. A key feature of the methodology involved structuring the inputs so that the forecast for every client incorporated the historical load data from all other clients on the same semi-bar. This was designed to investigate how mutual dependencies affect individual node performance within the local grid.

Energy consumption is heavily influenced by environmental and temporal factors. For this purpose, the baseline dataset was enriched with weather and time features. Meteorological variables were extracted using the meteostat Python library from a weather station situated near the target area. This added critical data, such as temperature, dew point, relative humidity, precipitation, wind speed and direction, and atmospheric pressure. These variables capture a diverse set of weather insights which could be crucial in analysing transmission line patterns and produce more accurate and robust forecasting models. In order to capture the natural seasonality of human activity and weather throughout the day, features representing the time of day and day

of the week were also integrated. Furthermore, these variables were transformed using continuous sine and cosine functions to preserve their cyclical nature and eliminate boundaries like the transition from midnight to the next day.

Local socioeconomic profiles may also affect grid behaviour. Public holidays, for example, drastically alter the energy landscape. To account for this, the Python holidays package was used to generate a Boolean feature flagging major Greek holidays. Additionally, a visual analysis of the load data (Figure 108) revealed three distinct distribution clusters characterised by frequent demand spikes. Since these spikes may be genuine reflections of local economic activity, k-means clustering was applied. This allowed to assign a daily categorical label to the data, helping the model identify which behavioural group a given day belongs to.

Figure 108: Example load visualisation

The final datasets were tailored to the specific tasks of the study. For client load prediction, the dataset had 49 variables, merging the anonymised loads of twelve clients with the weather, time, holiday, and cluster features. The DER generation forecast utilised this same dataset but operates under a specialised model configuration. The dataset for AI state estimation additionally incorporated Voltage Magnitudes and Phase Angles from the buses that the above clients connect to. On the contrary, the dataset for forecasting the semi-bar current excludes individual client loads entirely to observe how predictive dynamics change at a broader grid scale.

Before training, all datasets were chronologically split into training and testing, while Min-Max scalars were fitted exclusively to the training data and subsequently applied to normalise the test set to avoid information leakage. The time-series data was then structured into continuous sequences using a 48-hour historical lookback window.

Variable Selection

In predictive modelling, the inclusion of all the available variables can impact overall forecasting performance in a negative way. Redundant or indirectly correlated features often introduce noise and computational complexity without contributing genuine predictive value. To isolate features containing authentic information, this methodology incorporates variable selection testing based on Granger principles. Granger causality in energy consumption forecasting is widely explored by researchers (Sharma, Dwivedi, & Metri, 2022). The fundamental approach evaluates whether the addition of a specific variable X improves the predictive accuracy of a target variable Y.

Since variables in real datasets are rarely independent evaluating them in isolation may give misleading results. To account for the overlapping relationships among weather and grid data, a Leave-One-Out Conditional Importance method is used. This technique measures the isolated impact of a single variable while keeping all other variables present in the model.

The traditional Granger testing is designed for linear auto-regressive models and requires modification for application to complex non-linear architectures such as Long Short-Term Memory networks. To evaluate the predictive contribution within these non-linear models (Rosol, Mlyńczak, & Cybulski, 2022) the non-parametric Wilcoxon test is utilised. The forecasting errors of a model including variable X are compared against a restricted model which excludes X, to determine if variable X provides sufficient unique information to forecast the target Y. This evaluation is executed on the testing dataset to prevent false conclusions, as neural networks tend to overfit and memorise noise during training. Assessing variable importance on unseen data confirms the true generalisation capabilities of the model. Finally, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test is applied prior to analysis to verify stationarity, and appropriate differencing is performed on any non-stationary data.

Three model configurations were established for each forecasting task. The single model relies exclusively on the historical data of the target variable. The full model incorporates the entire dataset. Finally, the restricted model utilises only the specific subset of variables validated by the selection process.

DER Forecasting

The dataset includes a specific client transformer that connects to a solar power plant, actively injecting electricity back into the distribution network. A dedicated Distributed Energy Resource forecasting module was developed specifically for this node.

The optimisation of day-ahead grid operations requires a solar forecasting module that generates 24 individual hourly predictions for the upcoming day. Statistical analysis of autocorrelation functions indicated that a 48-hour historical lookback window optimally captures the daily seasonality of solar power generation. The developed system utilises 24 independent predictive models, with each one exclusively dedicated to forecasting a single specific hour. This isolated modelling strategy is highly effective for short-term forecasting because it strictly prevents the accumulation and propagation of errors which is quite common in time-series forecasting.

The selected architecture is based on a dual-branch LSTM. The primary branch utilises a 32-unit LSTM layer to extract patterns from historical energy and weather time-series. The output from

this stage is concatenated with temporal features, including the hour of the day and the day of the week, before being processed by another 16-unit layer for further temporal refinement. Finally, a Dense layer controlled by the ReLU activation function computes the specific hourly forecast.

DER Forecasting Results

The final subset of selected features consisted of active_1, active_2, reactive_2, active_4, reactive_4, cluster_5, active_6, cluster_6, active_7, reactive_7, cluster_8, active_9, active_11, cluster_11, active_12, temperature, humidity, pressure, and day of week (sine transformed), where the numerical suffix appended to the load and cluster variables corresponds to the anonymised client ID. Out of the 49 original candidates, only 19 demonstrated genuine predictive value for the forecasting models. Table 30 provides a comparative analysis of the Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) across the three modelled configurations. The restricted model achieved the lowest overall error rates, validating the hypothesis that filtering out non-essential variables minimises noise and directly enhances predictive accuracy.

Metric	Single	Restricted	Full
MAE (kW)	10.83	10.49	12.33
RMSE (kW)	24.02	20.93	23.98

Table 30. DER forecasting metrics.

Load Forecasting

This use case requires forecasting of active and reactive loads for all client transformers that connect to a specific semi-bar. To achieve this, individual models are trained on historical data for each client's load. The load time-series contain mixed distributions, as seen in Figure 108. Initial tests showed that standard single-model architectures, both linear and LSTM-based, struggled to capture these fluctuations.

To address this, the forecast generation time was shifted to 09:00 AM. Incorporating morning measurements up to 08:00 AM provides baseline data that reduces the forecasting error caused by these daily spikes, while still allowing the provider sufficient time for grid planning. Furthermore, a Mixture of Experts approach was implemented to account for the varying data distributions. The training data was divided into three clusters based on predefined thresholds, and a separate expert model was trained on each group. During operation, the system evaluates the morning observations against these thresholds to assign the current day to a specific cluster. The corresponding expert model is then activated to generate the 24-hour prediction. Hyperparameter tuning determined the final model architecture which consists of two LSTM layers containing 128 and 64 units, followed by a dropout layer and a dense output layer of size 1.

Load Forecasting Results

Table 31 shows the MAE and MSE for the single, restricted, and full models across all client loads. The distribution of these results clearly indicates that there is no global, universally superior forecasting approach for the entire distribution network. The single models achieved the lowest

MAE for thirteen specific targets, the restricted models outperformed the others for seven, and the full models proved the best for four. This variance demonstrates a core principle of modern grid analytics. As the analytical focus narrows to individual local nodes, the predictive strategy must be specifically tailored to the unique characteristics of each load.

For most clients, relying strictly on their own historical data leads to lower errors. However, the superior accuracy of the restricted models in seven specific instances confirms that localised cross-load dependencies exist. Furthermore, the bar chart (Figure 109) showcases the ranking of features by selection frequency for active targets. The overall hierarchy of predictive importance shows that historical active variables dominate the selection process. In addition, meteorological features, like wind speed (wspd), relative humidity (rhum) and precipitation (prcp), consistently contribute to the forecasting models, while time-related features appear less frequently.

Client Load	Single MAE	Restr. MAE	Full MAE
active_1	5.5265	5.3456	5.43
active_2	4.7455	5.0155	5.08
active_3	3.385	2.9223	3.21
active_4	2.4899	2.5048	2.44
active_5	3.4579	3.8903	4.85
active_6	3.8691	4.2314	4.03
active_7	11.169	10.888	11.18
active_8	1.5821	1.663	1.66
active_9	2.6252	2.765	2.62
active_10	2.6849	3.1881	3.19
active_11	0.0411	0.0388	0.04
active_12	0.2859	0.3132	0.31
reactive_1	4.4451	4.7281	4.56
reactive_2	2.3968	2.3232	2.37
reactive_3	0.826	0.9629	0.88
reactive_4	2.4046	2.4593	2.55
reactive_5	1.0635	1.0975	0.98
reactive_6	1.0367	1.1397	1.13
reactive_7	6.0581	6.4028	6.7
reactive_8	2.0258	2.0145	2.28
reactive_9	4.96	5.3679	5.09
reactive_10	0.5964	0.5589	1
reactive_11	0.0499	0.0502	0.05
reactive_12	0.0621	0.0678	0.06

Table 31. Metrics comparison for each client and configuration.

Figure 109: Selection frequency of features.

State Estimation

For this task we have developed two approaches. The first one implements a state estimation approach that utilises a Deep Learning model to essentially filter voltage magnitude (Vm) and phase angles (Pa) of all the buses that the clients from the previous task connect to. By applying this technique on the same clients as the previous task, a homogenous solution is presented, providing the opportunity to further focus on the local aspect of the study and showcase the necessity to adjust generic solutions to the specific needs of individual localised grids. The second one approaches the overall goal of state estimation in a more abstract way by focusing on forecasting the aggregate current of the semi-bar.

Deep Learning State Estimation with degraded dataset

In the context of modern grid operations, maintaining accurate state estimation is frequently challenged by sensor noise and telemetry unavailability. To address these vulnerabilities, an Artificial Intelligence-based state estimation filter was developed utilising a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural network architecture. The primary objective of a model like this is to dynamically reconstruct the true operational state of the grid despite the presence of corrupt or missing data streams, which is a well-documented topic in literature [(Gotti, Amaris, & Ledesma Larrea, 2021), (Sun, 2025)].

The required data for this task are mainly voltage magnitude and phase angle measurements for each node of interest in the network per 15 minutes. These data were generated through simulations in the “Pandapower” library based on the PDF file that HEDNO provided. These extracted files contain vital information that describe the structure and operation of the network.

For the needs of this task, the first step was to isolate the client transformers that were studied in the forecasting modules. Then, the buses that they connect to were specified. This was an important step to identify the voltage magnitudes and phase angles of these individual buses. Furthermore, voltage and angle measurements were merged with client load data, as well as with the weather and holiday parameters that were described earlier. Thus, the final dataset consisted of voltage measurements, angle measurements, active and reactive loads, weather parameters and holidays information in 15-minute intervals.

A supervised learning approach was combined with synthesised conditions to train the LSTM network to effectively filter noise and deal with missing values (Che, 2018). The target dataset, representing the ground truth (Y), was derived entirely from clean grid measurements. On the contrary, the training feature set (X) was intentionally degraded to simulate real-world operational anomalies. This degradation process involved injecting Gaussian noise across all bus measurements to replicate standard sensor inaccuracies and transmission interference. Furthermore, to simulate total sensor failure and intermittent communication losses, measurements from one specific bus were entirely nullified, while random zero-value omissions were introduced into the data streams of several other designated "faulty" buses. A Boolean variable indicating the health of the bus was introduced, so as to instruct the model not to misinterpret these faulty measurements as valid data.

The temporal dynamics of the power distribution network were captured by structuring the input data into sequential time steps. Specifically, the LSTM was fed an input sequence of the intentionally corrupted measurements up to a specific time step t . The model was tasked with predicting the corresponding actual measurement for that exact time step t . By mapping these degraded input sequences to verified targets, the LSTM effectively functions as an advanced state estimation filter rather than a forecasting mechanism. It attempts to learn the underlying physical and temporal correlations necessary to autonomously bridge data gaps and correct readings based on the surrounding network context.

The empirical evaluation of this methodology showcased encouraging results, demonstrating the model's resilience in state reconstruction. Standard performance metrics, including MAE and MSE confirmed a high degree of predictive accuracy across the network. Most notably, a comparative analysis of the error margins revealed that the prediction errors for the fully operational buses and the intentionally corrupted "faulty" buses were remarkably similar, as seen in Figure 110 and Figure 111. In these figures, the mean errors of V_m and V_a are presented for each bus. Bus 'C' was the one that had all its measurements nullified. Surprisingly, the errors indicate that realistic outputs were produced. This similarity in error distributions indicates that the model successfully learned to infer the missing states of compromised nodes with the same reliability as nodes that provide valid data.

Figure 110: Vm Error comparison for healthy and faulty buses.

Figure 111: Va Error comparison for healthy and faulty buses.

Semi-bar Current Forecasting

This section approaches state estimation from a macro perspective. Providers should maintain transmission lines within specific operational thresholds to ensure the network remains safe and reliable. Current levels that exceed these limits pose a significant risk to the physical integrity of grid equipment. This implementation treats semi-bar current as a primary indicator of system health.

A Multi-Step LSTM architecture was chosen for this task. This specific model generates an entire 24-hour sequence simultaneously through a single network execution. The final configuration includes two LSTM layers with 64 and 32 units, a dropout layer and a 24-unit dense output layer. Data preparation and scaling procedure follow the same methodology used for the load forecasting modules.

The final selection includes holiday, temperature, relative humidity, precipitation, pressure, wind speed, condition code, and the sine transformation of the day of the week. Performance metrics for the single, restricted, and full model configurations are compared in Table 32. All three versions demonstrate comparable accuracy across the test set. While the full model technically achieves the highest precision, the improvement over the restricted version is negligible. This encourages the use of streamlined feature sets to build computationally efficient forecasting tools. Reducing the input requirements without sacrificing accuracy is a vital step towards creating lightweight models for modern grid infrastructure.

Metric	Single	Restricted	Full
MAE (A)	6.68	6.51	6.13
RMSE (A)	10.24	10.24	9.48

Table 32. Semi-bar current forecasting metrics.

Appendix B – Pilot 4

E-REDES Content Specification

Artifacts

This section presents the data artifacts shared within the scope of the project. These artifacts represent the structured data assets made available to support the project objectives and form the foundation for the datasets and data products described in the subsequent sections.

The data artifacts encompass both raw and curated data structures, enabling consistent data integration, analysis, and reuse across different business and technical use cases.

Artifact Name
P_4_01_E-REDES_NetworkConnections_AR
P_4_02_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_AR
P_4_03_E-REDES_ConnectionsNetworkPowerGenerationCentres_AR
P_4_04_E-REDES_ConnectionsElectricMobility_AR
P_4_05_E-REDES_SubstationCapacity_AR
P_4_06_E-REDES_NetworkConnectionRenewables_AR
P_4_07_E-REDES_TelcoAbleInfrastructures_AR
P_4_08_E-REDES_TelcoAbleInfrastructures_Poles_RAW_AR
P_4_09_E-REDES_TelcoAbleInfrastructures_LineSegments_RAW_AR
P_4_10_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_Arms_RAW_AR
P_4_11_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_Columns_RAW_AR
P_4_12_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_Specialized_RAW_AR

P_4_01_E-REDES_NetworkConnections_AR

Summary

Monthly number of completed network connection requests by municipality, covering new connections, power increases, public lighting, network modifications, and self-consumption, provided for indicative and analytical purposes.

Description

This artifact provides monthly information on the number of network connection requests completed, aggregated by municipality. It covers a range of connection related activities within the electricity distribution network, including new network connections, power increases, public lighting connections, network modifications, self-consumption connections, and other related service requests.

The information is extracted from EREDES operational systems and reflects the status of completed requests at the time of data collection. Given the dynamic nature of network connection

points, grid configurations, and consumption and production values, the data represents an approximation and may be subject to subsequent updates or revisions. Occasional omissions or inaccuracies may also occur because of system updates or data collection timing.

This artifact is intended to support monitoring and analysis of network connection activity, workload trends, and service demand evolution at the municipal level. It is provided for informational and analytical purposes only and does not replace the need for direct consultation with EREDES to obtain the most up-to-date or operationally binding information. EREDES does not assume liability for decisions or actions taken based on the use of this data without appropriate validation.

E-REDES Open Data portal reference:

- <https://e-redes.opendatasoft.com/explore/dataset/16-pedidos-concluidos-plrs/table/>

Data Quality Rules

Name	Description	Dimension	Rule Condition
p401_non_negative_pedidos_executados	The field "pedidos_ligacao_rede_executados_nr" should be greater than or equal to 0.	Accuracy	pedidos_ligacao_rede_executados_nr >= 0

P_4_02_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_AR

Summary

Public lighting characterisation by district, county, and parish, including number of luminaires, lighting technology, and installed power, provided for indicative and analytical purposes.

Description

This artifact provides a characterisation of public lighting infrastructure across administrative territories, organised by district, county, and parish. It includes information on the number of luminaires, the lighting technology used, and the installed electrical power associated with public lighting systems in each geographic area.

The information is sourced from EREDES systems and reflects the network conditions at the time of data collection. Given the dynamic nature of the electricity distribution network, connection points, and consumption and production values, the data represents an approximation and may be subject to subsequent updates or revisions. Occasional omissions or inaccuracies, including those related to asset location, may occur because of system updates or data collection timing.

This artifact is intended to support infrastructure management, energy planning, and analytical activities related to public lighting. It is provided for informational purposes only and does not replace the need for direct consultation with EREDES to obtain updated or operationally binding information. EREDES does not assume liability for decisions or actions taken based on the use of this data without appropriate validation.

E-REDES Open Data portal reference:

- https://e-redes.opendatasoft.com/explore/dataset/cadastro_iluminacao_publica/table/

Data Quality Rules

Name	Description	Dimension	Rule Condition
p402_non_negative_luminarias	The field "luminarias" should be greater than or equal to 0.	Accuracy	luminarias >= 0
p402_non_negative_lampadas	The field "lampadas" should be greater than or equal to 0.	Accuracy	lampadas >= 0
p402_non_negative_potencia_instalada_total	The field "potencia_instalada_total" should be greater than or equal to 0.	Accuracy	potencia_instalada_total >= 0

P_4_03_E-REDES_ConnectionsNetworkPowerGenerationCentres_AR

Summary

Monthly number of new Small Production Units (UPAC) completed by municipality and connection power, provided for indicative analysis and planning purposes.

Description

This artifact provides monthly information on the number of new Small Production Units (UPAC) with completed connection to the electricity distribution network, aggregated by municipality and connection power. It enables visibility into the evolution of small-scale decentralised generation, including self-consumption installations, across geographic areas and capacity ranges.

The information is extracted from EREDES systems and reflects the status of completed UPAC connections at the time of data collection. Due to the inherently dynamic nature of connection points, grid configuration, and consumption and production values, the data represents an approximation and may be subject to subsequent updates or revisions. Occasional omissions or inaccuracies, including those related to geographic location or classification, may occur because of system updates or data collection timing.

This artifact is intended to support monitoring, analysis, and planning activities related to distributed generation, network impact assessment, and energy transition initiatives. It is provided for informational and analytical purposes only and does not replace the need for direct consultation with EREDES to obtain the most current or operationally binding information. EREDES does not assume liability for decisions or actions taken based on the use of this data without appropriate validation.

E-REDES Open Data portal reference:

- <https://e-redes.opendatasoft.com/explore/dataset/26-centrais/table/>

Data Quality Rules

Name	Description	Dimension	Rule Condition
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p403_non_negative_processos_concluidos	The field "processos_concluidos_nr" should be greater than or equal to 0.	Accuracy	processos_concluidos_nr >= 0
p403_non_negative_potencia_ligacao	The field "potencia_ligacao" should be greater than or equal to 0.	Accuracy	potencia_ligacao >= 0

P_4_04_E-REDES_ConnectionsElectricMobility_AR

Summary

Monthly number of new grid connections related to electric mobility, integrated into the Mobi.e network, aggregated by municipality and provided for indicative analysis and planning purposes.

Description

This artifact provides monthly information on the number of new connections to the electricity distribution grid associated with Electric Mobility, aggregated by municipality. It includes grid connections related to electric mobility infrastructure that is integrated into the Mobi.e network, supporting the deployment and expansion of electric vehicle charging solutions.

The information is sourced from EREDES systems and reflects the status of completed grid connections at the time of data collection. Given the dynamic nature of connection points, the electricity distribution network, and associated consumption patterns, the data represents an approximation and may be subject to subsequent updates or revisions. Occasional omissions or inaccuracies, including those related to geographic location or classification, may occur due to system updates or data collection timing.

This artifact is intended to support monitoring and analysis of electric mobility infrastructure growth, network planning, and energy transition initiatives at the municipal level. It is provided for informational and analytical purposes only and does not replace the need for direct consultation with EREDES to obtain updated or operationally binding information. EREDES does not assume liability for decisions or actions taken based on the use of this data without appropriate validation.

E-REDES Open Data portal reference:

- <https://e-redes.opendatasoft.com/explore/dataset/9-plr-mobilidade-eletrica/table/>

Data Quality Rules

Name	Description	Dimension	Rule Condition
p404_ano_not_null	The field "ano" should not be null.	Completeness	ano IS NOT NULL
p404_valid_mes	The field "mes" should represent a valid calendar month.	Validity	mes BETWEEN 1 AND 12
p404_non_negative_pedidos_executados	The field "pedidos_ligacao_rede_executados_nr" should be greater than or equal to 0.	Accuracy	pedidos_ligacao_rede_executados_nr >= 0

P_4_05_E-REDES_SubstationCapacity_AR

Summary

Georeferenced data on HV/MV substations, MV areas of influence, and available and forecasted hosting capacity for power generation, provided for indicative planning and subject to validation with EREDES.

Description

This artifact provides georeferenced information on High Voltage / Medium Voltage (HV/MV) substations within the electricity distribution network, including the associated geographic areas of influence of Medium Voltage (MV) lines and the available hosting capacity for power generation. The data includes both quarterly updated values and forecasted hosting capacity, offering visibility into current and expected network capacity for integrating new generation.

For each HV/MV substation, the hosting capacity at the high and medium voltage bus(es) is estimated based on the capacity already occupied by existing electricity production centres, as well as those with a confirmed or compromised connection to the Distribution Grid. The information is extracted from EREDES systems and reflects network conditions at the time of data collection.

The information provided represents an approximation of substation characteristics, MV network conditions, and available hosting capacity, recognising the inherently dynamic nature of connection points, grid topology, and consumption and generation values. As such, the data may be subject to subsequent changes, updates, or corrections, including occasional inaccuracies related to asset location.

This artifact is intended for indicative and planning purposes only. It does not constitute a contractual proposal, does not guarantee connection to any specific point or asset, and does not replace the formal consultation process with EREDES for grid connection requests. EREDES reserves the right to evaluate, on a case-by-case basis, the most appropriate technical solution in accordance with applicable legal and regulatory obligations. EREDES does not assume liability for decisions or actions taken based on the use of this information without prior validation and confirmation.

E-REDES Open Data portal reference:

- <https://e-redes.opendatasoft.com/explore/dataset/capacidade-rececao-rnd/table/>

Data Quality Rules

Name	Description	Dimension	Rule Condition
p405_chave_not_null	The field "chave" should not be null.	Completeness	chave IS NOT NULL
p405_codigo_not_null	The field "codigo" should not be null.	Completeness	codigo IS NOT NULL
p405_instalacao_not_null	The field "instalacao" should not be null.	Completeness	instalacao IS NOT NULL

P_4_06_E-REDES_NetworkConnectionRenewables_AR

Summary

Monthly number of executed grid connection requests and associated connection power for new Renewable Production Units, including UPAC above 1 MW, aggregated by municipality and provided for indicative analysis.

Description

This artifact provides monthly information on the number of grid connection requests executed and the associated connection power for new Renewable Production Units, aggregated by municipality. It covers renewable generation projects connected to the electricity distribution network, including Small Production Units (UPAC) with installed power greater than 1 MW.

The information is sourced from EREDES systems and reflects the status of executed connection requests at the time of data collection. Given the dynamic nature of grid connection points, network topology, and consumption and production values, the data represents an approximation and may be subject to subsequent updates or revisions. Occasional omissions or inaccuracies, including those related to geographic location or classification, may occur due to system updates or data collection timing.

This artifact is intended to support monitoring and analysis of renewable generation integration, assessment of network connection activity, and planning activities related to the energy transition at the municipal level. It is provided for informational and analytical purposes only and does not replace the need for direct consultation with EREDES to obtain updated or operationally binding information. EREDES does not assume liability for decisions or actions taken based on the use of this data without appropriate validation.

E-REDES Open Data portal reference:

- <https://e-redes.opendatasoft.com/explore/dataset/25-plr-producao-renovavel/table/>

Data Quality Rules

Name	Description	Dimension	Rule Condition
p406_valid_ano	The field "ano" should represent a valid operational year.	Validity	ano BETWEEN 2000 AND 2100
p406_valid_mes	The field "mes" should represent a valid calendar month.	Validity	mes BETWEEN 1 AND 12
p406_non_negative_potencia_ligacao	The field "potencia_ligacao" should be greater than or equal to 0.	Accuracy	potencia_ligacao >= 0
p406_non_negative_pedidos_executados	The field "pedidos_ligacao_rede_executados_nr" should be greater than or equal to 0.	Accuracy	pedidos_ligacao_rede_executados_nr >= 0

P_4_07_E-REDES_TelcoAbleInfrastructures_AR

Summary

Georeferenced data on Low Voltage network poles suitable for telecommunications infrastructure use, in line with DL 123/2009, provided for indicative analysis and infrastructure sharing purposes.

Description

This artifact provides georeferenced information on poles of the Low Voltage (BT) electricity distribution network that are suitable for use by electronic communications network infrastructure, in accordance with DecreeLaw No. 123/2009 (DL 123/2009). It enables the

identification of existing electrical infrastructure that may support telecommunications deployments, promoting infrastructure sharing and efficient use of network assets.

The information is sourced from EREDES systems and reflects the status of the network at the time of data collection. Additional reference information on suitable infrastructure is available through the SIIA – Suitable Infrastructure Information System, managed by the national regulatory authority ANACOM, which serves as the official platform for infrastructure sharing information. Guidance on access conditions and procedures is also available via EREDES, in accordance with applicable regulatory and operational frameworks.

Given the dynamic nature of the electricity distribution network and associated assets, the data represents an approximation and may be subject to subsequent updates or revisions. Occasional omissions or inaccuracies, including those related to geographic location, may occur due to system updates or data collection timing. This artifact is provided for informational and analytical purposes only and does not replace the need for direct consultation with EREDES to obtain updated or operationally binding information. EREDES does not assume liability for decisions or actions taken based on the use of this data without appropriate validation.

References:

- E-REDES Open Data portal - <https://e-redes.opendatasoft.com/explore/dataset/apoios-baixa-tensao/table/>
- SIIA - Suitable Infrastructure Information System (ANACOM): <https://siia.anacom.pt/>
- EREDES - Access to Infrastructure Use: <https://www.e-redes.pt/pt-pt/clientes-e-parceiros/operadores-de-telecomunicacoes/espaco-em-postes-de-baixa-tensao>

Data Quality Rules

Name	Description	Dimension	Rule Condition
p407_non_negative_altura_m	The field "altura_m" should be greater than or equal to 0.	Accuracy	altura_m >= 0
p407_geometry_not_null	The field "geometry" should not be null.	Completeness	geometry IS NOT NULL

P_4_08_E-REDES_TelcoAbleInfrastructures_Poles_RAW_AR

Summary

Disaggregated raw data on Low Voltage network poles, including assets in exploration or reserve/disconnected status, provided as a foundational source for telecommunications related infrastructure analysis.

Description

This artifact provides disaggregated raw data at individual pole level for poles of the Low Voltage (BT) electricity distribution network. The artifact represents a foundational inventory of network assets, and, at this stage, no filtering or qualification has been applied to determine compliance with DecreeLaw No. 123/2009 (DL 123/2009) or suitability for telecommunications use.

The raw data includes only poles with asset status “In Exploration” or “In Reserve/Disconnected”, as recorded in EREDES systems at the time of data extraction. The information reflects the operational state of assets at the moment of collection and serves as the base layer for subsequent enrichment, filtering, and eligibility assessment in downstream artifacts and data products.

Given the dynamic nature of the electricity distribution network, asset status and attributes may change over time, and the information provided represents an approximation subject to updates or revisions. This artifact is provided strictly for informational, analytical, and integration purposes and does not constitute confirmation of infrastructure suitability, regulatory compliance, or availability for telecommunications deployment. Consultation with EREDES remains necessary for validated and operationally binding information.

Data Quality Rules

Name	Description	Dimension	Rule Condition
p408_valid_funcao	The field "funcao" should contain only allowed domain values.	Validity	funcao IN ("BT","IP","BT ramal")

P_4_09_E-REDES_TelcoAbleInfrastructures_LineSegments_RAW_AR

Summary

Raw data on isolated Low Voltage overhead line segments, provided without georeferencing for RGPD purposes and intended to be combined with pole data for infrastructure eligibility analysis.

Description

This artifact provides disaggregated raw data on isolated overhead line segments of the Low Voltage (BT) electricity distribution network. For RGPD and data protection purposes, these line segments are not georeferenced and do not contain spatial coordinates.

The artifact includes only line segments associated with assets in “In Exploration” or “In Reserve/Disconnected” status, as recorded in EREDES systems at the time of data collection. At this stage, the data has not been filtered or assessed for compliance with DecreeLaw No. 123/2009 (DL 123/2009) and does not, on its own, indicate suitability for telecommunications infrastructure deployment.

This raw artifact is designed to be combined with the Low Voltage poles raw artifact through the supplied foreign keys, enabling downstream processes to identify structural relationships between poles and overhead line segments. When integrated, these artifacts support the derivation of curated artifacts/datasets that determine which poles may be technically capable of supporting telecommunications infrastructure.

As with other raw network data, the information represents an approximation of network conditions and may be subject to updates or revisions. This artifact is provided for analytical and integration purposes only and does not replace the obligation to consult EREDES for validated, uptodate, or operationally binding information.

Data Quality Rules

Name	Description	Dimension	Rule Condition
p409_valid_situacao	The field "situacao" should contain only allowed domain values.	Validity	situacao IN ("Em exploração", "Desligado/Reserva")

P_4_10_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_Arms_RAW_AR

Summary

Disaggregated raw data on public lighting luminaires installed on arms, provided as a source for deriving aggregated public lighting characterisation.

Description

This artifact provides disaggregated raw data on public lighting luminaires installed on arms, representing one of the infrastructure components used in public lighting systems. The dataset includes asset level information that, in conjunction with other raw public lighting artifacts, supports the derivation of aggregated public lighting indicators by administrative territory.

The information is sourced from EREDES systems and reflects the status of public lighting assets at the time of data collection. Due to the dynamic nature of the electricity distribution network and associated lighting infrastructure, the data represents an approximation and may be subject to subsequent updates or revisions. Occasional omissions or inaccuracies may occur as a result of system updates or data collection timing.

This artifact is intended for analytical, integration, and transformation purposes, serving as an input to curated datasets and data products related to public lighting. It is provided for informational purposes only and does not replace the need for direct consultation with EREDES to obtain validated or operationally binding information. EREDES does not assume liability for decisions or actions taken based on the use of this data without appropriate validation.

Data Quality Rules

Name	Description	Dimension	Rule Condition
p410_valid_tipo_ip_braço	The field "tipo_ip" should indicate "Braço IP".	Validity	tipo_ip = "Braço IP"
p410_n_total_lampadas_match_structure	The field "n_total_lampadas" should equal "n_total_luminarias_existentes" multiplied by "n_lampadas_luminaria".	Consistency	n_total_lampadas = n_total_luminarias_existentes * n_lampadas_luminaria

P_4_11_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_Columns_RAW_AR

Summary

Disaggregated raw data on public lighting luminaires installed on columns, provided as a foundational source for public lighting aggregation and analysis.

Description

This artifact provides disaggregated raw data on public lighting luminaires installed on columns, capturing asset level details of one of the primary physical supports used in public lighting infrastructure. When combined with other raw public lighting datasets, this artifact enables the construction of a comprehensive view of public lighting assets.

The information is extracted from EREDES systems and reflects network and asset conditions at the time of data collection. Given the dynamic nature of public lighting infrastructure and associated network elements, the data represents an approximation and may be subject to updates or revisions. Occasional omissions or inaccuracies may occur due to system changes or timing of data extraction.

This artifact is intended to support data integration, transformation, and analytical processing within the project context. It is not intended for standalone operational use and does not replace the need for direct consultation with EREDES for updated or binding information. EREDES does not assume liability for decisions or actions taken based on the use of this data without appropriate validation.

Data Quality Rules

Name	Description	Dimension	Rule Condition
p411_non_negative_n_total_lampadas	The field "n_total_lampadas" should be greater than or equal to 0.	Accuracy	n_total_lampadas >= 0
p411_n_total_lampadas_match_structure	The field "n_total_lampadas" should equal "n_total_luminarias_existentes" multiplied by "n_lampadas_luminaria".	Consistency	n_total_lampadas = n_total_luminarias_existentes * n_lampadas_luminaria

P_4_12_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_Specialized_RAW_AR

Summary

Disaggregated raw data on specialised public lighting luminaires, provided as an input for deriving aggregated public lighting characterisation.

Description

This artifact provides disaggregated raw data on specialised public lighting luminaires, representing lighting installations that do not fall under standard arm or column-based configurations. The dataset contributes to a complete inventory of public lighting assets and, when combined with other raw public lighting artifacts, supports the derivation of curated public lighting datasets.

The information is sourced from EREDES systems and reflects asset conditions at the time of data collection. As public lighting infrastructure is subject to ongoing changes, the data represents an approximation and may be updated or revised over time. Occasional omissions or inaccuracies may occur due to system updates or data collection timing.

This artifact is provided for analytical and data transformation purposes and is intended to be used in conjunction with other public lighting raw datasets. It does not constitute a validated or operationally binding view of public lighting infrastructure and does not replace the need for direct

consultation with EREDES. EREDES does not assume liability for decisions or actions taken based on the use of this data without appropriate validation.

Data Quality Rules

Name	Description	Dimension	Rule Condition
p412_data_processamento_n ot_future	The field "data_processamento" should not represent a future date.	Timeliness	data_processamento <= CURRENT_DATE
p412_non_negative_n_total_l uminarias	The field "n_total_luminarias_existentes" should be greater than or equal to 0.	Accuracy	n_total_luminarias_existentes >= 0
p412_n_total_lampadas_matc h_structure	The field "n_total_lampadas" should equal "n_total_luminarias_existentes" multiplied by "n_lampadas_luminaria".	Consistency	n_total_lampadas = n_total_luminarias_existentes * n_lampadas_luminaria

Datasets

EREDES_GridConnectionsRenewables_DS

Artifacts

This dataset is composed by the following artifacts:

- P_4_03_E-REDES_ConnectionsNetworkPowerGenerationCentres_AR
- P_4_06_E-REDES_NetworkConnectionRenewables_AR

Summary

Executed grid connection requests and associated connection power for renewable and other power generation units, aggregated by municipality, time and connection power.

Description

This dataset provides monthly information on executed grid connection requests and the corresponding connection power for renewable production units and other power generation centres connected to the electricity distribution network. It includes data on Small Production Units (UPAC), including installations above 1 MW, supporting visibility into distributed generation integration.

The information is extracted from EREDES systems and reflects the status of executed connections at the time of data collection. Given the dynamic nature of network configuration,

connection points, and production capacity, the data represents an approximation and may be subject to subsequent updates or revisions.

This dataset supports monitoring of renewable integration, network planning, and energy transition analysis. It is provided for informational and analytical purposes only and does not replace formal consultation with EREDES for operational or contractual grid connection processes.

EREDES_GridConnectionsElectricMobility_DS

Artifacts

This dataset is composed by the following artifacts:

- P_4_04_E-REDES_ConnectionsElectricMobility_AR

Summary

Monthly executed grid connections related to electric mobility infrastructure, aggregated by municipality.

Description

This dataset provides monthly information on executed grid connections associated with electric mobility infrastructure, aggregated by municipality. It includes connections related to electric vehicle charging infrastructure integrated into the Mobi.e network, supporting analysis of electric mobility deployment and growth.

The information is sourced from EREDES systems and reflects the status of executed connections at the time of data collection. Due to the evolving nature of the electricity distribution network and electric mobility infrastructure, the data represents an approximation and may be subject to updates or revisions.

This dataset is intended to support monitoring, planning, and reporting activities related to electric mobility and the energy transition. It is provided for informational purposes only and does not replace the need for direct consultation with EREDES to obtain updated or binding information.

EREDES_GridConnections_DS

Artifacts

This dataset is composed by the following artifacts:

- P_4_01_E-REDES_NetworkConnections_AR

Summary

General executed network connection activity by municipality and time, covering multiple types of grid connection requests.

Description

This dataset provides monthly information on the number of executed network connection requests, aggregated by municipality. It covers a broad range of connection activities, including

new connections, power increases, public lighting connections, network modifications, self consumption connections, and other related requests.

The information is sourced from EREDES operational systems and reflects the status of executed requests at the time of data collection. Given the dynamic nature of the electricity distribution network and connection processes, the data represents an approximation and may be subject to subsequent updates or revisions.

This dataset supports operational monitoring, workload analysis, and demand trend assessment for grid connection activities. It is provided for informational and analytical purposes only and does not replace formal consultation with EREDES for validated or operationally binding information.

EREDES_PublicLightingInfrastructure_DS

Artifacts

This dataset is composed by the following artifacts:

- P_4_02_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_AR
- P_4_10_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_Arms_RAW_AR
- P_4_11_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_Columns_RAW_AR
- P_4_12_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_Specialized_RAW_AR

Summary

Aggregated and disaggregated data on public lighting infrastructure by administrative territory, including luminaires installed on columns, arms, and specialised supports, with associated technology and installed power.

Description

This dataset provides a comprehensive view of public lighting infrastructure across administrative territories, organised by district, county, and parish. It includes both curated aggregated indicators and disaggregated raw data on public lighting luminaires installed on columns, arms, and specialised supports, enabling consistent analysis at various levels of detail.

The dataset consolidates information on the number of luminaires, lighting technology, and installed electrical power, sourced from EREDES systems and reflecting the status of assets at the time of data collection. Given the dynamic nature of public lighting infrastructure and the electricity distribution network, the information represents an approximation and may be subject to subsequent updates or revisions.

This dataset is intended to support infrastructure management, energy planning, sustainability analysis, and policy development related to public lighting. It is provided for informational and analytical purposes only and does not replace the need for direct consultation with EREDES to obtain validated or operationally binding information.

EREDES_LowVoltageInfrastructureForTelecommunications_DS

Artifacts

This dataset is composed by the following artifacts:

- P_4_07_E-REDES_TelcoAbleInfrastructures_AR
- P_4_08_E-REDES_TelcoAbleInfrastructures_Poles_RAW_AR
- P_4_09_E-REDES_TelcoAbleInfrastructures_LineSegments_RAW_AR

Summary

Low Voltage network infrastructure data supporting analysis of potential telecommunications deployments, based on poles and overhead line segments.

Description

This dataset provides information on Low Voltage (BT) electricity distribution network infrastructure that can be used to support analysis of potential telecommunications infrastructure deployment. It includes both curated views and disaggregated raw data on poles and isolated overhead line segments, enabling structural and relational analysis of the network.

At the raw data level, the dataset represents a foundational inventory of assets without the application of eligibility filters or compliance assessment under DecreeLaw No. 123/2009. Poles and line segments can be combined through supplied foreign keys to support downstream derivation of telecommunications capable infrastructure.

The information is sourced from EREDES systems and reflects network conditions at the time of data collection. Due to the dynamic nature of the distribution network and associated assets, the data represents an approximation and may be subject to updates or revisions. This dataset is provided for analytical and planning purposes only and does not constitute confirmation of infrastructure suitability or availability.

EREDES_DistributionSubstationHostingCapacity_DS

Artifacts

This dataset is composed by the following artifacts:

- P_4_05_E-REDES_SubstationCapacity_AR

Summary

Georeferenced information on HV/MV substations, MV areas of influence, and available and forecasted hosting capacity for power generation in the distribution grid.

Description

This dataset provides information on High Voltage / Medium Voltage (HV/MV) substations, including associated Medium Voltage (MV) areas of influence and available and forecasted hosting capacity for power generation. Hosting capacity is evaluated considering existing electricity production centres and units with confirmed or committed connections to the distribution grid.

The information is extracted from EREDES systems and reflects network conditions at the time of data collection. Due to the dynamic nature of grid configuration, connection points, and consumption and generation values, the data represents an approximation and may be subject to subsequent updates or revisions.

This dataset is intended for indicative planning and analytical purposes, supporting network development, renewable integration assessment, and strategic decision-making. It does not constitute a contractual proposal, guarantee of connection, or binding technical solution, and does not replace the need for direct consultation with EREDES.

Data Products

EREDES_GridConnectionActivity_DP

Datasets

This data product is composed by the following datasets:

- EREDES_GridConnections_DS
- EREDES_GridConnectionsRenewables_DS
- EREDES_GridConnectionsElectricMobility_DS

Summary

Integrated view of executed grid connection activity across general connections, renewable generation, and electric mobility, supporting operational monitoring and energy transition analysis.

Description

This data product provides a unified and standardised view of executed grid connection activity within the electricity distribution network. It consolidates datasets covering general network connections, renewable power generation connections, and electric mobility-related connections, enabling consistent analysis across municipalities and time.

The data product includes information on the number of executed connection requests and, where applicable, associated connection power. The information is sourced from EREDES operational systems and reflects the status of executed connections at the time of data collection. Due to the dynamic nature of network configuration and connection processes, the information represents an approximation and may be subject to subsequent updates or revisions.

This data product is intended to support operational monitoring, workload management, planning activities, and energy transition reporting. It is provided for informational and analytical purposes only and does not replace formal consultation with EREDES for operational or contractual grid connection matters.

EREDES_DistributionHostingCapacity_DP

Datasets

This data product is composed by the following datasets:

- EREDES_DistributionSubstationHostingCapacity_DS

Summary

Indicative information on HV/MV substation hosting capacity for power generation, supporting distribution network planning and renewable integration analysis.

Description

This data product provides georeferenced information on High Voltage / Medium Voltage (HV/MV) substations, including associated Medium Voltage areas of influence and available and forecasted hosting capacity for power generation within the distribution grid.

Hosting capacity values are evaluated considering existing electricity production centers and units with confirmed or committed connections to the network. The information is extracted from EREDES systems and reflects network conditions at the time of data collection. Given the inherently dynamic nature of grid topology, connection points, and consumption and generation values, the data represents an approximation and may be subject to subsequent updates or revisions.

This data product is intended for indicative planning, strategic analysis, and regulatory transparency. It does not constitute a contractual proposal, guarantee of connection, or binding technical solution and does not replace the need for direct consultation with EREDES for grid connection requests.

E-REDES_PublicLightingInfrastructure_DP

Datasets

This data product is composed by the following datasets:

- EREDES_PublicLightingInfrastructure_DS

Summary

Comprehensive view of public lighting infrastructure by administrative territory, supporting asset management, energy efficiency, and sustainability initiatives.

Description

This data product provides a comprehensive characterisation of public lighting infrastructure across administrative territories, organised by district, county, and parish. It integrates aggregated indicators and disaggregated asset data related to public lighting luminaires installed on columns, arms, and specialised supports.

The data product includes information on the number of luminaires, lighting technology, and installed electrical power, sourced from EREDES systems and reflecting asset conditions at the time of data collection. Due to the evolving nature of public lighting infrastructure and the electricity distribution network, the information represents an approximation and may be subject to updates or revisions.

This data product supports infrastructure management, energy planning, efficiency assessments, and policy development related to public lighting. It is provided for informational and analytical purposes only and does not replace direct consultation with EREDES for validated or operationally binding information.

EREDES_TelecommunicationsSupportInfrastructure_DP

Datasets

This data product is composed by the following datasets:

- EREDES_LowVoltageInfrastructureForTelecommunications_DS

Summary

Low Voltage distribution network infrastructure data supporting analysis of potential telecommunications infrastructure deployment and infrastructure sharing.

Description

This data product provides information on Low Voltage electricity distribution network infrastructure that can support analysis of telecommunications infrastructure deployment. It integrates curated views and disaggregated raw data on poles and isolated overhead line segments, enabling assessment of structural relationships and potential infrastructure reuse.

At the raw data level, the information represents a foundational inventory of network assets without the application of eligibility filters or regulatory compliance assessment. Downstream processes may derive telecommunications capable infrastructure by combining poles and line segments using defined relationships.

The information is sourced from EREDES systems and reflects network conditions at the time of data collection. Given the dynamic nature of the distribution network and associated assets, the data represents an approximation and may be subject to updates or revisions. This data product is provided for analytical and planning purposes only and does not constitute confirmation of infrastructure suitability or availability.

EREDES_EnergyTransitionMonitoring_DP

Datasets

This data product is composed by the following datasets:

- EREDES_GridConnectionsRenewables_DS
- EREDES_GridConnectionsElectricMobility_DS
- EREDES_DistributionSubstationHostingCapacity_DS

Summary

Integrated view of renewable generation, electric mobility grid connections, and distribution network hosting capacity to support monitoring of the energy transition.

Description

This data product provides a consolidated view of key indicators supporting the energy transition within the electricity distribution network. It integrates datasets related to renewable generation grid connections, electric mobility infrastructure connections, and available and forecasted hosting capacity at HV/MV substations.

By combining connection activity with network capacity information, the data product enables monitoring of how renewable energy and electric mobility adoption evolve in relation to the distribution grid's ability to accommodate new demand and generation. The information is

sourced from EREDES systems and reflects network and connection status at the time of data collection.

Given the dynamic nature of grid conditions, connection processes, and consumption and generation values, the information represents an approximation and may be subject to subsequent updates or revisions. This data product is intended for analytical, planning, and reporting purposes, supporting strategic decision-making, regulatory transparency, and sustainability initiatives. It does not replace formal consultation with EREDES for operational or contractual matters.

EREDES_TerritorialInfrastructureOverview_DP

Datasets

This data product is composed by the following datasets:

- EREDES_PublicLightingInfrastructure_DS
- EREDES_GridConnections_DS
- EREDES_LowVoltageInfrastructureForTelecommunications_DS

Summary

Territorial overview of electricity distribution-related infrastructure and activity, supporting regional analysis and public infrastructure planning.

Description

This data product provides an integrated territorial perspective on infrastructure and activity associated with the electricity distribution network, organised by administrative geography. It combines information on public lighting infrastructure, general grid connection activity, and Low Voltage network assets relevant for telecommunications infrastructure analysis.

The data product supports a holistic understanding of how public lighting assets, network connection demand, and infrastructure sharing potential are distributed across municipalities and regions. It is particularly suited to regional planning, public policy analysis, and cross-sector infrastructure coordination.

The information is sourced from EREDES systems and reflects asset and network conditions at the time of data collection. As infrastructure and connection activity evolve continuously, the data represents an approximation and may be subject to updates or revisions. This data product is intended for informational and analytical use, supporting planning and coordination activities, and does not constitute operational or contractual commitments.

Govern

Domains

Name	Description
Electricity Distribution Network	Covers concepts related to the electricity distribution network, including grid assets, substations, network capacity, and grid connection processes.

	This domain supports planning, operation, and analysis of the distribution grid.
Grid Connections and Customer Access	Covers concepts related to requests for connection to the electricity distribution network, including general connections, renewable generation, electric mobility, and associated connection power and execution status.
Public Lighting Infrastructure	Covers concepts related to public lighting assets operated within the distribution network, including luminaires, supporting structures, lighting technologies, and installed power across administrative territories
Telecommunications Support Infrastructure	Covers concepts related to electricity distribution infrastructure that may support telecommunications deployment, including Low Voltage poles and overhead line segments used for infrastructure sharing analysis.

Glossaries

Name	Description	Associated Domains
Grid Assets Glossary	Defines key terms related to physical assets of the electricity distribution network, including substations, poles, and line segments.	Electricity Distribution Network Telecommunications Support Infrastructure
Grid Connections Glossary	Defines terms related to grid connection requests, execution status, connection power, and connection purposes.	Grid Connections and Customer Access
Hosting Capacity Glossary	Defines concepts related to the ability of the distribution grid to integrate power generation, including available and forecasted hosting capacity	Electricity Distribution Network
Public Lighting Glossary	Defines terms related to public lighting infrastructure, luminaires, technologies, and supporting structures.	Public Infrastructure Lighting
Telecommunications Infrastructure Glossary	Defines concepts related to the use of electricity distribution infrastructure for telecommunications purposes, including regulatory and structural aspects.	Telecommunications Support Infrastructure

Terms

Name	Short and Long Description	Associated Glossaries
Distribution Network	<p>Short Description</p> <p>The electricity network responsible for delivering power from transmission systems to end users.</p> <p>Long Description</p> <p>The distribution network comprises substations, lines, and associated assets that deliver electricity from the transmission network or local generation sources to consumers.</p>	Grid Assets Glossary

	It operates at High, Medium, and Low Voltage levels and is managed by the distribution system operator.	
Grid Connection Request	<p>Short Description</p> <p>A formal request to connect an installation or asset to the electricity distribution network.</p> <p>Long Description</p> <p>A grid connection request is submitted to EREDES to establish a new connection, modify an existing one, or connect production, consumption, or mobility infrastructure to the distribution network. Requests may relate to residential, commercial, public lighting, renewable generation, or electric mobility use cases.</p>	Grid Connections Glossary
Executed Connection	<p>Short Description</p> <p>A grid connection request that has been completed and implemented in the network.</p> <p>Long Description</p> <p>An executed connection refers to a grid connection request that has progressed through approval and technical implementation stages and has been physically completed in the electricity distribution network, as recorded in EREDES systems.</p>	Grid Connections Glossary
Connection Power	<p>Short Description</p> <p>The electrical power associated with a grid connection.</p> <p>Long Description</p> <p>Connection power represents the maximum electrical capacity agreed and implemented for a grid connection, expressed in kilowatts (kW) or megawatts (MW), and defines the allowable consumption or production capacity at the connection point.</p>	Grid Connections Glossary
Hosting Capacity	<p>Short Description</p> <p>The ability of the distribution network to accommodate additional power generation.</p> <p>Long Description</p> <p>Hosting capacity is an indicative measure of the amount of additional electricity generation that can be connected to a specific part of the distribution network without requiring major network reinforcements. It considers existing generation, committed connections, and network constraints at a given moment.</p>	Hosting Capacity Glossary
HV/MV Substation	<p>Short Description</p> <p>A substation connecting High Voltage and Medium Voltage networks.</p>	Grid Assets Glossary Hosting Capacity Glossary

	<p>Long Description</p> <p>An HV/MV substation is a network asset that transforms electricity from High Voltage to Medium Voltage levels and distributes power to downstream MV and LV networks. It is a key element for assessing grid capacity and hosting capability for new connections.</p>	
Public Lighting Luminaire	<p>Short Description</p> <p>A lighting unit installed as part of public lighting infrastructure.</p> <p>Long Description</p> <p>A public lighting luminaire is a lighting device installed on columns, arms, or specialised supports to illuminate public spaces. Luminaires are characterised by technology type, installed power, and location within administrative territories.</p>	Public Lighting Glossary
Lighting Technology	<p>Short Description</p> <p>The type of technology used by a public lighting luminaire.</p> <p>Long Description</p> <p>Lighting technology refers to the technical solution used by a luminaire to produce light, such as LED, sodium vapor, or other technologies, and influences energy consumption, efficiency, and maintenance requirements.</p>	Public Lighting Glossary
Low Voltage Pole	<p>Short Description</p> <p>A physical support structure in the Low Voltage distribution network.</p> <p>Long Description</p> <p>A Low Voltage pole is a structural asset used to support overhead electricity lines. Depending on technical and regulatory conditions, poles may be analyzed for potential use in supporting telecommunications infrastructure.</p>	Grid Assets Glossary Telecommunications Infrastructure Glossary
Overhead Line Segment	<p>Short Description</p> <p>A segment of overhead electricity line connecting network assets.</p> <p>Long Description</p> <p>An overhead line segment represents a portion of the electricity distribution network connecting poles or other assets. Line segments are used to model network topology and, when combined with pole data, support analysis of infrastructure sharing potential.</p>	Grid Assets Glossary Telecommunications Infrastructure Glossary
Electric Infrastructure	<p>Short Description</p> <p>Infrastructure supporting electric vehicle charging.</p>	Grid Connections Glossary

	<p>Long Description</p> <p>Electric mobility infrastructure includes charging points and associated installations connected to the electricity distribution network, often integrated into national platforms such as Mobi.e, supporting the deployment of electric vehicles.</p>	
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Data Product Publications

Publication EREDES_GridConnectionActivity_FTP_PUB

Token: ftp://<e-redes_user>:<e-redes_pw>@eu.ftp.huwise.com:21/grid_connection_activity

Data Product

Published Data Product:

- EREDES_GridConnectionActivity_DP

Description

Publication of the Data Product EREDES_GridConnectionActivity_DP to the E-REDES Open Data portal FTP. The resulting files are then automatically ingested by the portal via a harvester.

Publications / E-REDES_GridConnectionActivity_FTP_PUB

E-REDES_GridConnectionActivity_FTP_PUB Publications

Creation date	Last Edition	Unique Id	Version	Size
Mar 16 2026, 11:25:27	Mar 16 2026, 11:27:34	49bc7f7f-109a-4d17-8831-fed4552a6886	2	-

Description

Publication of the Data Product E-REDES_GridConnectionActivity_DP to the E-REDES Open Data portal FTP. The resulting files are then automatically ingested by the portal via a harvester.

Portal

opendatasoft

- index.csv
- P_4_01_E-REDES_NetworkConnections_AR.csv
- P_4_03_E-REDES_ConnectionsNetworkPowerGenerationCentres_AR.csv
- P_4_04_E-REDES_ConnectionsElectricMobility_AR.csv
- P_4_06_E-REDES_NetworkConnectionRenewables_AR.csv
- schema_P_4_01_E-REDES_NetworkConnections_AR.csv
- schema_P_4_03_E-REDES_ConnectionsNetworkPowerGenerationCentres_AR.csv
- schema_P_4_04_E-REDES_ConnectionsElectricMobility_AR.csv
- schema_P_4_06_E-REDES_NetworkConnectionRenewables_AR.csv

Publication EREDES_DistributionHostingCapacity_FTP_PUB

Data Product

Token: ftp://<e-redes_user>:<e-redes_pw>@eu.ftp.huwiese.com:21/distribution_hosting_capacity

Published Data Product:

- EREDES_DistributionHostingCapacity_DP

Description

Publication of the Data Product E-REDES_DistributionHostingCapacity_DP to the E-REDES Open Data portal FTP. The resulting files are then automatically ingested by the portal via a harvester.

The screenshot shows the publication details for 'E-REDES_DistributionHostingCapacity_FTP_PUB'. The page includes a breadcrumb trail 'Publications / E-REDES_DistributionHostingCapacity_FTP_PUB', a 'Publications' button, and a table with the following data:

Creation date	Last Edition	Unique Id	Version	Size
Mar 16 2026, 11:33:48	Mar 16 2026, 11:33:48	0589f8ff-8678-4e62-853f-cb47a3472a8c	3	-

The description states: 'Publication of the Data Product E-REDES_DistributionHostingCapacity_DP to the E-REDES Open Data portal FTP. The resulting files are then automatically ingested by the portal via a harvester.' The portal is identified as 'opendatasoft'.

```

x icon index.csv
x icon P_4_05_E-REDES_SubstationCapacity_AR_opendatasoft_version_3.csv
x icon schema_P_4_05_E-REDES_SubstationCapacity_AR_opendatasoft_version_3.csv

```

Publication EREDES_PublicLightingInfrastructure_FTP_PUB

Data Product

Token: ftp://<e-redes_user>:<e-redes_pw>@eu.ftp.huwiese.com:21/public_lighting_infrastructure

Published Data Product:

- EREDES_PublicLightingInfrastructure_DP

Description

Publication of the Data Product E-REDES_PublicLightingInfrastructure_DP to the E-REDES Open Data portal FTP. The resulting files are then automatically ingested by the portal via a harvester.

Publications / E-REDES_PublicLightingInfrastructure_FTP_PUB

E-REDES_PublicLightingInfrastructure_FTP_PUB Publications

Creation date	Last Edition	Unique Id	Version	Size
Mar 16 2026, 11:41:33	Mar 16 2026, 11:41:33	9a03b85b-7271-4da6-8d46-e1ea9cf27bb8	3	-

Description

Publication of the Data Product E-REDES_PublicLightingInfrastructure_DP to the E-REDES Open Data portal FTP. The resulting files are then automatically ingested by the portal via a harvester.

Portal

opendatasoft

```

x a index.csv
x a P_4_02_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_AR.csv
x a P_4_10_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_Arms_RAW_AR.csv
x a P_4_11_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_Columns_RAW_AR.csv
x a P_4_12_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_Specialized_RAW_AR.csv
x a schema_P_4_02_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_AR.csv
x a schema_P_4_10_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_Arms_RAW_AR.csv
x a schema_P_4_11_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_Columns_RAW_AR.csv
x a schema_P_4_12_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_Specialized_RAW_AR.csv

```

Publication EREDES_TelecommunicationsSupportInfrastructure_FTP_PUB

Data Product

Token: ftp://<e-redes_user>:<e-redes_pw>@eu.ftp.huwise.com:21/telecommunication_support_infrastructure

Published Data Product:

- EREDES_TelecommunicationsSupportInfrastructure_DP

Description

Publication of the Data Product E-REDES_TelecommunicationsSupportInfrastructure_DP to the E-REDES Open Data portal FTP. The resulting files are then automatically ingested by the portal via a harvester.

Publications / E-REDES_TelecommunicationsSupportInfrastructure_FTP_PUB

E-REDES_TelecommunicationsSupportInfrastructure_FTP_PUB Publications

Creation date	Last Edition	Unique Id	Version	Size
Mar 16 2026, 11:47:57	Mar 16 2026, 11:47:57	2d70c89f-16a8-4957-9fa5-af69202d4a5d	3	-

Description

Publication of the Data Product E-REDES_TelecommunicationsSupportInfrastructure_DP to the E-REDES Open Data portal FTP. The resulting files are then automatically ingested by the portal via a harvester.

Portal
opendatasoft

```

x a index.csv
x a P_4_07_E-REDES_TelcoAbleInfrastructures_AR.csv
x a P_4_08_E-REDES_TelcoAbleInfrastructures_Poles_RAW_AR.csv
x a P_4_09_E-REDES_TelcoAbleInfrastructures_LineSegments_RAW_AR.csv
x a schema_P_4_07_E-REDES_TelcoAbleInfrastructures_AR.csv
x a schema_P_4_08_E-REDES_TelcoAbleInfrastructures_Poles_RAW_AR.csv
x a schema_P_4_09_E-REDES_TelcoAbleInfrastructures_LineSegments_RAW_AR.csv

```

Publication EREDES_EnergyTransitionMonitoring_FTP_PUB

Data Product

Token: ftp://<e-redes_user>:<e-
redes_pw>@eu.ftp.huwise.com:21/energy_transition_monitoring

Published Data Product:

- EREDES_EnergyTransitionMonitoring_DP

Description

Publication of the Data Product E-REDES_EnergyTransitionMonitoring_DP to the E-REDES Open Data portal FTP. The resulting files are then automatically ingested by the portal

via a harvester.

Publications / E-REDES_EnergyTransitionMonitoring_FTP_PUB

E-REDES_EnergyTransitionMonitoring_FTP_PUB

Publications

Creation date	Last Edition	Unique Id	Version	Size
Mar 16 2026, 11:53:42	Mar 16 2026, 11:53:42	743a9c41-d316-4d80-834f-35c4f13918c6	3	-

Description

Publication of the Data Product E-REDES_EnergyTransitionMonitoring_DP to the E-REDES Open Data portal FTP. The resulting files are then automatically ingested by the portal via a harvester.

Portal

opendatasoft

```

x a index.csv
x a P_4_03_E-REDES_ConnectionsNetworkPowerGenerationCentres_AR.csv
x a P_4_04_E-REDES_ConnectionsElectricMobility_AR.csv
x a P_4_05_E-REDES_SubstationCapacity_AR.csv
x a P_4_06_E-REDES_NetworkConnectionRenewables_AR.csv
x a schema_P_4_03_E-REDES_ConnectionsNetworkPowerGenerationCentres_AR.csv
x a schema_P_4_04_E-REDES_ConnectionsElectricMobility_AR.csv
x a schema_P_4_05_E-REDES_SubstationCapacity_AR.csv
x a schema_P_4_06_E-REDES_NetworkConnectionRenewables_AR.csv

```

Publication EREDES_TerritorialInfrastructureOverview_FTP_PUB

Data Product

Token: ftp://<e-redes_user>:<e-
redes_pw>@eu.ftp.huwise.com:21/territorial_infrastructure_overview

Published Data Product:

- EREDES_TerritorialInfrastructureOverview_DP

Description

Publication of the Data Product E-REDES_TerritorialInfrastructureOverview_DP to the E-REDES Open Data portal FTP. The resulting files are then automatically ingested by the portal via a harvester.

Publications / E-REDES_TerritorialInfrastructureOverview_FTP_PUB

E-REDES_TerritorialInfrastructureOverview_FTP_PUB Publications

Creation date	Last Edition	Unique Id	Version	Size
Mar 16 2026, 11:59:17	Mar 16 2026, 11:59:17	e2591238-aa89-4ed8-9350-dda5374073bc	3	-

Description

Publication of the Data Product E-REDES_TerritorialInfrastructureOverview_DP to the E-REDES Open Data portal FTP. The resulting files are then automatically ingested by the portal via a harvester.

Portal

opendatasoft

- index.csv
- P_4_01_E-REDES_NetworkConnections_AR.csv
- P_4_02_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_AR.csv
- P_4_07_E-REDES_TelcoAbleInfrastructures_AR.csv
- P_4_08_E-REDES_TelcoAbleInfrastructures_Poles_RAW_AR.csv
- P_4_09_E-REDES_TelcoAbleInfrastructures_LineSegments_RAW_AR.csv
- P_4_10_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_Arms_RAW_AR.csv
- P_4_11_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_Columns_RAW_AR.csv
- P_4_12_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_Specialized_RAW_AR.csv
- schema_P_4_01_E-REDES_NetworkConnections_AR.csv
- schema_P_4_02_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_AR.csv
- schema_P_4_07_E-REDES_TelcoAbleInfrastructures_AR.csv
- schema_P_4_08_E-REDES_TelcoAbleInfrastructures_Poles_RAW_AR.csv
- schema_P_4_09_E-REDES_TelcoAbleInfrastructures_LineSegments_RAW_AR.csv
- schema_P_4_10_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_Arms_RAW_AR.csv
- schema_P_4_11_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_Columns_RAW_AR.csv
- schema_P_4_12_E-REDES_PublicLightingLuminaires_Specialized_RAW_AR.csv

E-REDES_PublicLightingInfrastructure_DP_EDC_PUBData Product

Data Product

Token:<empty>

Published Data Product:

- E-REDES_PublicLightingInfrastructure_DP

Description

Publication of Data Product E-REDES_PublicLightingInfrastructure_DP to the EDC connector.

Access Policy:

```

{
  "permissions": [
    {
      "target": "",
      "assigner": "",
      "assignee": "",
      "action": "use",
      "constraints": [
        {
          "type": "location",
          "locations": [
            "eu"
          ]
        }
      ]
    },
    {
      "target": "",
      "assigner": "",
      "assignee": "",
      "action": "use",
      "constraints": [
        {
          "type": "purpose",
          "purposes": [
            "research"
          ]
        }
      ]
    },
    {
      "target": "",
      "assigner": "",
      "assignee": "",
      "action": "use",
      "constraints": [
        {
          "type": "time_interval",
          "lower_bound": "2026-01-01T00:00:00+00:00",
          "upper_bound": "2026-12-31T00:00:00+00:00"
        }
      ]
    }
  ],
  "prohibitions": [
    {
      "target": "",
      "assigner": "",
      "assignee": "",
      "action": "use",
      "constraints": [
        {
          "type": "purpose",
          "purposes": [
            "commercial"
          ]
        }
      ]
    }
  ],
  "obligations": null
}

```

Access Policy ODRL Format:

```

{
  "@context": {
    "@vocab": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/"
  },
  "@id": "policy_research_eu_2026",
  "policy": {
    "@context": "http://www.w3.org/ns/odrl.jsonld",
    "@type": "Set",
    "permission": [
      {
        "action": "use",
        "constraint": [
          {
            "@type": "AtomicConstraint",
            "leftOperand": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/timeInterval",
            "rightOperand": {
              "@type": "xsd:dateTime",
              "@value": "2026-01-01T00:00:00+00:00"
            },
            "operator": {
              "@id": "odrl:gteq"
            }
          },
          {
            "@type": "AtomicConstraint",
            "leftOperand": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/timeInterval",
            "rightOperand": {
              "@type": "xsd:dateTime",
              "@value": "2026-12-31T00:00:00+00:00"
            },
            "operator": {
              "@id": "odrl:lteq"
            }
          }
        ]
      },
      {
        "action": "use",
        "constraint": [
          {
            "@type": "AtomicConstraint",
            "odrl:leftOperand": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/location",
            "rightOperand": {
              "@type": "xsd:string",
              "@value": "eu"
            },
            "operator": {
              "@id": "odrl:eq"
            }
          }
        ]
      },
      {
        "action": "use",
        "constraint": {
          "@type": "AtomicConstraint",
          "odrl:leftOperand": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/purpose",
          "rightOperand": {
            "@type": "xsd:string",
            "@value": "research"
          },
          "operator": {
            "@id": "odrl:eq"
          }
        }
      }
    ]
  }
}

```



```
    ],  
    "prohibition": [  
      {  
        "action": "use",  
        "constraint": {  
          "@type": "AtomicConstraint",  
          "odrl:leftOperand": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/purpose",  
          "rightOperand": {  
            "@type": "xsd:string",  
            "@value": "commercial"  
          },  
          "operator": {  
            "@id": "odrl:eq"  
          }  
        }  
      }  
    ],  
    "obligation": []  
  }  
}
```